

**Digital discourse and the power and paradox of patriarch in diaspora
entrepreneurship**

Azhar Uddin Ahmed

**Thesis submitted to University of the West of Scotland for the degree of
Doctor of Business Administration, January, 2021.**

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

First of all, I would like to thank almighty Allah, who has given me enormous strength to accomplish this long journey.

I would like to express the heartiest gratitude to my mentor and supervisor, Dr Matthew Frew, for his endless active guidance throughout the course. His undoubted skills, knowledge, motivating power, excitement, endurance, generosity and pleasant nature inspired me all the time and helped me to complete this endeavour.

I would also like to thank the rest of the panel members of the thesis: Dr Karina McGowan and Theofilos Tzandis, for their insightful thoughts, comments, criticism and motivations throughout the course.

My earnest appreciation also goes to the library crews (UWS Paisley campus), members of the International student support team, admission team and all other people in the University of the West of Scotland I have come across during the study for their unequivocal care.

I would also like to express sincere respect to my parents Mr Akhtar Uddin Ahmed and Mrs Mina Begum, for their moral support. Thanks also go to the rest of the family members, friends and colleagues in the University for their direct and indirect assistance.

I am also incredibly indebted to Naga Sailander Kumar Gubbala for the huge financial support that I received for this project.

Last but not least, warm appreciation goes to my partner Rubina Hayat for her divine and unconditional encouragement and mental support throughout the DBA exploration.

ABSTRACT

This study aims to explore critically how cultural heritage impacts the utilization of the power and potential of social media as a business strategy among small food retail businesses. The culturally driven South-Asian diaspora own small family businesses in the context of this study. This area has become potential due to a narrow focus on the view of social media in diasporic family business strategy that has been done on the previous research. Moreover, Bourdieusian habitus, field and capital theory have not been applied widely before to interpret the behaviours and dispositions of the agents, power struggles in the field of family and business concerning the social media usage and finally identify the different forms of capitals and their transformations in the diasporic family businesses. Therefore, this study addresses the shortcomings by using Bourdieusian lenses. A case study approach was adopted to answer the research question, and the Scottish index of multiple deprivations (SIMD) was used to locate shops in Glasgow for unstructured interviews and ethnographic observations. The study revealed the key findings which highlight the discourses of disruption, technophobia and influencer network, ethnic enclaves: cultural cryostasis and capitals of containment, privilege and poverty: digital adoption and diaspora, entrepreneurship and digital discourse: the paradox of patriarchy and prosperity. This paper implies that it informs the patriarchal nature of the family business that causes intergenerational conflicts in the business operations. Therefore, social media adoption in the business is considered a challenge or threat to the cultural heritage of the family business. Furthermore, it also informs that the other cultural heritages of South-Asian diaspora like gender dominance, involvement of Islamic faith in daily life and community involvement in the decision-making

process are also considered key factors of implementing social media as a business strategy.

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ABBREVIATIONS

COVID-19= Corona virus diseases-19

ICT= Information and communication technology

SIMD= Scottish index of multiple deprivation

SME= Small and medium-sized enterprise

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1.0 INTRODUCTION

Social media and smart technologies have undoubtedly become the most ubiquitous form of engagement in the 'Networked society' since the beginning of the twenty-first century (Vodanovich, Sundaram and Myers, 2010; Harris, Rae and Misner, 2012). It

is now imminent that people are constantly on social media for personal and business issues while walking down local high streets, pubs, and supermarkets. Social media enables multiple users to execute a range of social interactions through an internet-based platform across a space of flows and timeless time (Scott and Orlikowski, 2014). Social media is a general term used for describing a group of platforms that appear in different forms like social networking sites, e.g. Facebook; Business networking sites, e.g. LinkedIn; Microblogging sites, e.g. Twitter; Audio-video sharing platforms, e.g. YouTube; Picture sharing sites, e.g. Pinterest, Flickr etc.; Virtual sites, e.g. Second Life and various others manifestations (Whiting and Williams, 2013; Valos et al. 2016). Platforms should have some key characteristics to become a part of the social media family. Those pointed out by Kaplan and Haenlein (2010) as platforms must be built ideologically and technologically on the base of Web 2.0, and they must allow the users to create and exchange the contents. Communication through social media is not confined only to personal purposes. It is now evident that along with a surprising number of personal social media users (Kane et al. 2014; Boyd and Ellison, 2007), a KPMG study reveals around 75% of organisations are now using any sort of social media for communicating purposes regardless of its size and area of businesses (Kiron et al. 2012). The scholars describe the impact of Web 2.0 technologies in different studies over time as a dynamic communication tool that has been adopted profusely by all ages of people and leading an extensive shift in communications habits with impressive outcomes (Bernoff and Li, 2010; Li and Shiu, 2012).

The rapid rise of the phenomenon of 'social media' is attracting scholars from a wide range of disciplines (Aral, Dellarocas and Godes, 2013), but it is a challenging job for them to manage pace with working on it (Treem and Leonardi, 2013). Scholars

described social media as an eloquent target with its constant brisk development characteristics (Hogan and Quan-Haase, 2010; Kane et al., 2014). Some research suggests that the rapidly changing nature of the platforms will outpace the user's capability to capitalise it when moving criteria reach their peak (Dijck, 2013). A growing number of studies has contributed various perceptions into the inference of social media usage for the organisations (Treem and Leonardi, 2013; Scott and Orlikowski, 2014; Koch, Leidner and Gonzalez, 2013; Leonardi, 2014). In most cases, those studies have emphasised the internal utilisation of social media, particularly by large multinational companies (Huang, Baptista and Galliers, 2013; Leonardi, Huysman and Steinfield, 2013).

In the context of large organisations, the research studies have pointed out different affordable communicational consequences which were formerly unachievable (Treem and Leonardi, 2013). Particularly it was thought that social media usage is only to deepen knowledge sharing and improve communication among the geographically scattered organisations (Huang, Baptista and Galliers, 2013). However, the literature on social media relatively becomes biased because of scholars' nearly undivided attention on the large companies. One of the outcomes of this bias is that researchers are liable to build theory established on the incorrect speculation that users will use and explain the social media similarly based on almost steady characteristics of the social media platform (Huang, Baptista and Galliers, 2013; Koch, Leidner and Gonzalez, 2013).

The economic growth is determined largely by its small and medium-sized business sector (Bahaddad, AlGhamdi and Houghton, 2012; Acs. et al., 1997; Fong, 2011). This is because they have a huge impact on the national economy, particularly by creating job opportunities. For that reason, the Small and medium-sized business

sector is considered as one of the crucial and necessary elements of high-tech society (Rahayu and Day, 2015).

In the age of globalisation, rapid and consistent changes in technology put all forms of businesses to face more challenges in the competitive environment (Skoko, Ceric and Huang, 2008). Therefore, businesses need to assimilate Information & communication technology to reinforce their ventures (Sambamurthy, Bharadwaj and Grover, 2003). This information and communication technology (ICT) has become a compulsory tool for boosting the economy (Oliveira and Martins, 2011) and a major source of competition in the business (Stroeken, 2001).

Conversely, it is well evident that, like large businesses, small ones do not have enough capacity to embrace the Information and communication technology (ICT) in their organisational setting, which has become the indispensable means of maintaining and increasing stability (Kapurubandara, 2009). But the dissemination process in the small businesses is still stagnant despite this factual evidence (Gibbs, Sequeira and White, 2007). Therefore, to hold their position in the business field, small organisations should continue to emphasise the effort of developing and implementing the latest technologies even though having scarce funds, that might usually be legitimate for small and medium-sized businesses (Yang, Lee and Lee, 2007; Beck and Demirguc-Kunt, 2006).

Businesses can use numerous types of Information and communication technology tools in their settings, including social media. Scholars argued that social media is one of the latest ways of performing business activities, and it can change the traditional operation procedures by transforming them (Aral, Dellarocas and Godes, 2013; Andzulis, Panagopoulos and Rapp, 2012). Social media have become a new

modern age or marketing phenomenon to drive businesses into the future. Business organisations have progressively adopted social media at different levels, and such type of adoption is likely to increase in the coming days (Levy, 2009; Andriole, 2010). All forms of organisations can recognise the power and potentiality of social media regardless of size (Nah and Saxton, 2012). Businesses get many benefits from using social media in almost every area, including marketing, branding a product, advertising and promotion, research & development, building and maintaining customers' rapport, and so on (Ainin et al., 2015; Weber, 2013). Certainly, the advantages derived from social media are not only reserved for larger organisations anymore; small and medium-sized businesses can also be the beneficiary if they adopt in right time (He, Wang and Zha, 2014; Meske and Stieglitz, 2013; Wamba and Carter, 2014; Verheyden and Goeman, 2013).

Kim, Lee and Lee (2013) denoted that Web 2.0, specifically social media in the small and medium-sized businesses, is gaining momentum. In 2015, the social media platform LinkedIn carried out a survey on 456 SMEs in the UK, where 75% of them think of social media as an effective marketing tool to their business (Pickup, 2016). This percentage gives a positive indication of an increase in understanding social media use by small and medium-sized businesses. Furthermore, Small and medium-sized enterprises (SME) towards social media also indicates that they have recognised the benefits of Web 2.0 presence. Subsequently, it will also enable them to face challenges and take appropriate steps to solve the issues caused by social media in the business operation (Jagongo and Kinyua, 2013; Mannonen and Runonen, 2008).

Scholars identified that despite having numerous benefits and an increasing number of social media adopters in SMEs, the literature suggests an insignificant number of

small and medium-sized businesses have been compromised by the perceived advantages and value-added service of social media (Saldanha and Krishnan, 2012; Peltier, Zhao and Schibrowsky, 2012).

Mainly from two perspectives, most of the research was carried out on the adoption of social media. The first one is all about the usage and impact on the Individual level, and the other is on the context of organisations (Hu and Wang, 2012; Bertot, Jaeger and Hansen, 2012; Fischer and Reuber, 2011). In the organisational context, a significant amount of research has been done on public affairs and non-profit or charitable organisations (Nah and Saxton, 2012; Curtis et al., 2010). However, in terms of social media adoption, the majority of the literature emphasises larger organisations, and an insignificant number of studies have been dedicated to SMEs (Meske and Stieglitz, 2013).

It is not widely known about the underlying factors to embrace or reject Web 2.0 technologies by small and medium-sized firms (Vlachvei and Notta, 2014) because of the shortcomings in the research study (Durkin, McGowan and McKeown, 2013). The importance of social media on SMEs needs further attention, and therefore more study is required on the embrace and application (Aral, Dellarocas and Godes, 2013; He, Wang and Zha, 2014; Kim, Lee and Lee, 2013). Among the factors, the culture of the business owner plays a vital role in the inclusion or exclusion of new technology in the business. Business owners of all SMEs in the UK are not of the same nationality. The approach towards adopting new technologies in the business by indigenous white British would not be the same by other nationalities who have also been doing business for a long time in the same environment. The number of diaspora owned family businesses are increasing rapidly in the UK, and among them, a significant number of SMEs are run by south Asian diaspora communities.

Current literature shows that most of the studies on these SMEs are run by indigenous people. Very little focus has been given to those which are run by the diaspora communities in the UK. From this point of view, this study holds significance. Moreover, as a native to the South Asian diaspora community in the UK, the researcher can easily enter into their business environment, which the researchers from the indigenous community do not, and investigate the cultural aspect concerning the social media application into the family business. The gap in the current literature will be more highlighted in the literature chapter.

Today social media and smart technologies have become ubiquitous across the globe. Walking down in local high streets, pubs, supermarkets, we see people constantly on social media for personal and business issues. Social media have become a new modern age or marketing phenomenon to drive businesses into the future. However, this study argues that many small businesses are not capitalising on social media for the benefits of strategic marketing development and future growth and sustainability. Therefore, it would be argued that many small businesses are not using social media as an effective marketing tool to strategically market, develop, grow and ensure their sustainability.

One of the key features of the study is the theoretical lenses that will be applied to understand how the agents in small businesses view social media as a business strategy. Particularly, this research will embrace the influential and ground-breaking work of French sociologist Pierre Bourdieu. Thereupon, Bourdieu's key notions of habitus, capital and field are thoroughly considered an analytical toolkit for this study. The Bourdieusian theories covered a wide range of areas, including Education, Media and journalism, Bureaucracy and Politics, Sociology and others. However, the Bourdieusian framework as a means of understanding the complex relationship

between cultural heritage, social media use and small business is relatively novel in academia. Therefore, Bourdieu's analytical toolkit and especially his oeuvre to the sociology of family, culture, and entrepreneurialism in the diaspora community (Bourdieu, 1990b) will play a significant role in analysing this study's data findings.

Bourdieu's concept of field is suitable for this study that gives an understanding of how he (Bourdieu) perceived family as a distinct field of reproduction where individual's dispositions for specific actions (particularly the implementation of social media in the business) could be developed (Bourdieu, 1985). Moreover, it is also important to understand how an individual acts in the other fields, particularly the retail food industry with the habitus developed in the family field and with the help of different forms of capital gained over some time (Jenkins, 2002).

1.1 RESEARCH CONTEXT

The small food retail businesses in Glasgow are the main focus of the study. The researcher has chosen this context for various reasons. Glasgow is one of the major big cities in the United Kingdom and is a former port city, and it plays a significant role in the country's economy. Contribution in the UK's economy by SMEs is rising day by day. A recent study carried out by the Centre for Economics and Business Research in collaboration with challenger bank Hampshire Trust reveals that by 2025 total contribution is expected to hit £241 billion combined from SMEs across

the ten major cities in the UK. According to the research, the contribution from Glasgow is expected to reach from £5 billion to £6 billion from SMEs (Dorsey, 2017). This ascending trend indicates that contributing to economic success will be continued in upcoming years. Among the different sectors in SMEs, the South-Asian Muslim diaspora community mainly run the small food retail industry. However, very little focus has been given on South-Asian Muslim diaspora community own SMEs. Therefore, the study has chosen this context.

Moreover, the researcher's area of study is in Glasgow, and the researcher has been working in the field of diaspora family-owned retail food industry for over a decade. Therefore, this is another important factor in choosing the Glasgow and diaspora community as a context of the study.

1.2 RESEARCH SIGNIFICANCE

This research study will be significant for Glasgow's economy because it focuses on the cultural features that convince social media acceptance as a new technology in small business premises. The findings will be based on Bourdieu's habitus, field and capital lenses of social theories. Understanding cultural heritage under these social theories will give a new dimension to this study. It might help in encouraging more new entrepreneurial businesses and the rise of start-ups by understanding cultural issues. Furthermore, the study will contribute to the inadequate literature on the cultural aspects of adopting social media strategies in small food retail settings.

Furthermore, the recommendations will provide valuable insights for the existing businesses in Glasgow to improve their projects. In addition, the outcome of the

research study will give the direction of appropriate implementation of recent technologies in business settings. Consequently, this study will give a clear idea about cultural factors behind social media acceptance, which will help recognise the upcoming technologies in small business settings specifically and others in general.

1.3 AIM AND OBJECTIVES

This study aims to explore critically how cultural heritage impacts the utilisation of the power and potential of social media as a business strategy for growth among small food retail businesses.

The south-Asian Muslim family predominantly runs the small food retail businesses across the UK (Rafiq, 1992). Islamic faith and culture create a controlling system because the family brings religious customs and exercise in the business activities (Kavas, Jarzabkowski and Nigam, 2020). . Moreover, this doctrinal value is a motivation for their business strategy. The Islamic culture is important for them because the agents in the family have grown up, embodied and internalised the dispositions from the religious environment, which also provide different forms of capital. The religious faith provides entrepreneurial spirit in the habitus of the agents, and at the same time, the power of Islamic faith retains some views that inhibit the changes in the field of the family business. This is the power and politics of Islamic culture that see the digital platforms in the business as a challenge to their identity and ignore the conversion of capitals. Therefore, the core aim of the study is premised on the centrality of Islam to entrepreneurialism and the appropriation,

application or resistance to new digital marketing media. However, in order to achieve the above aim, a series of objectives are required, which are:

- To provide an exploration of the rise of social media.
- To evaluate the social media adoption in the small food retail businesses.
- To explore the role of ethnic entrepreneurship in the cultural diaspora.
- To examine the impact of cultural heritage on social media as a business strategy.
- To critically analyse the relationship between diaspora culture and social media implementation in the business via Bourdieu's habitus, field and capital theory.

1.4 KEY DEFINITION OF TERMS

Capital: Capital can be described as anything entitled "as being of value" (Beames and Telford, 2013, p.84).within a particular field. More categorically, capital is "the set of actually usable resources and powers" that Bourdieu classified into three core types "economic capital, cultural capital and [..]Social capital" (Bourdieu, 1984, p.114). Capital provides a view on how an individual's resources in a particular area are favoured, degraded, exchanged and captured (Bourdieu, 1985).

Discourse: This is the pattern of language closely related to and articulating or communicating the code and conduct of a specific cultural field (Webb, Schirato, and Danaher, 2002).

Doxa: Doxa refers to the set of values and perceptions formed by the objective or unbiased social conditions; however, those are encountered as innate and obvious, and thus accepted undoubtedly (Harker, Mahar and Wilkies, 2016). Habitus and field both are run by Doxa or rules that set up and provide a sense to the behaviours. Moreover, fields hold the doxa or the standards of operation and that Doxa sets the affinities amidst the actors within a specific field.

Field: Field can be described as an organised space of rankings or positions among the actors where everyone is fighting to get superior status or position in that particular field. Bourdieu's concept of the field only remains when competitions or forced conflicts are present among the actors (Bourdieu, 1990a). Moreover, the field is usually uncertain or volatile, including inconstant dissemination of force at any point in time. In a nutshell, the field can be summarised as the interplay between the actor's habitus and the field development of the field.

Habitus: Habitus is nothing but a concept that lies in the individuals' minds that leads to their actions so that they cannot be thoroughly integrated. Habitus can be described as "the learned set of preferences or dispositions by which a person orients to the social world" (Edgerton and Roberts, 2014, p.195). Therefore, habitus is embedded in a family, nurtured and mastered by an individual's status in society.

Hexis: Bourdieu has acknowledged that the notion of the habitus is evolved from Aristotle's vocabulary 'hexis' "that is usually translated as 'state', 'stable disposition', 'habitus', 'way of being', or even 'possession'" (Rodrigo, 2011)

Illusio: Illusio provides the basis of how agents are captivated or caught up in and off the field. Bourdieu's illusio notion is derived from the game 'Ludus and linked to the 'collusion', which is the foundation of the competition. Every field demands its

actors to possess *illusio* for preparing themselves to spend in the interest of the play and to build "practical mastery of its rules" (Bourdieu & Wacquant, 1992, p. 117). In essence, through *illusio* the actors perform the field, embodying and enacting the field and legitimate the field.

Misrecognition: Misrecognition that Bourdieu refers to as the "form of forgetting" (Webb, Schirato and Danahar, 2002, p.24) of the agents in the given field because they are unable to understand that they create the situation; instead, their circumstances appears to them as "the natural order of things" (Webb, Schirato and Danahar 2002, p.25).

Symbolic violence: Symbolic violence can be described as "the violence which is exercised upon a social agent with his or her complicity" (Bourdieu and Wacquant, 1992, p.167). This type of violence is exerted symbolically rather than physically upon an individual. However, its consequence is remarkable because it allows particular groups holding powerful positions to maintain supremacy over others and thus plays an important "role in the reproduction and naturalising of the social hierarchy" (Webb, Schirato and Danahar 2002, p.118).

1.5 STRUCTURE OF THE RESEARCH STUDY

This study is divided into five chapters:

Chapter one discusses the overall view of the study. First, it gives the research background, followed by research motivation, aims and objective of the study,

research significance, methodological outlines, research contributions and lastly, the structure of the study.

Chapter two is a literature review of the study. It is divided into several subsections. First, this chapter reviews the social media revolution and then understands social media and its application in the organisational context. The literature review also focuses on the benefits and drawbacks of social media in separate subheadings. Next, this chapter discusses cultural diaspora, including capitalism and transnationalism, ethnic entrepreneurship and South Asian diaspora entrepreneurship in the UK. Finally, this chapter concludes with a discussion of the social theory of Bourdieu's habitus, field and capital that have been used as analytical lenses for this study.

Chapter three provides the method and methodology in detail used in this study. The discussion starts with research paradigms, approaches and design, along with the justification. Further, this chapter focuses on the case study research strategy, types of data and its collection procedure, process and rationale of using unstructured interviews and participant observations. It also highlights the population and sampling technique and criteria used in this study. Lastly, this chapter covers the ethical issues and methodological reflection.

Chapter four presents an analysis and interpretation of the data.

Chapter five is the conclusion of the research. It contains the contribution of knowledge in the relevant field. It also includes recommendations for the various stakeholders.

2.0 LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 INTRODUCTION

The preceding chapter gives a comprehensive overview of the background of this study along with the recognised gap that the research intends to address. This section reviews previous relevant studies related to cultural heritage that impact social media adoption in small businesses in their development. The literature review is important in describing the essential outline of present knowledge and academic contributions to specific research work. Therefore, this chapter is organised in different sections and subsections to be aware of the demand for accuracy and reduce ambiguity. So, the literature review chapter begins with how social media evolved, followed by social media and its different perceptions. Then the chapter sheds light on the application of social media in the organisation's context, particularly the small retail industry, its benefits and dark side in separate sections. As the study focuses on the cultural heritage of the diaspora community in terms of adopting social media in the businesses, the literature review also discusses the cultural diaspora: networked communities and businesses in the distinct heading. Under this caption, several subheadings are introduced to give the readers a better understanding of the issue, namely diaspora and transnationalism, capitalism and entrepreneurship, ethnic entrepreneurship, and south Asian diaspora entrepreneurship in the UK. Moreover, the most prominent ethnic entrepreneurial theories, models and approaches of ethnic entrepreneurship are discussed in subsections under the ethnic entrepreneurship heading. Furthermore, the literature review chapter includes a discussion on Pierre Bourdieu's habitus, field and capitals as his theory is used as a lens to analyse the study's data.

2.2 THE SOCIAL MEDIA REVOLUTION

Human behaviours, habitations and communications have been significantly altered due to recent rapid proliferation in the techno-communication realm, particularly online social networking platforms (Tiago and Veríssimo, 2014). Budden et al. (2011) argued, these myriad social networking sites drive the physical form of social relationship to shift into the virtual form, which empowers people to dispense knowledge and entertainment and reduce the cultural gap by promoting dialogues among the different nationalities.

The present matured form of social communication interfaces has evolved over the last two centuries as a part of the daily social rehearsal of the individuals (Dijck, 2013). The technological revolution in communication started in 1792, with the invention of the telegraph that allowed people to send and receive memos from faraway (Edosomwan et al., 2001), followed by radio and telephone in late 1800 for social communication (Rimskii, 2011). Dijck (2013) postulated that those technologies are developed for cultural practices in the form of chatting or messaging. Lisa Gitelman (2008, p.7), in her book, *Always Already New: Media, History and the Data of Culture*, states the difficult prospect of the media as “socially realised structures of communication, where structures include both technological forms and their associated protocols, and where communication is a cultural practice, a ritualised collocation of different people on the same mental map, sharing or engaged with popular ontologies of representation.” Therefore, the communication process is revolutionised technologically and has been shaped by cultural practices over the years.

Computer technology became popular, and the sign of reputation in 1970 for the colossal organisation as a controller of instruments (Jensen, 1993), but society took this as oppression against human empowerment, and as a result, the counterculture

had been established simultaneously in the community for personal freedom of using information technology (Dijck, 2013). Computer giant Apple's favourite campaign in 1984 was the extraordinary example of this counterculture where they portrayed Macintosh users as the dweller of unconventional culture (Dormehl, 2012). From this action, it can be said that tech giants recognised the importance of the culture and used it as a campaign tool.

Email is another significant landmark in the communication revolution invented in 1960, but society had to wait for the internet to become public till 1991 for its wide use (Perez, 2003). As a consequence, networked communication has come to an evident with the invention of WWW (World Wide Web), where hypertext technology has been connected to the internet, and subsequently, this World Wide Web established a connection between culture and counterculture (Dijck, 2013). Despite not having a collaborative nature like social networking sites, it cannot be denied that the foundation of Email is considered the starting of a two-way nature of social media (Sajithra and Patil, 2013). Lee and Finger (2010) exemplified that the development of computer technologies has also played a vital role in the evolution of technocommunication. Multi-users Domain (MUD), Bulletin Board System (BBS), USENET, LISTSERV and IRC were some of the major software and applications used for communicating fiction, online chat (Bartle, 2009); reading newspapers, transfer software, interchange messages (Edosomwan et al., 2001); group emailing (Sajithra and Patil, 2013) group communication, private chat (Jones, 2003).

Moreover, Dijck (2013) added that the technological advancement of computer-oriented technologies is to create communities online and support them when they are offline. In the 1990s, based on those software and applications, different social networking sites began to emerge like Six Degrees, Lunar Storm, Classmates.com

etc. but major shifting happened from networked or systematic communication to both ways and even multiway, interactive networked channels when Web 2.0 came to action at the very beginning of this new millennium (Castells, 2007). As a result, commercial giants like Google, Amazon etc., converted to commercialism from communism overnight, primarily Web 1.0 (Dijck, 2013). Therefore, the revolution in communication technology got the influencing power to change the internal and external environment of the organisations.

Musser and O'Reily (2007, p.10) describe the Web 2.0 as a “set of economic, social and technology trends that collectively form the basis for the next generation of the Internet, a more mature, distinctive medium characterised by users’ participation, openness, and network effects.” Some scholars argued that involute coevolution exists in the step by step rise of the communication media, from technologies to the end-users and institutions to the infrastructures (Winston, 1998; Marvin, 1990). From the year 2000 to till date, people have witnessed numerous popular social networking sites like Wikipedia in 2001, LinkedIn in 2002, Myspace in 2003, Facebook and Flickr in 2004, YouTube in 2005, Twitter in 2006, Spotify in 2008, Instagram and Pinterest in 2010, Snapchat in 2011 (Junco, Heiberger and Loken, 2010; Edosomwan et al., 2001). Social network sites are network-based facilities that let people build a public profile inside a confined structure, make a user’s list of connections, and scan and navigate their own connections list as well as others (Boyd and Ellison, 2007). These social platforms usually work on their dynamic objectives, which are altered in the needs of the users and the demand of the competitors and change of financial and technological environment (Feenberg, 2009).

2.3 SOCIAL MEDIA CONCEPT AND DEFINITIONS

The phenomenon 'Social media' emerged as an 'applied paradigm' with the main target of building a communicating network among the people of the same belief but indubitably with some vague theorisation behind it (Ngai, Tao and Moon, 2015). Furthermore, a large part of the recent understanding of social media is grounded on the untested premise, unremarkable literature or unscientific evidence (Ghezzi et al., 2016). Moreover, current academic work is more focused on exploring explicit types of social media instead of developing innovative interpretative spectacles and setting up unequivocal guidelines for the small businesses on their collective usage (Aral, Dellarocas and Godes, 2013). It is due to the rapidly changing nature of social media that drives the scholars to focus on the different types rather than focus on its' regulations.

It is believed that AOL executive Ted Lenosis, in 1997, first used the term 'Social media' in print while commenting on organisations who should deliver their consumer a "social media, places where they can be entertained, communicate, and participate in a social environment" (Treem and Leonardi, 2013, p.143). Treem and Leonardi (2013) also remarked that the debut of many widely accepted SNS (Social Networking Sites) drive social media terminology to change swiftly into the mainstream from digital-savvy. Though all people now use social media, it is truly a difficult task to describe what it really means. Some scholars like Aral, Dellarocas and Godes (2013); Hogan and Quan-Haase (2010) referred to social media as an ongoing target, and it is hard to define because of its constantly changing nature and brisk development (Kane et al., 2014).

The terminology, 'Social media, which is the affordances of high technology, has more impact on its social setting rather than its technical landscape and emerged from the term 'Web 2.0' that can assist the people of all lifestyles in rethinking the character of technology, can play in data circulation, civic improvement, and communication (Boyd, 2015). However, the rise of social media platforms is still repeatedly merged with Web 2.0, and the 'participatory' character of social media is badly credited to the technological layout of the web (Dijck, 2013). Logically to this transformation, social media can be described as a social communication among the persons by creating, sharing and exchanging knowledge and information in the virtual networks (Ghezzi et al., 2016). Users generating content and sharing content (Web 2.0) are the two main concepts on which the Social media phenomenon has primarily been built (Nicholls, 2011). Interaction, a wide range of sources and the controlling power of end-users are the basic characteristics of Web 2.0 that enhances participants' understanding, experiences and teamwork in the professional and communal processes (Constantinides, 2014). Besides, Web 2.0 provides the opportunity to share and modify the contents jointly in a constant way (Kaplan and Haenlein, 2010).

The definition of social media has evolved because the number of research gradually focused on theoretical and pragmatic application in the institutions has increased over time (Treem and Leonardi, 2013).

Boyd and Ellison (2007, p. 211) defined social network sites as,

"Web-based services that allow individuals to (1) construct a public or semi-public profile within a bounded system, (2) articulate a list of other users with whom they

share a connection, and (3) view and traverse their list of connections and those made by others within the system".

Definition of social media, according to Kaplan and Haenlein (2010, p. 61), is,

"a group of internet-based applications that build on the ideological and technological foundations of Web 2.0 and that allow the creation and exchange of user-generated content".

Majchrzak et al. (2013, p. 38) referred social media to,

"A group of Internet-based technologies that allows users to easily create, edit, evaluate, and/or link to content or to other creators of content".

Kane et al. (2014, p. 279) criticised the work of Boyd and Ellison (2007) and updated the social media meaning as

"social media networks possess four essential features, such that users (1) have a unique user profile that is constructed by the user, by members of their network, and by the platform; (2) access digital content through, and protect it from, various search mechanisms provided by the platform; (3) can articulate a list of other users with whom they share a relational connection; and (4) view and traverse their connections and those made by others on the platform".

Balan and Rege (2017, p. 43) describe social media as

"Computer-fabricated tools that enable the faster exchange of information in virtual networks."

The definitions mentioned above exhibit some common characteristics like networking ability, UGC (Users Generated Content) and internet role (Kaplan and Haenlein, 2010; Boyd & Ellison, 2007; Kane et al., 2014). Furthermore, Kietzmann et

al. (2011) pointed out share, co-creation, discussion and modification of the user-generated content are the main characteristics of vastly interactive platforms created by cellular phones and Internet-related technologies under the influence of Social media. However, Dijck (2013) undoubtedly stated that the two most important characteristics of social media, interactivity and participatory, make the virtual media democratic more than the traditional unidirectional media.

Boyd and Ellison (2007) provided a ground-breaking definition of Social media though their work is in the field of SNSs (Social Networking Site), where they are concerned about the interaction among the users influenced by social media usage. Later Kiron et al. (2012) endorsed that social networking sites cause boosting awareness in society, particularly via Facebook. Many scholars working in the same field primarily accepted the Boyd and Ellison (2007) definition of social networking sites (DiMicco et al., 2008; Beer, 2008; Lewis et al., 2008). However, Kaplan and Haenlein (2010) defended that the heterogeneity character of any sites does not mean that they are entitled to use social media terms. As a result, scholars of early studies in this field skipped to provide a clear definition and used some popular social media platforms for the readers to recognise. For example, Culnan, McHugh and Zubillaga (2010), Marwick and Boyd (2010) and Lerman and Gosh (2010) used Twitter as a reference of social media in their work. Treem and Leonardi (2013) pointed out that scholars were unsuccessful to provide noteworthy theoretical understanding because of this practice. Subsequently, new forms of the platform have emerged that led novice users to utilise the social media diversely, e.g. organisational level, resulting in the ground-breaking definition of Boyd and Ellison (2007), and referential tactic used in the studies became obsolete quickly (Treem and Leonardi, 2013; Kane et al., 2014).

After Boyd and Ellison (2007), the most widely accepted alternative definition of social media emerged from Kaplan and Haenlein (2010, p. 60-61) study where they stressed the internet for the usage of social media and specifically Web 2.0, "a term that was first used in 2004 to describe a new way in which software developers and end-users started to utilise the World Wide Web; that is, as a platform whereby content and applications are no longer created and published by individuals, but instead are continuously modified by all users in a participatory and collaborative fashion."

Kaplan and Haenlein (2010) mentioned that Web 2.0 gives the conceptual and high-tech foundation and Users generating content is the entire means of using social media by the people. They also added that the term 'User-generated content' relates freely available numerous types of media content that produced the end-users (Kaplan and Haenlein, 2010). Most of the definitions (Kim, Jeong and Lee, 2010; Vodanovich, Sundaram and Myers, 2010; Martini, Massa and Testa, 2013; Majchrzak et al. 2013) is based on those two characteristics or merely used Kaplan & Haenlein (2010) definition (Yuan et al., 2013)

Social media ranges from Facebook, MySpace, Bebo (social networking site), YouTube (audio-video sharing), Flickr (picture sharing), LinkedIn (Business networking), Twitter (micro-blog), and various others (Whiting and Williams, 2013; Valos et al. 2016).

2.4 USE OF SOCIAL MEDIA IN THE CONTEXTS OF ORGANISATION

Empirical studies are behind the race due to the rapidly changing nature of social media at every societal level (Treem and Leonardi, 2013). Aral, Dellarocas and Godes (2013) asserted that overarching consequences of social media had inspired the interdisciplinary scholars, but some other scholars argued that 'communication studies' (Treem & Leonardi, 2013) and 'information system' (Aral, Dellarocas and Godes, 2013), are the two most suitable arena that suits most for the social media study. However, social media studies concerning organisations are done so far in almost every discipline.

In the marketing field, social media has predominantly been accepted as a tool of marketing, and therefore, most of the research questions in the literature are about consumers (Kiron et al., 2011; Kane et al., 2014). The researchers in this realm have investigated how social media influences consumer behaviour (Campbell, Ferraro and Sands, 2014; Goel and Goldstein, 2014), consumers' ability on product rating (Kumar et al., 2013), consumers' comments in the social media on their favourite brand (Colliander and Hauge Wien, 2013; Toubia and Stephen, 2013) and last but not the least, how consumer influences other with the help of social media (Kumar et al., 2013; Kerr et al., 2012; Ahrens, Coyle and Strahilevitz, 2013).

Likewise, social media has also affected the HR (Human Resource) industry. Research on Human resources has now focused on the transformation of traditional procedures, particularly employee selection by using social media (Roth et al., 2013; Van Iddekinge et al., 2016) and change in job searching behaviour (Feuls, Fieseler and Suphan, 2014; Janta and Ladkin, 2013; Thomson, 2013). Social media also give rise to ethical issues while communicating among the co-workers internally (Mainiero and Jones, 2012; Mainiero and Jones, 2013; Van Laer, 2013) and externally about organisation's corporate social responsibility strategies (Castelló, Morsing and

Schultz, 2013; Lyon and Montgomery, 2013; Clark and Roberts, 2010; Lee, Oh and Kim, 2013; Whelan, Moon and Grant, 2013; Fieseler and Fleck, 2013). Though the influences and applications in different fields of the organisations are evident in the scholarly articles, the role of social media in the small businesses owned by South Asian diaspora families has been ignored.

Social media is the interactive tool that emerged due to advancement and the low cost of internet technologies (Kim, Lee and Lee, 2013; Maguire, Koh and Magrys, 2007) and offered numerous opportunities for empowerment not only to the individual level but also at organisational levels (Peris et al., 2013). Primarily it was devised for personal use by connecting people at an individual level (Schlagwein and Prasarnphanich, 2014), but now social media have become inseparable from the people due to its rapid assimilation into daily life (Boyd and Ellison, 2007). These interactive tools let people go beyond the geographical border for connectedness across the globe (Jagongo and Kinyua, 2013). Before moving into the discussion regarding the growth of social media and its adoption in organisations, it is necessary to discuss the recent trends related to the leading platforms concisely. This is vital because the growing number of user base platforms provide a strategic motivation for businesses to accept these interactive communication technologies.

Billions of people are connected now by social media, and its comprehensive effects have reached a new height than expected (Samuel and Joe, 2016). Facebook is the most popular platform of having more than 2.2 billion monthly active users all over the world till the last quarter of 2017 (Statista, 2018), and popular microblogging platform Twitter (Jansen et al., 2009) has over 330 million active users per month by the end of the year 2017 (Statista, 2018). This growing number of monthly users

attracts all business forms to link up more with the potential customers and build up the business profile in the respective field (Jones, Borgman and Ulusoy, 2015).

Regardless of this, social media is comparatively a new tool for businesses (Wamba and Carter, 2014; Kane et al., 2014), though organisations have already started shifting globally towards embracing and implementing it in their operational activities. It is now recognised that businesses have become successful nowadays because of social media, which creates an online space where they meet stakeholders and customers (Culnan, McHugh and Zubillaga, 2010; Jagongo and Kinyua, 2013). This is not surprising that the literature shows growing attention among the organisations, regardless of their size, in using the enormous opportunities offered by social media for carrying out several functions globally with the different types of industries. However, this shifting trend is not evident in every small business. For example, the diaspora family owns many shops in the UK, and their acceptance of social media into the business is very insignificant. Though the literature showed attention to the organisations regardless of their size, there was very little attention on how diaspora family businesses view social media as an opportunity for the business.

Several scholars have noticed the different parts of the business like CRM (Customer Relationship Management), marketing, research and development where social media is widely used (Nakara, Benmoussa and Jaouen, 2012; Soto-Acosta, Perez-Gonzalez and Popa, 2014). Furthermore, Xiang and Gretzel (2010) and Dyerson, Harindranath and Barnes, (2009) added that not only the different parts of the organisation is using social media but also a significant number of industries like retail, manufacturing, health and service, travel and tourism industries have started getting the benefits after using it.

As the study previously mentioned, all businesses have embraced social media somewhat to explain the cost of using it. The cost associated with using social media does not necessarily need huge investment is proved by the various empirical studies (Cesaroni and Consoli, 2015; Kaplan and Haenlein, 2010; Michaelidou, Siamagka and Christodoulides, 2011), indicating that the size of the organisations does not seem an issue of using these tools. However, existing literature suggests that those virtual platforms are predominantly relevant and beneficial for the small enterprises (Dirgiatmo, 2015; Kahar et al., 2012; Broekemier, Chau and Seshadri, 2015), particularly to supersede boundaries related to the size of the small business (Cesaroni and Consoli, 2015). Social media has the power to break the boundaries of small and medium enterprises; mostly, the literature highlights the indigenous enterprises. Therefore, there is a scope for the researchers to focus on why social media cannot enter into their diaspora enterprises.

From the small and medium enterprise perspective, studies show the positive views towards adopting social media. Cesaroni and Consoli (2015) and He, Zha and Li (2013) mentioned that small and medium firms can now identify the significance of utilising the power of these platforms. For instance, a survey revealed that nearly half of the participating small and medium enterprises are on the four popular interactive platforms like Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn and YouTube (Vlachvei and Notta, 2018). Another survey carried out by Broekemier, Chau and Seshadri (2015) showed 54% of the SMEs who took part in the study were operating social media for multiple reasons. However, the survey did not give any importance to those SMEs which were run by ethnic communities. Some scholars did mention why ethnic entrepreneurship should consider social media, but the understanding of the reasons for their negligence remains superficial.

Surprisingly, the growing number of organisations using social media are considering more investment in it. According to the Forrester report, only in the United States spending on social media will be expected to increase up to \$18.7 billion from \$8.2 billion in 2019 (Miglani, 2014). Moreover, Bughin (2008) and Lacho and Marinello (2010) argued that the estimated increase in social media expenditure indicates that the businesses are moving towards adopting social media because businesses think these communication technologies are better than other information technologies.

To put it briefly, it is evident that all forms of enterprises are getting advantages of adopting social media to carry out numerous actions. Current studies provide factual evidence of positive and inclusive impacts on small and medium enterprises due to embracing social media in their organisational settings (He et al., 2015; Jones, Borgman and Ulusoy, 2015). The evidence of the benefits of creating social media presence by the small and medium-size businesses is increasing, and now big organisations are not the beneficiary of those benefits (Verheyden and Goeman, 2013). Yet, there is a gap in the academia to study in-depth to get a deeper understanding of the digital discourse in the diaspora enterprises. The next section will give a further understanding of the advantages of social media, including small businesses.

2.5 BENEFITS OF SOCIAL MEDIA USE

The number of social media is increasing day by day, and it escalates various issues regarding how those virtual platforms bring benefits to the organisations, particularly in the perspective of this study. Various academic works have discoursed numerous benefits, giving some practical evidence related to the social media adoption by small businesses. Those studies identified that the acceptance of social media in small businesses delivers a significant number of benefits like electronic word of mouth branding (Michaelidou, Siamagka and Christodoulides, 2011; Jansen et al., 2009), development of brand relationships (Hudson et al., 2015; Dahnil et al., 2014), product and service information (Vlachvei and Notta, 2014), improve customer relationship (Broekemier, Chau and Seshadri, 2015; Persaud, Spence and Rahman, 2012), network building and collaboration with the stakeholders (Meske and Stieglitz, 2013), awareness expansion (Jones, Borgman and Ulusoy, 2015), and marketing and promotion (He et al., 2015).

In addition, some researchers have also worked on how social media plays a potential role in managing consumer information. In particular, Chua and Banerjee (2013) recommended that organisations deploy social media to acquire information about the customers and involve them in the sharing process. Furthermore, Lacho and Marinello (2010) and Vlachvei and Notta (2014) demonstrated that social media enables organisations to create online brand communities and help to engage the customers in rich discussions. Sigala (2012) affirmed that customer engagements endorse sharing and swapping ideas, and it helps the businesses develop the product by enhancing the customers' creativity. Moreover, Michaelidou, Siamagka and Christodoulides (2011) remarked, knowledge sharing assists in constructing an exclusive brand identity. Therefore, social media reinforces all forms of businesses to utilise feedback generated by the customers, influencing the overall performance.

Therefore, Vlachvei and Notta (2014) truly posited social media as a dynamic tool for enterprises to expand their network worldwide and obtain invaluable feedback.

Barnes et al. (2012) pointed out that collaborative nature is another significant advantage of social media which attracts small businesses, and therefore Mannonen and Runonen (2008) argued that sharing nature sometimes gives sole power to the small businesses to face competition with the giants in the market. Therefore, these dynamic characteristics of social media drive small businesses to implement the different forms of the platform into their business and get the benefits that are very hard to achieve through traditional media.

Apart from those benefits, several scholars have tried to delineate the financial ROI (Return on Investment) of using social media, but this debatable matter still needs clear outcomes. Meske and Stieglitz (2013) and Michaelidou, Siamagka and Christodoulides (2011) mentioned that it is seemingly challenging for social media adopters to measure ROI. Consequently, Cesaroni and Consoli (2015) and Broekemier, Chau and Seshadri (2015) stated that many business owners are still doubtful about the use of social media in the business setting that causes the revenue growth. For example, a survey carried out by Bell (2011) on 130 business settings revealed, around 70% of the business owners claimed that only 10% of the total sales has increased due to social media adoption. On the other hand, another study showed that Facebook usage on small and medium businesses has a solid positive correlation on the business performance, and as a result, it increases customer number, transactions and sales volume (Ainin et al., 2015). The empirical evidence is also evident in another study where sales were increased in the small and medium enterprises in the rural area of the United States due to social media implementation in the businesses (Jones, Borgman and Ulusoy, 2015).

Although social media offers numerous benefits to all forms of businesses, including small and medium-sized enterprises, their social media acceptances are still considered to be the early stage (Persaud, Spence, and Rahman, 2012; Treem and Leonardi, 2013). Furthermore, researchers have also noticed hesitancy among the small firms to embrace social media because they are still in doubt either these platforms would effectively support their brands or not (Michaelidou, Siamagka and Christodoulides, 2011; Nakara, Benmoussa and Jaouen, 2012). From this scholarly point of view, it is prominent that lack of knowledge about social media outcomes prevents them from embracing social media.

Some studies also figured out that some serious issues exist in the small and medium businesses, like reluctance and late adoption of social media, especially in the emerging countries (Hashim and Noor, 2014; Yeboah-Boateng and Essandoh, 2014). Therefore, it is very significant for small businesses to recognise the influential factors of embracing social media to benefit from using it (Omosigho and Abeysinghe, 2012). The reluctance is present in the emerging countries and the businesses owned by the diaspora communities in the developed countries.

2.6 DARK SIDE OF SOCIAL MEDIA

Often research and social media applications are presented as a "bright side" of this techno-cultural revolution (Djik, 2013). However, while there are many opportunities and positive gains to be gleaned from social media, social media undoubtedly has a "dark side". Interestingly, as will be evidenced in the findings of this study, this dark side or negative view of social media is referenced to negate its adoption for growth.

Today the revolution of social media is now seen as posing a threat, not on a personal level, but for communities, businesses, various aspects of the societal level, even to the global arena due to its supersonic reach power (Baccarella et al., 2018). Recently this has been exemplified in the scandals of Cambridge Analytica and the USA Trump election and Brexit (Allcott and Gentzkow, 2017). Now scholars are paying more attention to fixing the negative side of social media to maximise its bright, positive nature. This subsection of the literature review seeks to unmask the dark side of social media in the context of business and enterprise. Moreover, it is important to focus on this area to consider the counter critique of social media and its accelerating techno culture.

The most common examples of the darkness of social media include cyber harassment (O'Keeffe and Clarke-Pearson, 2011), fishing (Buckels, Trapnell and Paulhus, 2014), privacy infringement (Pai and Arnott, 2013), fraudulent news (Allcott and Gentzkow, 2017), online outbursts (Pfeffer, Zorbach and Carley, 2014) and social media addiction (Blackwell et al., 2017). In addition, a recent survey carried out on Britons (aged between 14-24) revealed an exacerbation of the tension, sleep deprivation and desolation in individual health occur in social media use (Levenson et al., 2016). Other studies showed that in the organisation, negative consequences result from the advantages of social media through conflict and interruptions in the work-life (Van Zoonen, Verhoeven and Vliegenthart, 2017). Despite the above-

identified negative phenomena of social media, the degree of despair is usually an idiosyncratic matter. For instance, a career in the UK who uploaded a picture of a group of residents in a singalong task on Facebook has been fired due to sharing a faux-pas (Karl, Peluchette and Schlaegel, 2010; Schmidt and O'Connor, 2015). For this act, most of the public in the UK thought the Facebook post was harmless and naive, but this could not save her 21 years of work. From the employer's point of view, this was considered a breach of law (privacy invasion). So, the business needs to pay attention to the multi-faceted nature of social media, if not its positive and negative impacts, to become more aware of their possible risk and take well-informed decisions.

To better understand social media's functionalities at a personal and organisational level, Kietzmann et al. (2011) developed a honeycomb framework that unpacks social media functionalities into several building blocks. Therefore, those blocks can also be applied to aid to explain and investigate the various aspects of the negative side of social media. The researcher of this study has used each functional block to describe the negative outcomes that a business and its consumer encounter from social media. The explanations used are not comprehensive but are established on the typical behaviours and cases.

Fig.2.1: The dark side of social media functionality (Baccarella et al., 2018).

Businesses should be aware of how positive aspects of the conversation functionality of social media turn into unrestricted, hostile and flawed engagement with the customers. The bulletin board, Reddit, illustrates this point as it faced several incidents where a good conversation on a given topic spun into private harassment. Particularly in 2013, 'online witch hunts' on Reddit wrongly came out with several names as suspects from its users concerning the Boston bombing incident (BBC News, 2013; Suran and Kilgo, 2015). Moreover, artificial chatbots or social bots used covertly by the online platforms can contaminate the conversation on social media with cold calls and deceptive advertisements because of their mimicry of human nature (Ferrara et al., 2016). From those scenarios, it can be said that organisations should be aware of their conversation with consumers to protect everyone's privacy.

The sharing criterion of social media can be fast and furious if it is used incorrectly. Therefore, Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) are at risk because social media enable users to share other user-generated content (sometimes that might be inappropriate or inadmissible) without prior consent from the original holder of the content (van Dijck, 2009; Berthon et al., 2015). Various cases of copyright infringement happened over the period, but of them, the case of Stephanie Lenz is worth considering. She posted a video on YouTube in 2007 of her baby dancing to the song of Prince, which belongs to the copyright of Universal Music Group. Despite raising a dispute by Lenz to the YouTube and Universal group, finally, YouTube had to take down the video because of a US \$150,000 fine notice (Lessig, 2008). In addition, social media had a tremendous impact on the US presidential election 2016, where hundreds of websites were charged for sharing bogus news about the election result (Allcott and Gentzkow, 2017).

Businesses who are using social media platforms can be tracked down without letting them know. Facebook's messenger application was the best example where the application's default settings had collected geolocation of the users from 2011 to 2015 while they were in conversation. Several organisations raised issues against Facebook about the stalking of the users but in vain (Cipriani, 2012). Furthermore, 'Marauder Map', an extension of Google chrome, is the modified and upgraded version of the messenger application, used for stalking the users in a more precise and scientific way (Nosouhi et al., 2017). So, in the context of negative aspects of social media, the 'presence' functionality block is closely related to the issues involving the safeguarding or capturing of private information and perhaps the well-being of the participants who use social media.

People use different social media according to the nature of the relationship they offer. Therefore, LinkedIn is mainly for professionals, and Facebook is structured for all kinds of friendships. However, organisations should keep in mind that the relationship-building power of social media also gives rise to detrimental consequences, depending on the nature of the engagement established with the customers. Of them, cyberbullying, hunting, and online annoyance are increasing at an alarming rate (Kwan and Skoric, 2013). Statistics show 10%-40% of youth in the United States (Kowalski et al., 2014) are being victimised of bullying online and surprisingly, 40% of social media users have been doing it as fun, perhaps from jealousy (Horner, Asher and Fireman, 2015). From the organisational point of view, bullying can happen between the business and the customers or among the customers. In both ways, the consequences will be deleterious for the business.

The next functionality block is the reputation which can be built or humiliated through social media in a matter of time. Whatever the reputation (functional, social or expressive) gained overtime is at risk based on the appropriateness of the content shared on social media platforms (Eisenegger, 2009). Each year, many businesses, political and public figures, are compelled to resign or apologise for their offensive, deceitful or absurd posting on social media. In fact, nowadays, employers' are also screening applicants' social media pages to see the quality and suitability of the content to protect their reputation during the hiring process (Roulin, 2014). Apart from professional life, numerous incidents also warn all walks of people on social media to pay attention regarding reputation. For example, blogs named 'Gawker' and 'Wonkette' come first to destroy the prestige of public figures, and several sites like 'Revenge porn', 'Don't Date Him Girl' and 'Hollaback' support disgrace, humiliation or scolding of others (Woodruff, 2014).

The downside of the next functionality block, 'Groups', starts with 'in group-outgroup bias' (Tajfel and Turner, 2004). The human nature of the people tend to join a group in social media where they think their voice will be amplified with the people of the same ideology, and from there, a conflict like 'in group love and outgroup hate' evolves (Brewer, 1999). As a result, people of different thoughts become isolated and restricted to the polarised discourse (Hogg and Reid, 2006). Unfortunately, most of the businesses slip to recognise that negativity lies underneath this social media functionality block.

The final and central functionality block of the honeycomb is the identity where the individuals are in control of providing subjective information to shape the personal profile into the virtual world. Social media's visibility, clarity, continuity, and granularity nature takes away the control of users' identity and places it at the edge of threat. However, now it is acceptable or harmless to stalk people's personal information before approaching them or board them into the organisation or see their spouse's recent update (Lyndon, Bonds-Raacke and Cratty, 2011). In spite of possible privacy matters, such prying behaviour is firmly favoured by numerous online platforms. For example, a report carried out by the Belgian Privacy Commission blamed Facebook, the largest platform by the number of users, for its poor controlling mechanism on users' private information. The report also points out that it is very challenging for the users to find out the default settings, which leads Facebook to generate behavioural patterns without their (the users) concern (Van Alsenoy et al., 2015).

The example used above concerning the function block of social media can assist the businesses (who are already on social media platforms or who are willing to adopt) to understand the multidimensional nature of the darkness of social media

well. At the same time, the negative incidents are changing and evolving as technology develops over the period. So businesses and enterprises should always seek appropriate solutions to encounter additional unfavourable progress caused by the inherent ramifications of social media.

For businesses, it is hard to quantify the price they pay for the wrong steps on social media, but the results can still be drastic. For example, United Airlines faced several incidents in the last decade that led to a troublesome impact on their business. Millions viewed the video on YouTube when in 2009, a musician composed a song about United Airlines regarding an unsuccessful attempt to reclaim the cost of his Taylor guitar wrecked by the airlines' handler (Tran, 2009). As a result, the stock value went down, and the business that holds high standards got punished due to the unforgiveness nature of social media. Despite this, United Airlines failed to learn the lesson from the failures. In 2017, another video footage of a passenger being dragged from the flight (United Express Flight 3411) went viral after the guitar handling catastrophe and caused another online outrage (Goldstein, 2017).

Apart from those public affairs social media fiascos, there are many examples of darkness within the horizon of the organisations. Such as monitoring the employees' activities, damage of the employers' reputation by the dissatisfied employees, workplace bullying among the colleagues and so on. Some other major social media disasters occurred recently that are also needed to consider.

#McDStories, in 2012, was the best example of how an intended positive promotion on Twitter turns into a massive negative online firestorm (Pfeffer, Zorbach and Carley, 2014). Similarly, #QantasLuxury on Twitter in 2011 (Samuel, 2011) and ING-DiBa (German bank) vegetarian rant on Facebook in 2012 were some highlighted

incidents of negative word of mouth in social media history (Brinkmann, 2012). Most recently, the Facebook-Cambridge Analytica incident in 2018 shook the world heartily because Facebook unethically passed its 50 million users' personal information to the third party, Cambridge Analytica, who particularly helps the political parties all over the world with targeted voters' personal information (Cadwalladr, 2018). This incident shows the power and irresponsibility of one of the top social media platforms that played with the trust of its users and needs to be scrutinised. The aftermath of the unaccountability caused a \$134 billion drop in market value. However, while this appears as an enormous sum, Facebook absorbed this with little impact, demonstrates the size, wealth and power of this global platform. Even after these revelations, Facebook has retained and built on its 2.2 billion users and remains the 3rd largest company globally (Mirhaydari, 2018).

Given the darkness of social media outlined in this section of the literature review, the reader will explicitly understand how the social media revolution continues with the unpredictable nature of negative traits. Indeed, different unfavourable social media events point out human social behaviour is stagnating online while the social media platforms keep advancing. Notwithstanding such pitfalls, its demand and attraction for business prevail. Today, and regardless of the negative connotations of social media, businesses of all sizes and types continue to invest in social media as a means to engage and grow their business. Notwithstanding, it is necessary to focus on the drawbacks of social media and businesses while mining its positive aspects and need to countenance its risks and detrimental consequences. Having considered hazardous issues of social media, the next section will focus on cultural diaspora and the networking of cultural communities with business, as this is central to this study.

2.7 CULTURAL DIASPORA: NETWORKED COMMUNITIES AND BUSINESSES

The cultural diaspora is considered the focal point of this study because of its remarkable importance. Diasporas have a crucial role in escalating the international competitive ability of a country in many ways like by enriching human resource development in the country from where they come, using the cosmopolitan network in both countries as a channel for businesses, presenting their own culture to the country of residence and so on (Chand, 2012). However, the word diaspora is exploited in various ways over and above its historical meaning; in addition, its interpretation has been changing continuously over the years (Vertovec, 1997).

The notion of diaspora was restricted to racial, indigenous or spiritual groups confined by the common cultural customs and conducts, which has started to widen from its conventional sense to deal with multicultural and international networks (Dutia, 2012). Therefore, the biggest power of exile entrepreneurs is the capability to construct social acquaintances through aesthetic and linguistic harmonies. The term 'diaspora' has managed to escape its theoretical enclosure and is applied now to describe a group of people like scientists, scholars, architects, sports players, among various instances (Cohen, 2010). Understanding cultural diaspora is important because people in the diaspora community were raised in an environment where every day's actions are influenced and determined by the culture. The following subsection will discuss the diaspora and culture.

2.7.1 DIASPORA AND TRANSNATIONALISM

Homogenous to the diaspora, transnationalism is based on the dissemination and expansion of the civic, bureaucratic and financial processes across the geographical borders. Transnationalism can be defined “as the process by which immigrants build social fields that link together their country of origin and their country of settlement. Immigrants who build such social fields are designated ‘transmigrants’. Transmigrants develop and maintain multiple relations- familial, economic, social, organisational, religious and political that span borders. Transmigrants take actions, make decisions, and feel concerns, and develop identities within social networks that connect them to two or more societies simultaneously” (Schiller, Basch and Szanton Blanc, 1992. p. 1-2). Therefore, immigrants can satisfy their financial goals without experiencing a long way of socialisation, as it took more time before (Jasso and Rosenzweig, 1990).

The notions of diaspora and transnationalism are significantly overlapped, which causes a hard task to differentiate between them (Bauböck & Faist, 2010), which is a central issue of the study. Diaspora community formed in the United Kingdom by establishing themselves via work ethic and business development network. Windrush generation from Jamaica is the first diaspora community formed in the United Kingdom in 1948, and according to the BBC (2020), “many of the arrivals became manual workers, cleaners, drivers and nurses- and some broke new ground in representing black Britons in society.”

Like the Windrush generation, people also migrated from the Indian sub-continent to the UK and formed the South Asian diaspora. The British Empire was the most powerful in the world by 1900 BC and became the first industrial nation and drove

the industrial revolution and territorialism and brutalised Indian sub-continent nations. Interestingly, the South Asian diaspora in the UK is more organised and building a reverse empire by their entrepreneurial spirit and hard-working culture. To understand the nature of the South Asian diaspora community, it is important to know about their culture and traditions. The following paragraph will focus on the general discussion about the culture and later will discuss the family culture of the South Asian diaspora community.

Engel, Blackwell and Miniard (1993, p.63) defined culture as “a set of values, ideas, artefacts, and other meaningful symbols that help individuals communicate, interpret, and evaluate as members of society”. McCracken (1986) indicted that individual belief shapes and constitutes the world we experience every day. Researchers of sociology and anthropology introduced that human interpretations are affected by socially shared meanings and beliefs. Boyacigiller et al. (2003) identified the two opposing assumptions relating to the culture: the first one is “culture is a coherent and enduring set of values that members of the nation-state carry and invariably act upon” (p. 140). Another assumption on culture suggests “is learned and passed on to new group members through social interaction; culture is dynamic—it changes over time” (pp. 100–101). The first assumption is supported by the work of Hofstede’s national culture (1987, 2001), House et al. (2004) study of GLOBE (Global Leadership and Organizational Behaviour Effectiveness) and the second assumption is consistent with the framework of Fang (2006) and the work of McSweeney (2002, 2009) (Waters and Lo, 2012).

Well-known cultural studies show the ethnographic images constructed from the rough conception of culture (Geertz, 1973; Sahlins, 1987). Organisational scholars followed those traditions and gave the concept of culture to the organisations

(Hofstede, 1980; Quchi, 1981). Cultural materials could be subjective or objective in organisations. Subjectively labelled materials are popular stories (Brown, Gabriel and Gherardi, 2009), customs and rituals (Rippin, 2011), traditional ceremonies (Dacin, Munir and Tracey, 2010), and humour (Robert and Wilbanks, 2012). Objectively defined materials are architectural design, sign and symbol, uniforms, sculpture etc. (Schein, 1991). Therefore, Swidler (1986) argued that culture could be seen as a sprinkled bit all over the organisation. However, Kitayama (2002) observed that researchers in cultural study are not working only with the external cultural features but also the emotional understandings associated with it. Though some scholars have worked on how cultural contexts drive to embrace social media in organisations, they have not considered how social media interpretations are shaped (Koch, Leidner and Gonzalez, 2013; Koch, Gonzalez and Leidner, 2012). Swidlers (1986) suggested that major social changes are responsible for forming new ways of describing and performing the phenomena. Treem and Leonardi (2013) denoted that social media can make radical changes in the communication process used by organisations.

2.7.2 ETHNIC ENTREPRENEURSHIP

Historically, the financial growth of previous immigrant societies in western countries had been reinforced by the engagement in small-sized businesses (Waldinger and Aldrich, 1990). The substantial flow of immigrants from the underprivileged countries of the world to advanced western countries has played a crucial role in forming

multicultural mix in their cities' society (Jensen and Arnett, 2012). Therefore, due to the evolution of global society spotted in the world's most advanced cities, more entrepreneurial movements are seen within the particular ethnic group in those places. So, those entrepreneurial activities are mainly based on the interactions with others in the society (Sarason, Dean and Dillard, 2006), and financial decisions are usually determined by the supremacy and concerns from the society (Fershtman, Murphy and Weiss, 1996). Inevitably, it is always said that entrepreneurial etiquette is firmly rooted in a particular socio-economic context where some people confront or uncover scopes through discourse with others (Kirzner, 1997).

In numerous industrialised countries, the inhabitants of ethnic society have reached a remarkable mass to encourage ethnic entrepreneurship (van Delft, Gorter and Nijkamp, 2000). According to Waldinger, Aldrich and Ward (1990, p.33), ethnic entrepreneurship can be portrayed as "a set of connections and regular patterns of interaction among people sharing common national background or migration experiences". Other scholars illustrate it as commercial activities, mainly small or sometimes medium-sized businesses, initiated by diasporic communities to fulfil the social and economic demands of exiles of different ethnic groups (Masurel et al., 2002; Rath, 2010). Indeed, this is considered a type of self-employed job that is comparatively the bottom part of the job market (Barrett, Jones and McEvoy, 1996). Subsequently, ethnic start-ups inspire a rise in the cumulative supply of employment facilities of the diaspora community without involving the local manpower (Light and Bonacich, 1988). Moreover, affluent ethnic enterprises can also open the door to job opportunities for the indigenous citizens (Light, Bernard and Kim, 1999) as this study seeks to explore the understanding of how the cultural heritage of the diaspora community impacts their entrepreneurial activities, the following section examines

some contemporary theories related to ethnic entrepreneurship to grasp the knowledge about the formation of ethnic business in the respective community.

2.7.2.1 ETHNIC ENTREPRENEURIAL THEORIES

Several theories were evolved to better understand this phenomenon, but a complete explanation with a single theory is still paradoxical (Volery, 2007). Most of the theoretical skeletons comprise two main strands in ethnic business or entrepreneurship: culturalist and structuralist. The most popular contemporary theories for ethnic businesses are the Middleman theory (Bonacich, 1973), Granovetter's (1985) concept of social embeddedness and Kloosterman, van der Leun and Rath's (1999) mixed embeddedness concept. The study will focus on some major theories of ethnic business under the respective approach outlined above. Certainly, each approach or strand describes the key underlying factors of why the diaspora community aims for entrepreneurial business. In general, members of the diaspora community embracing entrepreneurship in their country of residence to adopt some socio-economic trends that have a significant effect on their day-to-day life, such as social injustice, lack of skills, welfare cuts, and deregulation in the job market are most prominent (Pécoud, 2010).

Culturalist strand

This viewpoint stands on socio-cultural beliefs and components of culture as the primary factors of entrepreneurship. It assigns ethnic business to their particular

traditional and cultural traits instead of opportunities available in the country of residence (Portes and Sensenbrenner, 1993). The main features are family ethics, religious faith and communal unity that encourage the immigrants to do laborious jobs for low pay, which makes the ethnic business more competitive among the mainstream arena. Moreover, strong family ties and a willingness to help each other accelerates financial success in the ethnic community. This cultural strand additionally assumes that the diaspora community has culturally bound attributes key to gravitation to adopt self-employment (Masurel, Nijkamp and Vindigni, 2004). The embedded traits like hard-working commitment, economic lifestyle, and adventure, submissiveness in social values, team spirit, and tendency to be self-employed anticipate 'ethnic resources' which trigger entrepreneurial nature in the ethnic community (Fregetto, 2004).

Light and Bonacich (1988, p18-19) elaborate ethnic resources as "social features of a group which co-ethnic business owners utilize in business or from which their business passively benefits. Ethnic resources include values, knowledge, skills, information attitudes, leadership, solidarity, an orientation to sojourning, and institutions." Of them, solidarity is a key element that reduces the competition and supports co-ethnic entrepreneurs by eliminating transaction expenditures, sharing knowledge and information and allowing access to distant but trustworthy partners (Light and Rosenstein, 1995). In this way, the diaspora community is engaging in entrepreneurial activities. To understand the ethnic activities in the diaspora community, it is important to recognize the ethnic resources shaped by the cultural heritage of that particular community.

In addition, the entrepreneur's skill is also recognized as an inheritance ethnic resource and family plays the central role in tailoring that skill (Borjas, 1993).

Besides, religion also plays a significant role in the respective diaspora community for establishing an entrepreneurial business. For example, Muslims in the diaspora community always tend to go for their own business because business has been given considerable attention by their faith (Ramadani et al., 2015). On the other hand, ethnic bonds also allow migrants to implement their knowledge capital to develop a new business overseas (Portes, Guarnizo and Haller, 2002). Thus, based on culture, the following theories emerged.

Middleman Minority Concept

The following Turner and Bonacich (1980) Middleman minority theory derives from the cultural approach to better understand the readers. The main theme of this theory is the status of the members of ethnic communities in their new country of residence where they have been labelled as 'Minority', which in turn is considered an impetus of entrepreneurship. The minority class tends to entrepreneurial businesses to gain recognition in the host country through ethnic resources or capital because of the exclusion from usual social, political and so on in the society.

This middleman minority prototype claims that migrants become a sojourner in personality and get engaged in middleman professions or the types of business with fewer entry barriers due to host country antagonism, social unfairness and a restricted chance for moving upward (Morokvasic, 1993). According to this theory, entrepreneurs positioned themselves as a middleman where they work as negotiators between ethnic products and consumers and between ethnic employers and employees (Bonacich, 1973). Additionally, the theory also determines the

categories of business that exiles or diaspora entrepreneurs captivate in (Zenner, 1991).

This theory explains how social capital is created in the diaspora community, influencing migrants to create their unique identity in the host community (Butler and Greene, 1997). In particular, trust is one of the underlying factors, assisting in developing social capital in the migrants' society as the members of the group endeavour support and assistance among themselves, which in turn form a powerful bond of shared solidarity and trust (Bonacich and Modell, 1980). Consequently, entrepreneurial businesses established by the different ethnic societies predominantly act as a job market for employing mostly from the same diaspora community and working like an ethnic enclave (Wilson and Portes, 1980). Therefore, it is evident in western countries that cultural elements cause the inclination of Asian diaspora communities to be self-employed in a particular field. For example, members of the Chinese diaspora community strongly involved in the catering industry-led various researchers to assume that some obvious proclivity of their culture enhances the involvement in that type of endeavour (Leung, 2002).

Structuralist strand

In comparison to the cultural strand, structuralist one endorses external features like discrimination, education and communication barriers and others, push the migrant to be self-employed. Moreover, this predisposition to self-employment by migrants is persuaded by the availability of scopes in the host community. However, the reactions derived from the external forces are different depending on the diversity of the diaspora community (Razin and Light, 1998). This approach demonstrates that

members of the diaspora community are squeezed into doing something for their own when realistically fewer chances are available for them to get employed, whereas reward and sovereignty pulled them into entrepreneurial activities probably from paid jobs (Borooah & Hart, 1999).

Fundamentally, this approach claims that the host community settings' dictate or provoke the diaspora community to get involved in the entrepreneurial business (Ojo, 2012). The opportunities offered by the host community should be considered at different levels due to scopes availability varies from one place to another (Boissevain et al., 1990). The significance of different scope availability was strongly confirmed by one study, where researchers conferred evidence for special digressions among same group migrants and digressions between distinct ethnic classes in a similar economic context (Razin and Light, 1998).

Some other logics can fit under the structuralist approach to give a better understanding of the readers. First one is constructed by British researchers, who identify the self-employment as an outcome of the settings where immigrants reside and work: blocked scopes, unavailability of employment for the ethnic groups or inequity results to go for entrepreneurship (Barrett, Jones and McEvoy, 1996), in term of ecological viewpoint, the most number of shops ditch diaspora neighbourhoods and open the floor to migrants which fosters a further process by promising market shaped by immigrants' certain needs (Aldrich, Zimmer and McEvoy, 1989); immigrants or exiles would set up their businesses on those field whose less demanding circumstances (like long shifts of working, poor outcome from the businesses etc.) withdraw their former business owners, either they belong to rich diaspora society or native population (Waldinger, 1994); lastly, immigrants business scopes might derive as a result of migrant or business welcoming policies

or of residence countries factual conditions (Waldinger, Aldrich and Ward, 1990; Gold and Light, 2000). Now the preceding passage will deliberate several theories concerning the structuralist strand.

Disadvantage Theory

It starts with the 'Disadvantage theory', which is encapsulated inside this approach. It originates in sociology and tries to demonstrate the ethnic business considering the obstacles experienced by the migrants in their new country of residence. For example, in the UK, the labour market for the diaspora community is considerably underprivileged (Barrett, Jones and McEvoy, 2001) because of deindustrialization and discrimination (Ram and Jones, 2008). Furthermore, self-employment in the diaspora community results from the deficiency in human capital like communication skills, job experiences and institutional knowledge, incorporated with unobtrusive mobility because of racism, destitution, and lack of knowledge about the national culture of the host country. Therefore, the Disadvantage theory outlooks ethnic businesses as nothing but as a substitute to employment.

Nevertheless, this theory is appropriate in describing the onset of casual and unlawful ventures but not enough to explain the accepted formation of ethnic businesses (Volery, 2007). This theory is reflected in the South Asian diaspora community. People were more prone to get involved in entrepreneurship due to getting rid of the social discrimination in the host society.

Enclave Concept

Another theory embraced by the structuralist strand is Enclave theory which argues that most of the time, the specific requirements for the ethnic products or services are satisfied by the same ethnic group with the understanding of palate and preferences, thus encouraging the establishment of ethnic businesses (Portes, 1995). Consequently, the theory demonstrates that ethnic business is interlinked in a nexus of same ethnic community webs within an independent ethnic zone (Zhou, 2006) and predominantly limited to the social framework and location of the co-ethnic groups (Bonacich and Modell, 1980). For instance, London has several ethnic localities like Whitechapel, Brixton, Barking and Chinatown, where new arrivals come and stay in respective communities to assimilate the host country environment. At the same time, newcomers found the economic possibilities that inevitably placed them within those ethnic localities (Schiller and Çağlar, 2009). So, ethnic businesses can largely be impacted by the economy of the ethnic belt. Migrants living in a large ethnic society are more prone to entrepreneurial activities than those living in comparatively small communities (Evans, 1989). In addition, the growth of ethnic businesses is also affected by the workforce and weight of the respective ethnic market (Fairlie and Meyer, 1996).

The essence of the Enclave theory is based on the structural (enclave) concentration of the ethnic class that facilitates the appearance of entrepreneurship, leading to economic progression (Waldinger, Aldrich and Ward, 1990). Subsequently, ethnic enclaves uphold ethnic business and improve the social capital of the migrants. Compared to middleman groups, enclaves are not scattered among the other populations (Portes, 1995). One study shows, in the UK, most of the ethnic enterprises are getting a stable customer circle because of the diaspora community's dwelling nature (Cook, Ekwulugo and Fallon, 2003). The study also proved that

ethnic endeavours had secured markets built by the diaspora community configuration, which is inheritance in nature (Aldrich et al., 1985).

The Enclave theory also suggests that primary opportunity emerges from inside the diaspora society (Light, 1972). In addition, the notion of ethnic niche emerged from this theory, where specific diaspora community members only provide the secured market scope (Ward, 1987). As a result, secured markets for distinctive ethnic requirements give businesses few shields against the competition with non-ethnic enterprises (Wilson, 1975).

Notwithstanding, the Enclave theory has been criticized for validity and explaining power to other different issues (Crick, Chaudhry, and Batstone, 2001). For example, the emergence of the multinational community and fresh enterprises deriving from the business activities of the diaspora community cannot be justified within the notion of this theory (Zohu, 2006). Furthermore, the second generation of the diaspora community is getting expertise and education. Therefore, this theory cannot explain their transformation from traditional labour-based ethnic businesses to technology-oriented professional enterprises with extensive market demand (Wang and Altinay, 2012). The enclave concept is also important for understanding entrepreneurship in the South Asian diaspora because one of their key features is that they prefer to stay in one place.

Concept of Social Embeddedness

The final theory the researcher discusses under the structuralist approach is social embeddedness theory which allows the reader to understand other logical reasons for getting involved in entrepreneurial activities initiated by the diaspora community. The theory originated by Granovetter in 1985 claims that independent entrepreneurs join in the diaspora related economic nexus, which assist in carrying out businesses (Rath, 2006). It can also be proclaimed that ethnic entrepreneurs do not work in socially isolated areas but are rooted in different diaspora networks that cause economic growth (Rath and Kloosterman, 2000). No doubt, the connotation of this theory is that the escalation in entrepreneurship results from the movement of immigrant entrepreneurs into their community. This embeddedness minimises bargain costs by eliminating explicit agreement, obtaining affluent access to key economic capitals, and giving steady expectations against the consequences of malfeasance (Granovetter, 2002). Specifically, financial matters are not exclusively logical outcomes made utilizing cost-benefit calculation but entrenched in “overarching social structures that affect their form and their outcomes” (Portes, 1995. p.6). In this manner, an individual immigrant is encapsulated in comprehensive social configurations utilizing idiosyncratic connections and networked relationships, portrayed by belief, anticipations and norms (Portes and Sensenbrenner, 1993).

However, capitalizing on the benefits of this social embeddedness depends on a well understanding of its complicated but dynamic procedures (Laud et al., 2015). This is due to a connection to different capitals like cultural, institutional, and economic, reliance on the target followed, and legislative and financial strength at the workplace. Moreover, it is hard to achieve social embeddedness because it results from the coupling between diaspora history and socio-economic and political inclusion. On the other hand, the theory exclusively focuses on the contributing part

of entrepreneurship, which allows the theory to be rejected. At the same time, critics also argue that the theory also pays attention to the unregulated and comparable economy as long as economies do not hold those characteristics in actual life. So, the theory gives narrow attention to the different authoritarian structures, which reflects discrimination in describing them by advancing specific financial activities and suppressing others. Finally, Wang and Altinay (2012, p.7) claim, “like the emergence of most influential theories, embeddedness as a theory has not been fully developed”.

The theories discussed in this section gives the idea of forming the entrepreneurship belt in the diaspora community. However, not every business formed in the community strictly followed the individual theories stated above, sometimes backed up from more than one theory.

2.7.2.2 MODEL AND APPROACH OF ETHNIC ENTREPRENEURSHIP

Based on the criticisms of different ethnic entrepreneurial theories, researchers have developed several contemporary models that disclose that a considerable amount of differentiated study is required to understand the ramifications of ethnic entrepreneurship. Furthermore, the higher proportion of ethnic businesses in the diaspora network has been connected with rapid social flexibility and progress among the diaspora community (Light & Gold, 2000), which causes more concern in exploring ethnic entrepreneurship by scholars. So, this subsection of the literature

review explores some current date models and prototypes of ethnic entrepreneurship that align with the theories discussed in the earlier section to give a comprehensive understanding of the issue.

The Interactive model

Waldinger, Aldrich and Ward developed the model, (1990) demonstrates that a single feature does not trace back to the initiation of the ethnic enterprise, which is accountable for the success in the diaspora community (Voley, 2007). Alternatively, a networked connection between opportunity structures and resources causes the successful outcome of any ethnic enterprise. As entrepreneurship is steered by demand and supply, so concerning the ethnic business, opportunity structure goes to the demand aspect and group resources to the supply side. This model holds the view of interactionism that combines the culturalist and structuralist strands, emphasizing the connection between possibilities available in the host community and the ethnic capitals of a diaspora community (Waldinger, Aldrich and Ward, 1990).

The opportunity dimension elements consist of the market's condition, access to ownership, condition of the labour market, and legislative framework. On the other side, the group resources dimension includes the cultural heritage and the network of the diaspora community, which both the host and immigrant community share. According to this model, niche markets allow the ethnic groups that usually emerge from the new diaspora community to provide specific ethnic products (Aldrich and Waldinger, 1990). The size of the market is determined by the cultural difference

between the diaspora and the host community. So, the greater the difference causes the greater need, creating a larger market (Williams, 2018). However, regardless of the size of the niche market, it offers limited opportunities and when it comes to the access of open market and ethnic entrepreneurs faces strong entry hindrance in the form of financial or knowledge-based because of the presence of local businessmen (Foley, 2008).

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Original figure can be found in Waldinger, R., Aldrich, H. and Ward, R. (1990). Opportunities, group characteristics and strategies. In Waldinger, R. Aldrich, H. and Ward, R. (eds), *Ethnic Entrepreneurs: Immigrant Business in Industrial Societies*, London: Sage, pp. 13–48.

Fig.2.2: Interactive Model of Ethnic Entrepreneurship (Waldinger, Aldrich and Ward, 1990).

The cultural traditions of the group resources dimension are built on the belief that the self-employment of the diaspora community is the outcome of their cultural preferences, which also needs to be considered cautiously so as not to be overemphasized (Putz, 2003). By the same token, the nexus of the diaspora community is nothing but the connection and rapport within and inside the family and the ethnic community that also has a significant aspect in the success of the ethnic business.

So, according to this interactive model, constant interaction exists between the opportunity structures and group characteristics, and sometimes opportunity structures are governed by the strong network of the diaspora community (Ojo, 2012). But when any problems like collecting information, manpower resources, political incursion, business rivalry, consumers and distributors, capitals and others emerge from the interaction, ethnic strategies support the solution (Boissevain et al., 1990).

Even though this model is beneficial in the categorization of entrepreneurship and the predecessor to many in-depth conceptual frameworks, it is not free from criticisms, particularly for its methods and inadequate consideration of social status and gender (Light & Rosenstein, 1995b). Other criticisms are inadequate importance on the procedures of ethnicization of migrants (Collins et al., 1995), consequent view that migrants' entrepreneurs perform diversely than conventional entrepreneurs (Kloosterman & Rath, 2003), and the model usually tends to assume ethnic uniformity and oversight intra-ethnic heterogeneity. Furthermore, it also tends to ignore the impression of the host community on diasporic entrepreneurship activities (Light and Bhachu, 1993). This model neglects the embeddedness of diaspora entrepreneurs in the host community, which can be used as an influencing determinant. Moreover, the complexity of policy and administrative framework and banking structure cannot be explained by this model (Light and Gold, 2000).

The mixed embedded model

The notion of this model is based on a diversified approach resulting from the identification of the importance of market dynamics and regulations (Kloosterman,

Leun, and Rath, 1999; Kloosterman and Rath, 2001). However, the mixed embedded model is the upgraded version of the opportunity structures and diaspora resources, beneficial in reconsidering the inside group resources and expanded financial and institutional setting in which diaspora entrepreneurship is inevitably integrated (Volery, 2007). Although the economic domain varies broadly on a national level, it offers at a large extent various scopes from one place to another place. This paradox was highlighted by Razin and Light (1998), who supported the evidence for geographical deviations among the identical diaspora groups and deviations between various diaspora societies in a similar economic environment.

2.7.3 SOUTH ASIAN DIASPORA ENTREPRENEURSHIP IN UK

Asians have been strongly represented in the UK for more than 400 years, partly due to the East India Company and generally for the British Empire (Seaman, Bent and Unis, 2016a). Different Asian diaspora networks formed from the different regions of the sub-continent in the UK, who usually arrived following war after labour requirements in the 1950s along with their experiences and choices (Kitwood and Borrill, 1980). In the beginning, males worked in textile factories in Britain, whereas women were house workers, of whom many preferred night shifts and adjustable working design (Penn, Martin and Scattergood, 1991). On the other side, Scotland employed immigrants in jute mills, the transport sector, building construction and bake shops in Glasgow because of their lack of skills. However, the scenario began to change in the 1960s, when the migrants from south Asia found the way to ascend

the financial employment ladder by setting small enterprises, which slowly changed their social status in the host community (Devine and McCarthy, 2018).

Census 2011 in the UK reveals the ethnic minority groups' percentage in Scotland had doubled to 4% from 2% in census 2001. Consequently, the population of the Asian community became 141,100 in 2011 from 69,000 in 2001, with a 1% rise. The census in 2011 also identified that in the Asian diaspora community, the Pakistani minority group is the largest compared to the others, holding one per cent of the whole community (Scotland's Census.gov.uk, 2011).

The culture of that community predominantly determines the nature of employment in the diaspora community. Informal evidence shows that parental profession acts as a key prognosticator of academic accomplishment and future occupation in children; for example, Indians are more in the medical occupation, Pakistanis in retail and manufacturing sectors and Bangladeshis in the restaurant industry as their first generation was employed in the respective sector (Seaman, Bent and Unis, 2016b). Certainly, a significant number of people in the diaspora community are in entrepreneurial activity because the percentage of self-employment in ethnic groups (17%) is higher significantly than the local white Scottish origin people (12%) (Scotland's Census.gov.uk, 2011).

A significant amount of research has been done concerning the ethnic community business since the 1970s when the first generation entered the start-up business (Light and Bonacich, 1988; Waldinger, Aldrich, and Ward 1990). Most of the studies focus on understanding the motive of starting entrepreneurship (Deakins, Majmudar and Paddison, 1997), clarifying the reasons and procedures of business by the

members of the minority communities, source of capital and market penetration (Deakins et al., 2009).

Two factors influence the diaspora communities' motivation to entrepreneurial activities: push and pull (Kickul and Zaper, 1999). Therefore, first-degree Asian immigrants in Scotland were pushed into their own business due to unfavourable circumstances and inequity at the workplace. So, the notion of entrepreneurship in the exile community can be seen as a substitute for unemployment in Scotland (Phizacklea and Ram, 1995).

Apart from the push factors, the work culture of a diaspora community drives them into the business to achieve a better future for their family (Chua, Chrisman and Sharma, 1999). So, south Asian ethnic businesses are a fair example of the social embeddedness of financial performances within their social context, where the cultural network within the diaspora community provides financial sources for starting entrepreneurship (Granovetter, 2002).

On the contrary, pull factors create scope for the second generation into entrepreneurial activities (Jones and Ram, 2003). One study shows that the second generation of the diaspora community in Scotland is highly educated than their predecessor and motivated firmly despite coming from family business context and related job experiences (Ram et al., 2003).

In the context of Scotland, the consensus in 2011 reveals that the diaspora community in Scotland is small but comparatively quickly expanding in a well-integrated manner (Seaman, Bent and Unis, 2016a). The stereotype, 'taxis and restaurants' labelled to the Asian diaspora community is becoming old fashioned, which was previously reinforced by some research work (Ram and Jones, 2008).

Culture is considered an identity for the South Asian diaspora community. Studies carried out in this area mainly focused on how entrepreneurial activities developed in this community. However, very little attention is paid to the cultural norms and values, which also have strong influence in the family and decision-making process. Therefore, cultural heritage and its influencing power on the family business in the South Asian diaspora is the key feature of this study. This study will address the gap in understanding how the culture determines the agents' actions in the family. The key components of the South Asian Diaspora family include patriarchy, Islamic faith, and obedience to the command of senior members in the family, seeking opinions from friends and relatives. Agents in the family embodied these norms and attitudes from their childhood and reproduced this behaviour.

2.8 ANALYTICAL TOOLKIT OF THE STUDY

Before discussing the methodology chapter, it is essential to inform the reader about the outline of theoretical lenses that were applied in this study. Particularly, this research embraced the influential and ground-breaking work of French sociologist Pierre Bourdieu. Therefore, the subsequent section provides an abstract of Bourdieu's analytical toolkit and especially his oeuvre to the sociology of family, culture and entrepreneurialism in the diaspora community. Thereupon, Bourdieu's key notions of habitus, capital and field are thoroughly considered. Bourdieusian concept of field is suitable for this study that explains how he (Bourdieu) perceived family as a distinct field of reproduction where individual's dispositions for specific actions could be developed. Moreover, it is also important to understand how an individual acts in the other fields, particularly the retail food industry with habitus developed in the family field and with the help of different forms of capital gained

over some time. Thus, this section has addressed the key issues of Bourdieu field theory related to the family in the diaspora community to analyse how those have been implemented in the different practices.

2.8.1 BOURDIEU'S THEORIES-THE METAPHYSICAL ORIGINS

Given this study adopts a Bourdieusian analysis, it is essential to locate his core formula, habitus+field+capital, with his theoretical development. The rationale being that Bourdieusian theory mirrors the dynamics of structure and agency and resistances or tension found within this study (Weininger, 2005). Like many others before him, Bourdieu adopted the concepts from his predecessors in sociology to develop these exclusive theories. Additionally, Bourdieu was qualified in the traditional theories on philosophy and had given lectures on the works of Durkheim and Saussure intending to establish the boundaries of those "pure theories" (Bourdieu, 1990a, p.6).

The preliminary work of Bourdieu provided structuralism in the academia of Algeria. The notion of his structuralism can be viewed in the concept of the societal world as an objective spatial relationship that provides transformation in the individuals (Bourdieu, 1979). In the beginning of his career, Bourdieu labelled himself as "a blissful structuralist" (Bourdieu, 1990b, p.9) in his work on the Kabyle house. This was the selection of Bourdieu's work dedicated to Levi-Strauss' birthday in 1970 and is a good piece of work on how behavioural observations can be applied to deduce power struggles between individuals. In that study, Bourdieu applied his structuralist stance to describe the relationship between the physical structure of the habitat of

the individuals and their social relations using it. From that very social phenomenon, he reached the conclusion about the customs and faith of the community in Kabyle, Algeria. This study is also about the 'faith and community of the south Asian diaspora community where Islam and Islamic culture are at their centre. Therefore, Bourdieusian analysis was considered as an excellent example in terms of structuralist analysis in his era. After reviewing Bourdieu's early work, Scholte (1973, p.3) described it as follows: "Bourdieu's article (translated into English and published in Social Science Information) is without a doubt one of the finest illustrations I know of concrete, ethnographic, and structural analysis. This study of the interior of a Kabyle house is exemplary of what the analysis of a "total social fact" is and should be all about."

Bourdieu's primary works describe the power discrepancy between males and females, explicitly demonstrated in the structuralist skeleton of how the natural world rules over the social microcosm. It is evident as follows in his work on the Kabyle house:

"The orientation of the house is fundamentally defined from outside, from the standpoint of men, and, so to speak, by men and for men, as the place men come out of. 'Man is the lamp of the outside, woman the lamp of the inside.' [...] 'Man trusts in God, woman looks to man for everything.'" (Bourdieu, 1979, p. 153).

On the other hand, at the same time, within this structuralist perception, it could not be able to clarify how power discrepancies emerge, how norms and demeanours are shaped, and in addition, how a person in the society is personalized and becomes influenced by the outside structures. Therefore, Bourdieu was ultimately to refuse the

Levi-Strauss and others structuralism as they were likely to eliminate social agents to a simple "automata, regulated like clocks, in accordance with laws they do not understand" (Bourdieu, 1990a, p. 9).

The questions mentioned above about structuralism leave Bourdieu to rethink his philosophical position repeatedly. Although, he was largely influenced by the philosopher Wittgenstein who identified that philosophers should possess "radical doubt", arguing that the individual questions themselves and why they "obeying a rule" (Bourdieu, 1990a, p.9) or structuring relations that surround them as such Bourdieu maintained the reflexive quality or essential need to continuously ask questions of those restrictions and habits that drive our thinking and acts. This process led Bourdieu to his conception of 'habitus' as a set of behaviours and norms that are generally unconscious, which individuals seldom challenge. Therefore, for Bourdieu, the habitus provides that grounding of structuring relations governs the subconscious mind and provides power or deriving force over the individuals' lives.

The limitations in structuralism philosophy led Bourdieu to divert his mind into Durkheim's work. Durkheim, considered amongst the pioneers of sociology, highlighted the significance of extrinsic social constructs concerning the individual but have controlling power on an individual's language and choices (Durkheim, 1893). Moreover, Durkheim's work comprises relationships, resources and culture. Therefore, Durkheim's work influenced Bourdieu and gave him a new window to think. The social constructs in Durkheim's work have strong influential power on human behaviour, and thus social scientists can analyse those structures easily by being impartial. Bourdieu, inspired by the notion Durkheim established, is that in order to govern the policy, social studies can be generalized. Durkheim exploited huge data sets to examine social conduct (Durkheim, 1897). That reflects later in

Bourdieu's work, where he used datasets originated from the government organizations to interpret social values.

In Durkheim's works, it is evident that he applied ethnography as a methodology to establish the clan concept, which was considered the most ancient financial activity unit (Durkheim, 1893). According to the concept, a clan performs shared responsibilities among its members, for example, free support and behaving uncompassionately with its competitors. Moreover, Durkheim anticipated that clans evolved from the family as financially driven. But, on the other hand, family is the ancient format of social agreement that is run mainly by civic solidarity, which is composed of a group of shared commitments and values enforced on them (Durkheim, 1995). Therefore, the clans and family concepts of Durkheim can yet be applied to explain a family firm in the starting or growing stage where its members assist each other in the business without any costs.

However, Durkheim's works were unable to anticipate the fact that the native ethnic groups in Australia and the United States were also able to share a typical social framework with modern industrialized societies. Though that idea was dubious in nature at that point in time, Bourdieu used the notions and systematic methods of Durkheim to the civilized western society (Di Maggio, 1979). In addition, Bourdieu claimed that categorizations like habitus, field and capitals' possibly originated from the Kabyle tribes in the north of Algeria but were also applicable to modern society in France. Moreover, Durkheim's clan concept and methodological diversities like ethnography and quantitative approaches were also applicable to the urbanized societies.

Apart from using mixed methodological approaches and social classifications originated from being an ethnographer, Bourdieu was even inquisitive about the language and its power usage. The Bourdieusian notion of language came out from the work of Wittgenstein, which is the way of both communication and construction of an individual's thought. Wittgenstein critiqued Cartesian thought that the individual's physical capacity and thinking power are the two distinct conceptions (Crossley, 2013). From this point of view, Bourdieu underlined habit as a mental process and a physical characteristic of a person. For example, Bourdieu mentioned how people know where to put fingers in typing, though they are unconscious while performing the act (Bourdieu et al., 1993). In the Bourdieusian concept, habitus is considered a corporal capacity that requires time to become flawless and a mental disposition (Lizardo, 2004). Therefore, habitus can be communicated via language and framed under language like specific phrases and terminologies that are deemed admissible in the particular context.

Lastly, Marx's work also motivated Bourdieu to develop his theory. In the Marxian view, Bourdieu considered people do not depend on their condition while making their history (Webb, Schirato, & Danaher, 2002). However, Bourdieu did not consider the economic viewpoint of the society, but it was evident in his notion of different types of capital and the financial capital that he used Marxian dialectics (Bourdieu, 1985). Ultimately, Bourdieu was curious about the power transmission, which has certain significance in this research. Family businesses, particularly run by the diasporic community, members in the lower rank of the hierarchy incapacitated to give an opinion or to model the firm, and are obeyed by the verbal orders and language of the senior, are appropriate to the implementation of the power theories.

This subsection has outlined the philosophical underpinnings of the Bourdieusian constructs. The various utilizations of his theories reflect their mixed origins that in turn rationalizes how influential and adaptable those concepts are. As highlighted above, Bourdieu's philosophical position and research trajectory changed, developing into his, now famous, formula of 'habitus+field+capital' (ref), which he deploys to explain a wide range of social contexts, including culture and art (Bourdieu, 1984), learning and education (Bourdieu & Passeron, 1990), sports and recreations (Bourdieu, 1978), and religion (Bourdieu, 1990a). Given this focus on the dynamic interplay of cultural heritage, community, family business and enterprise and the challenges of the digital marketing field and its technology adoption and impact, this research sees the application of a Bourdieusian lens as appropriate. Therefore, it is essential to provide a brief discussion of Bourdieu's core concepts.

2.8.2 HABITUS

Bourdieu's habitus concept aims to demonstrate not only the "the historical and cultural production of individual practices" but also "the individual production of practices-since the individual always acts from self-interest" (Webb, Danaher and Schirato, 2002). Bourdieu has acknowledged that the notion of the habitus is basically evolved from Aristotle's vocabulary 'hexis' "that is usually translated as 'state', 'stable disposition', 'habitus', 'way of being', or even 'possession' " (Rodrigo, 2011). Apart from Aristotle, Bourdieu was also largely influenced by the work of Mauss, Hegel and Husserl in the development of habitus (Bourdieu, 1990a). Hegel's

work is based on 'sittlichkeit' which means 'ethical life' where individuals use their own cultural interpretation of what is moral for their everyday life (Moyar, 2011). Basically, Hegel's ethical life was derived in retaliation to Kantian 'moral life' and here moral is enduring and ubiquitous in nature. On the other hand, Husserl's notion of 'Habitualität' or habitus is based on how individuals grow constant ways of thinking which in turn become solidified into long-lasting dogma or belief (Moran and Cohen, 2012). In addition, Mauss outlined an anthropological description about habitus and according to Mauss, habitus is a physical technique which is explicit to the social framework and exhibits one's expertise of the social setting (Mauss, 1979).

Habitus is considered as the "key concept" (Sapiro, 2007, p.37a) or the "core concept" (Bonnewitz, 2003, p.63) of the Bourdieu's oeuvre but Bourdieu's work does not provide a clear definition of it. However, Bourdieu's habitus concept created misinterpretations, many academics used it inaccurately, was extremely doubted, earned reviews and aggravated immense debates and discussions in the social sciences field (Asimaki and Koustourakis, 2014). Undoubtedly, this Bourdieusian construct can perform meaningfully, but also can be confusing since it does not provide a straightforward definition (Maton, 2008). For that reason, Dortier (2008, p.11) simply marks "don't search Bourdieu's work for a clear definition of habitus".

Therefore, Bourdieu, all in his career, reconsidered the narrative of habitus for addressing the critics and met the requirements of fresh and contemporary factual applications (Crossley, 2013). Bourdieu's habitus has been criticised as an "obscurantism" (Lizardo, 2004, p.378), also his definitions has been remarked as an "elliptical" and sometimes "inaccessible" (DiMaggio, 1979, p.1462). Consequently, Bourdieu's writing was labelled as "long-winded, obscure, complex and intimidatory"

(Jenkins, 2002, p. 9). Since the beginning, definition of habitus by Bourdieu seems roughly circular:

“The structures constitutive of a particular type of environment [...] produce *habitus*, systems of durable, transposable *dispositions*, structured structures predisposed to function as structuring structures, that is, as principles of the generation and structuring of practices and representations which can be objectively ‘regulated’ and “regular” without in any way being the product of obedience to rule” (Bourdieu, 1977,p.72).

The language Bourdieu has used to explain habitus, is repetitive in nature and contained loops through which he tried to break out the simplistic divisions (Edelman et al., 1992). The most significant criteria of all works of Bourdieu is the opposition to the dichotomies existing in social science as well as in the sociology field. Therefore, Bourdieu’s work attempts to reach beyond those polarities which he thinks illogical, and because of this, he additionally contradicts with the basic antagonism the objectivism versus subjectivism, Marxism versus Durkheimian, macro versus micro sociology, social physics versus phenomenology and so on (Asimaki and Koustourakis, 2014). As a result, Bourdieu rejected determinism because he observed that determinism in social life is the key imperfection of those who are structuralists (Bourdieu, 1990a). He also rejected the notion that individuals’ determine action based on their rationality and unconsciousness. Though Bourdieusian literature is hard to interpret, the constructs he made are influential.

Bourdieu develops his own paradigm in sociology, which he termed as “constructed or genetic structuralism”, the notion is established on the combination of objectivity

with subjectivity (Corcuff, 2007, p.27). He considered habitus as a span between extrinsic structures and intrinsic decision of determination of action. Bourdieu (1987, p.147) states his new construct as

“...saying structuralism I mean that in the social world there are...objective structures independent of the consciousness (awareness and desire) of the carriers [....]. By the term constructed I mean that there is a double social genesis. On the one hand, forms of attitude, thought and action.....of what I call hexis-habitus, and on the other, the social structures, what I call fields and groups [...].”

To make it more clearly for the readers, habitus will be discussed more explicitly in the following section.

According to Bourdieu's work, habitus can be characterized in three different ways. Firstly, habitus can be described as an absolute capability of generating products of ideas, interpretations, responses, and thoughts. Bourdieu (1990b, p.55) states:

“the habitus is an infinite capacity for generating products-thoughts, perceptions, expressions, actions- whose limits are set by the historically and socially situated conditions of its production”.

From the above definition, it can be said that habitus is nothing but a concept that lies in the individuals' mind that leads to their actions in such a way that they cannot be thoroughly integrated. Moreover, it could not be in the logical concerns of the person performing it. Therefore, in this point, the construct of habitus intersects *theories of power* of Bourdieu where “one of the privileges of the dominant, who move in their world as fish in water, resides in the fact that they need not engage in rational compilation in order to reach the goals that best suit their interests” (Bourdieu,

1990a,p.107). It means that habitus naturally produces socially acceptable behaviour that fulfils individuals' interest. However, the individual who does not have dominance power in the community, either he or she cannot figure out habitus or may be an individual's interest cannot be met by the habitus. It can be seen as an example, a factory worker will not be able to talk intelligently in the museum about artwork, his quietness or inexperienced opinion will be accepted as evidence of his lack of knowledge. In this perspective, habitus turns into a commodity of necessity. Bourdieu observed that poor labour class people consume rich and high fat food because of their inability to go for second choice and it is due to their habitus which is unavoidable outcome of financial necessity, still they are labelled as being class racism and tasteless where "Taste is *amor fati*, the choice of destiny, but a forced choice, produced by conditions of existence which rule out all alternatives as mere daydreams and leave no choice but the taste for the necessary" (Bourdieu, 1984,p.178).

Bourdieu (1990a, p.77) revisited the first definition of habitus and produced more precise definition:

"The habitus, as the system of dispositions to a certain practice, is an objective basis for regular modes of behaviour, and thus for the regularity of modes of practice, and if practices can be predicted, this is because the effect of the habitus is that agents who are equipped with it will behave in a certain way in certain circumstances".

Secondly, from the revised definition, habitus can be described as a symbol or embodiment of cultural norms, in other words, earned dispositions which can be gained via the interactions between the people as well as social context of the

interactions. It can also be said from the new definition that the concept of habitus is nothing but the manifestations of individual behaviour, it is not theoretical. Therefore, habitus is replicable without unequivocal direction and due to this nature, the people in the same ethnic community show similar types of behaviour. Moreover, due to having a predictive power in habitus, design of propositions for future activities can be possible, set up on the past experiences. This view makes the notion of habitus notably important for this study that tries to describe how cultural heritage, has influencing power of forming a Muslim diaspora habitus, can envision the behaviour with regard to social media implementation for the business. Habitus foresees the role of individuals' role as well as collective behaviour to exhibit an organised response. The predictive nature of the habitus mean that cultural heritage of the Muslim diaspora community should be distinct over a several diverse behaviour. According to the class in the same society, habitus would appear differently. Therefore, Bourdieu illustrated the middle class habitus as:

“Banalities about art, literature or cinema are inseparable from the steady tone, the slow, casual diction, the distant or self-assured smile, the measured gesture, the well-tailored suit and the bourgeois salon of the person who pronounces them” (Bourdieu,1984,p.174).

From the above description about habitus means that, habitus is also a physical exhibition of the individual like the hexis which is beared through manner, posture, dialect and costume in the body. Therefore, habitus can be act as a bodily state which can also be characterised as “as a system of acquired dispositions functioning on the practical level as categories of perception and assessment or as classificatory principles as well as being the organizing principles of action meant constituting the

social agent in his true role as the practical operator of the construction of objects” (Bourdieu, 1990a, p.13).

Finally, habitus can be remarked as a descriptive system that allows us to give a name according to the forms of the individual or object. It is important to note that in Bourdieu’s work, there is a tension between his dislike of binary antagonism and his eagerness to apply straightforward classifications. However, he observed the fact and applied simple categorization and mentioned that people outset to evaluate individual in the following way:

“The network of oppositions between high (sublime, elevated, pure) and low (vulgar, low, modest), spiritual and material, fine (refined, elegant) and coarse (heavy, fat, crude, brutal), [...] is the matrix of all the commonplaces which find such ready acceptance because behind them lies the whole social order” (Bourdieu, 1984, p.468).

Though those categorizations are beneficial for the social scientist and anthropologist, Bourdieu also informs that classification leaves us the controlling and controlled individuals’ in the society. Subsequently, the taxonomies used in Bourdieusian oeuvre are inevitably value laden. Bourdieu questions about the inference that social schemata is subjected to change, to describe this, he applied statistical instruments, and the controlling group always attempts to retain rather than alter the current status. Therefore, habitus will govern the integrity in the customs and habits of a cluster or group due to its durable nature (Bourdieu, 1990a) and it lets family firm to acquire information via the prism of what is acceptable and standard behaviour and at the same time inhibits learning because it holds the behaviours which they already inherited.

Interestingly, Bourdieu clearly placed his explanation of habitus opposed to the existing understanding of habitus where individuals' are aware of their behaviours and deliberately choose how to conduct them. Therefore, Bourdieu marked it impracticable that "each action [is] a sort of unprecedented confrontation between the subject and the world." (Bourdieu, 1986, p.42). From this notion, it can be said that habitus educates individuals how to react both quickly and subconsciously. Nevertheless, in crisis periods, it cannot be responded to and may be interrupted on behalf of logical understanding. Bourdieu clarifies this as follows:

"By way of aside, habitus is one principle of production of practices among others and although it is undoubtedly more frequently in play than any other [...] certainly in situations of crisis which disrupt the immediate adjustment of habitus to field - by other principles, such as rational and conscious computation" (Bourdieu, 1990a, p.108).

In the context of a family, members usually share the habitus and its notion provides significance to the historical facts. Moreover, in terms of operating the habitus, the course of time is very important: shared exercises and power framework are worked together in a means of replication, in the form of day to day interactions. Individuals usually encountered history as the granted requirements of every day's customs. Thereby, it shapes the foundation of habitus. For that reason, habitus can be explained as "a shared body of dispositions, classificatory categories and generative schemes is, if it is nothing else, the outcome of collective history" (Jenkins, 2002, p. 80).

In the field of family run organization, habitus turns up like a 'culinary sink' atmosphere where repeated clash exists between hierarchical order in the family, for

instance, parents particularly father who always looks he's grown young boy or daughter as a disobedient fellow, despite the fact that they become mature and their measures have changed.

Basically, to what degree one family can change further its habitus, made from the previous behaviour as well as the implementation of doxa, to enable for knowing from the recent experiences and manners. However, the flaw of Bourdieusian habitus notion is, it is experienced inevitably, without conventional guidance. On the other hand, this might not be correct in a family firm, where usually a masculine character remain the solid founder, often clearly determines what would be the desirable manners, both inside the family and across the family firm (García-Álvarez and López-Sintas, 2001).

Bourdieu in his Kabyle house study mentioned that Kabyle habitus restrains innovation or adoption of new things, and added “if innovation is always suspect - and not only inasmuch as it flouts tradition - this is because the peasants are always inclined to see it as the desire to distinguish oneself, to stand apart, a way of challenging others and crushing them” (Bourdieu, 1979, p.19).

Though this research will implement Bourdieusian notion of habitus, field and capital to the Muslim diasporic family businesses in Glasgow, the real habitus, field and capital will vary between the contemporary family business and the Kabyle house. It is due to the Kabyle society, in an Algerian rural area before the industrial revolution, founded on vast kinship is certainly distinct from the small food retail businesses based upon traditional nuclear family format in the South Asian exile community in Glasgow. Modern small and medium-sized enterprises which include small food retail businesses are sincerely urged to be creative (Foresight, 2013).

Therefore, innovation and new technology adoption would be supposed to be a component of the modern small food retail businesses habitus. For that reason, it can be expected that small food retail firms run by the diasporic family have established a habitus which discards culture and tradition, embodies competitions and are smart to accept changes according to the context.

2.8.3 FIELD

Again the concept of field is central to Bourdusian theory. In Gestalt psychology, Bourdieu followed Kurt Koffka (Crossley, 2013), who designed a psychological explanation of field theory (Koffka, 1935), claiming that individuals in their life period construct a field and construct a notion or gestalt through consolidating distinct components from his or her lives. Moreover, Koffka recognises individuals by gathering individual components such as family, job, sexual drive or interest to reconstruct their overall view of the world.

In his notion of field theory, Bourdieu clearly admitted the impact of the work of Cassirer and Lewin (Bourdieu & Wacquant, 1992). Like the previous meanings of field, in the Bourdieusian field construct, the core part is the context framework where the powers exist between each component in the field. However, Bourdieu views the societal world as a relative space and field as an independent space of operation which holds the doxa or the standards of operation; that doxa sets the affinities amidst the actors within a specific field.

Therefore, the field can be described as an organised space of rankings or positions among the actors where everyone is fighting to get superior status or position in that

particular field. In the French language, 'champs' also refers to a field of the game like 'champs des courses' or 'racetrack', and grassland like 'champs-elysees'. Hence, Bourdieu's field concept only remains when competitions or forced conflicts are present among the actors. Moreover, the field is usually uncertain or volatile, including inconstant dissemination of force at any point in time. Bourdieu mentioned this as follows:

“[...] fields, as historically constituted areas of activity with their specific institutions and their own laws of functioning. The existence of a specialized and relatively autonomous field is correlative with the existence of specific stakes and interests: [...] they arouse in the agents endowed with a certain habitus, the field and its stakes (themselves produced as such by relations of power and struggle in order to transform the power relations that are constitutive of the field) [...]” (Bourdieu, 1990a, p.87-88).

From the above-complicated explanation about the field, it is evident that Bourdieu drew a relationship between the field and his habitus construct. The characteristics of each actor of a particular field are determined by its degree of power, concern and habitus. Those criteria create controlled and controlling agents in a specific field. Therefore, how the agents act and apply their strategies can merely be realized relationally: how an actor or agent engages with others near them.

From the above, rather complicated quotation, the field can be summarised as the interplay between the actor's habitus and the field development of the field. Habitus endows the actor with the 'investments', allowing them to enter and engage with the

field. However, while legitimating the field itself, the power struggles that take place therein also reshape and solidify the field as a dynamic social construct.

Durkheim, in his work, differentiated between the various kinds of conflict between the different economic fields; also identified that, however within a particular field, not every agent does take part in the competition. He mentioned this as follows:

“The Soldier seeks military glory, the priest moral authority, the statesman power, the business man riches, the scholar scientific renown. Each of them can attain his end without preventing others from attaining theirs'. [...] Since they perform different services, they can perform them parallelly” (Durkheim, 1893, p.267).

This resonates with the likes of Foucault, who sees these spaces as a discursive construct within which actors are shaped and effect a 'technology of the self. That is the 'soldiers' (marches, fights, salutes as a soldier), the nurse (heals, tends and administers), the priest (prays, preaches and pastors the flock). So simple in this space, the garments and actions reinforce and legitimize the field, the actor, behaviours, and prohibitions.

Though the works or duties are sometimes close and just similar, then rivalry is inescapable. Therefore, when rivalry rises, the agents strive for the very same sources. That is because the agents in the specific field carry out precisely a similar job; they usually do not thrive protecting their mates' harm (Durkheim, 1893).

Bourdieu was fascinated about the forces lying in the field that produce clashes among the agents where scarcity of resources are present, and rivalry becomes intense to acquire those resources. Furthermore, if actors struggle for resources in business, then attempts are redirected to tackling those struggles. That bypass of attempts can be disadvantageous for the business regarding work accomplishment, as developed in the agency theory (Fama and Jensen, 1983).

From Durkheim's point of view, families should be freed from such forms of field conflict because he believed that there is a clear distinction between the family field and the business field. He described this as follows:

“Family members share in common their entire existence, whereas the members of a corporation share only their professional concerns. The family is a kind of complete society whose influence extends to economic activity as well as to that of religion, politics and science etc.”
(Emirbayer, 2003, p.222).

From the above description, it is clear that the family and the business are two different but overlying fields where the same actors are playing different roles like a father-shop owner, son-staff but having the same power in different positions.

At this point of the field theory, the study will discuss why agents in the particular field want to remain. Importantly, Bourdieu added the concept of *illusio* to link and further substantiate the concepts of field and *doxa*. Bourdieu's *illusio* provides the basis of how agents are captivated or caught up in and off the field. Therefore, by *illusio* Bourdieu means how “[...] players are taken in by the game, they oppose one

another, sometimes with the ferocity, only to the extent that they concur in their belief (doxa) in the game and its stakes; they grant these a recognition that escapes questioning. Players agree, by the mere fact of playing and not by the way of 'contract', that the game is worth playing." (Bourdieu and Wacquant, 1992, p.98)

Bourdieu's *illusio* notion is derived from the game 'Ludus' and also linked to the 'collusion', which is the foundation of the competition. Every field demands its actors to possess *illusio* for preparing themselves to spend in the interest of the play and to build "practical mastery of its rules" (Bourdieu & Wacquant, 1992, p. 117). In essence, through *illusio*, the actors perform the field, embodying and enacting the field and legitimate the field, its *Doxa*, which in turn and with others creates a self-perpetuating dynamic process. This process and how it works or works out in the dynamic interactions of the study will be evidenced in the analysis section.

In the perspective of a business owner, besides is a father, who acts as a father-owner agent, running the family equally as a 'playing field' and business as a 'killing field'. He could have a different *habitus* for his family field, including casual dress, a lenient manner to the offspring, gestures like cuddling, and warm language like affections. This is because *habitus* and field are run by *Doxa* or rules that set up and provide a sense to the behaviours. The *Doxa* of a family usually runs on a longer basis, which is the whole lifecycle of each actor. In addition, the *doxa* of a family gives preference to the support and safeguard of the other actors or members of the family. Despite this coordinated example, as time moves on, there could still be segments of a power clash, for example, weak and dependent elderly parents on children; second marriage, that unveils a new actor in the family as a step-parent along with creating a new degree of power among the children.

2.8.4 CAPITAL

The final construct of Bourdieu's theoretical trinity is capital, which is closely related to the notion of habitus and field. Capital provides a view on how an individual's resources in a particular area are favoured, degraded, exchanged and captured (Bourdieu, 1985). Bourdieu (1984, p.114) describes capital as "the set of actually usable resources and powers" that he classified into three core types "economic capital, cultural capital and [...]Social capital".

The fascinating feature of capital is that it is circumstances based, which means the appropriate resources for a certain social context might not be considered in another circumstance (Beames and Telford, 2013). Therefore, Bourdieu (1993, p.73) points out that "capital is effective in relation to a particular field". He also argued that people, either individually or in groups, fight within a particular field to upgrade their position about the different forms of capital that determine the field (Bourdieu, 1989; Bourdieu, 1993).

Economic or financial capital is reasonably straight that describes one's economic status, and undoubtedly more substantial than the other forms of capital. Concerning the family business, it may be instantly connected to the number of opportunities the business has. Social capital describes the individual's having the number of "social connections" (Bourdieu, 1985, p.47). Economic capital is fairly straightforward in that it refers to one's financial position and is certainly more tangible than other types of capital. With regard to physical activity, economic capital may be directly related to the number of opportunities young people have. That said, social and cultural capital

is no less important in explaining the possibilities for people in different social fields. Social capital, for instance, refers to an individual's stock of "social connections" (Bourdieu, 1986, p.47), that is, the relational networks that allow individuals to maximise their ability to convert capital into different forms.

Social capital can also be described as the total of factual and possible resources which can be used across a substantial structure of the relationship (Bourdieu, 1985). Access to the social network allows the agent to benefit from jointly owned and mutual capital (Bowey and Easton, 2007). When it comes to the point of conversation, it is evident that conversion of social capital to different forms of cultural capital becomes harder than on the other way around (Anheier, Gerhards and Romo, 1995). However, conversion can be possible through the technique of correlational learning (Karataş-Özkan, 2011). In relation to the transformation of symbolic capital from social capital, connection with famous agents can cause a positive impact (Reuber and Fischer, 2005), while relation with dubious agents can destroy reputation (Bourdieu, 1985).

On the other hand, cultural capital relates to all symbolic and material goods that might give an individual a higher status in society. Bourdieu (1985) also explained that cultural capital exists in three forms. Firstly, in the embodied state, as in how one acts; secondly, in the objectified state, in the form of cultural goods that one possesses (i.e. books); and finally, in the institutionalised state, in the form of educational qualifications that one has acquired (Bourdieu, 1985). Therefore, cultural capital can be described as an expansion of personal capital that denotes mostly the ability, training and job experience of individual entrepreneurs (Pret, Shaw and Drakopoulou Dodd, 2016). The capitals got conversion criterion, and due to this, the embodied cultural capital in the form of different economic status permits agents to

spread broad social or community networks (Anderson and Miller, 2003). Moreover, skills and expertise in specific areas lead to the design of cultural goods that hold financial value (Bhagavatula et al., 2010), and experience in specific industries can enhance fame building (Bitektine, 2011). Conversely, the absence of cultural capital could restrict the capacity to accommodate socially accepted habitus and, therefore, restrain entry to the public networks and inhibit status improvement (De Clercq and Voronov, 2009; Lounsbury and Glynn, 2001).

Symbolic capital is another form of capital that can be generated from the capitals mentioned above (Bourdieu, 1985). This type of capital is considered a powerful capital as it can produce the quality, trust, and justify the agents' actions (De Clercq and Voronov, 2009). Reputation, social status and fame are related to symbolic capital (Terjesen and Elam, 2009). This capital can also be transformed into cultural as well as social capital by accessing educational institutions and community networks (Lawrence, 2004). On the other hand, inadequate symbolic capital restrains agents' performance in the given field and provides negative effects on fame and performance (Reuber and Fischer, 2007).

The main theme of Bourdieu's habitus, field and capital is that every agent competes for the different forms of capital to acquire authoritative stands within the particular field. The agent's actions are governed by the socially framed habitus (Karataş-Özkan, 2011). In any given field, the power relations of the agents are valid due to the conversion of the capitals (De Clercq and Voronov, 2009). Moreover, each field evolves and validates particular types, sizes and dispensation of capital (Drakopoulou-Dodd et al., 2014; Lawrence, 2004) and the fight for securing the capitals resulted from subliminal processes administered by the habitus of the agents (Tatli et al., 2014).

The following section will highlight Bourdieu's ideas on habitus, field and capital as the theoretical framework with the various themes like social media, South Asian diaspora, ethnic entrepreneurship, economic development, and enclaves etc., discussed in the literature review.

2.9 SOCIAL MEDIA, SOUTH ASIAN DIASPORA FAMILY BUSINESS AND BOURDIEU'S THEORY

Bourdieu's habitus, field and capital theory can be applied to evaluate, not only on the individual experiences but also on the social conducts that form and set the boundary of that experience (Bourdieu, 2003). However, although some of Bourdieu's work is based on traditional media and journalism, the trinity (habitus, field and capital) (Asimaki and Koustourakis, 2014) of him on digital media has been unnoticed in the field of South Asian diaspora family business. Moreover, though Bourdieu's work was used more commonly in some articles, predominantly regarding social capital, the detailed application of his habitus, field and capital theories are demeaned in the business literature.

Despite providing a strong theoretical argument of different social worlds, including business analysis, Bourdieusian interpretation stands primarily in the field of sociological literature (Portes, 1998). This absence is remarkable because due to the richness of the business field and the family's power struggles, the inner strength within the actors, whose motivations are often unknown but governed by strict rules. Therefore, this study will focus on the gap in the knowledge by attempting the

inclusive usage of Bourdieusian habitus, field and capital theory to the South Asian diaspora family business literature.

The notion of habitus used by Bourdieu (1984) is the way of understanding how different mechanisms drive the reproducing or transforming of specific behaviours. In this study, the view and application of social media into the family business is constructed and shaped by the social and cultural structures and, specifically, how the habitus of two generations is shaped may impact their preliminary and progressive involvement in digital transformation in the business. Moreover, the habitus of the agents also describes the nature and causes behind their activities.

Family as a field is a key realm in facilitating and constructing the different norms, behaviours, preferences, and interests with the help of the culture (Fitzgerald and Kirk, 2009). Therefore, it is important to unearth how the cultural heritage of the South Asian diaspora family shapes the agents' habitus and preference for social media in their day to day life. The agents' habitus as the way they experienced from their upbringing in the family and the various forms of capital they possessed over time drive them to captivate social media activities. Therefore, applying the Bourdieusian notion of habitus, field and capital in this study is crucial for understanding the relationship between family culture and social media application in terms of agents' social position, space and time (Grenfell, 2008).

Both national and family cultures have a dominant role in legitimizing the geology of business activities. The interrelation between culture and family business are networked and hard to untangle, however difficult to avoid (Spigel, 2013). The Bourdieusian framework would be able to see the business practices in South Asian diaspora families by understanding agents' views on the social rules around them

and, moreover, the values in the forms of different capital they inherited and which they try to acquire (Bourdieu, 2005). Therefore, the Bourdieusian field-based theoretical framework gives a course to explain the connection between the role of culture and family entrepreneurial activities.

Bourdieu's habitus, field and capital theories are essential for this study because the cultural heritage is often shed as a predetermined force within diaspora family business research. Inevitably, studies regarding the impact of culture in the family business often either restrict culture as a sub variable or rely upon some case studies of specific cultural characteristics that cannot establish the relationship between cultural heritage and agents' action (Spigel, 2013). These concerns derive from the lack of a theoretical framework coupling family culture with family business practices. Without applying such a theoretical framework, it is challenging to go in-depth simply narrating the family culture and thoroughly analyze the cultural heritage and its impact on daily and durable practices of the agents (Lahire, 2003).

The purpose of using the Bourdieusian toolkit to ethnic entrepreneurship is to give the analytical framework to critically analyze the impact of cultural heritage on the various issues agents encounter in the family business (Cederberg and Villares-Varela, 2018). Therefore, conceptualizing the impact of culture within this analytical toolkit lowers the drawback of ad-hoc aesthetic analysis and hypothetical description. As a result, culture is no longer considered an intangible force about the agents in the family business but rather creates the environment in which entrepreneurial activities unfold (Salvato and Melin, 2008).

3.0 METHODOLOGY

3.1 INTRODUCTION

Research is a powerful and indispensable tool that leads to progress. The curiosity of man causes him to discover the secrets of nature. For this reason, individuals apply their best effort to reveal those secrets. Eventually, humans found some facts of those mysteries by executing cause and effect techniques. Simply, this is the means of research. The research focused on uncovering novel facts is a vital and enormous way to reach a specific goal. So, the researchers need to adopt a well-judged research design to find out the answer to the research queries. Therefore, a good research design is the combination of the befitting research approach, rational research strategy, appropriate data collection techniques, and the researcher's philosophical position underpinning the study. Yin (2018) described methodology as a process where knowledge is constructed. It comprises the methods and techniques of collecting and analysing the information. Silverman (2011) defined methodology as a holistic approach, from the philosophical stance of the researcher to the data gathering and analysis.

Moreover, Saunders et al. (2012, p.3) marked a clear distinction between methods and methodology as “the term methods refer to techniques and procedures used to obtain and analyse data. This, therefore, includes questionnaires, observation and interviews as well as both quantitative (statistical) and qualitative (non-statistical) analysis techniques while the term methodology refers to the theory of how research should be undertaken.” Unquestionably, research methodology is how to carry out a research study (Maylor, Blackmon and Huemann, 2017); it can be a procedure that

enhances or upgrades knowledge by designing, implementing and examining the outcomes of the particular research questions.

This chapter of the study aims to describe the research map implemented in this paper to explore critically how cultural heritage impacts the utilisation of power and the potential of social media as a business strategy among small food retail businesses in Glasgow. Therefore, for the benefit of the readers, the researcher has divided the chapter into the following sections according to Saunders et al.'s (2012) research onion. First, start with section 3.2, which discusses the nature of this study. Then, section 3.3 provides an insight into the different theoretical paradigms with the justification of adopting a specific philosophical assumption appropriate for this study. Section 3.4 illustrates a different research approach along with the rationalisation that fits into the adopted philosophy. The next section, 3.5, describes various available methodological choices termed 'research design', particularly detailed discussion on qualitative research design because of the nature of the study. Section 3.6 gives deep insight into the case study research with the justifications alongside other strategies that are not appropriate for this study. Section 3.7 describes different types of data collection techniques which is followed by the justification of interviews and observation under a sub-section. Next, section 3.8 describes the sampling strategy, and finally, section 3.9 describes ethical issues related to the study.

3.2 NATURE OF THE STUDY

Understanding the nature of the research is an essential task of a researcher because it helps design the research. The nature of the study is decided by what type of questions are used to answer the objectives of the research (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2012). Therefore, research can be exploratory, explanatory and descriptive according to how the research question is being asked. The section will briefly discuss the type of study appropriate for addressing this research problem in contrast to other types.

The research will be exploratory in nature when, how and what questions are used to find and understand the new phenomenon of the study being researched. This study fits into the exploratory nature because the researcher seeks to understand the family culture and its influencing power on the business by asking how and what questions. Moreover, this study is exploratory because the researcher aims to explain his understanding of family culture on social media adoption in the business, which is broad and not precisely defined. (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2016). But, though the exploratory research starts with focusing broadly, it becomes narrower while the study advances (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2016). The most important criteria of this type of study include adjusting in nature and allowing researchers to become flexible to change during its course (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2012). On the other hand, this study does not fit as an explanatory or descriptive because the researcher is not trying to establish random or casual relationships among the variables (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2012) or dealing with a naturally occurring phenomenon (Hedrick, Bickman and Rog, 1993). Furthermore, it should be noted that the research becomes explanatory if, why and how questions are asked, and on

the other hand, it becomes descriptive if 'what' type of questions are asked (Gray, 2014).

3.3 RESEARCH PHILOSOPHY

Researchers need to consider certain concepts because of their fundamental importance in guiding and influencing the procedure and application of the research. Scholars argued that the successful result of the study was largely influenced by these terms (Bazeley, 2004). Researchers often interchangeably use them as 'paradigm', 'theory', 'philosophy' or 'world view' (Doyle, Brady and Byrne, 2009) and are interconnected with the researcher's belief. Researchers should be aware of the interrelatedness of those terminologies because those can influence the researcher's commitment to the inquiry and the knowledge of cultural ancestry of entrepreneurs, nature of entrepreneurship and application of social media into the enterprises.

Therefore, the research paradigm or philosophy is the outer layer of the research onion of Saunders et al. (2012), which is considered a research culture that encompasses different beliefs, integrities, morals, natures and conduct of the study (Johnson and Onwuegbuzie, 2004). Research philosophy critically examines the foundations of being or the fundamental essences of what exists, knowledge, its forms and how it can be claimed. The research philosophies or world views incorporate a perspective associated with the reality and its nature (ontology), acceptable and legitimate knowledge (epistemology), the meaning of values in the study (axiology), a dialect of the study (rhetoric) and finally the procedures adopted to carry out the investigation (methodology) (Creswell, 2003). Hence, the selected

research paradigm gives direction in the study's theoretical assumptions and helps select appropriate methods for the research (Ponterotto, 2005). Consequently, the researcher needs to master the paradigm of research and the assumptions because the research is always based on the underlying assumption, which assists in constructing lawful study and selecting suitable methods (Myers, 1997; Doyle, Brady and Byrne, 2009; Morgan, 2007). Moreover, Burrell and Morgan (1979) argue that philosophies notify and create researchers about complications of organisational research and understanding the influence of the research paradigm on knowledge development.

Undoubtedly, the nature of the paradigm has evolved over some time. According to Guba and Lincoln (1994), positivism, post-positivism, constructivism and critical theory are the four major underlying theories used in qualitative research. Conversely, Positivism, Interpretivism and Critical theory are the main paradigms based on the epistemology suggested by Orlikowski and Baroudi (1991). In addition, Sarantakos (2005) also classified paradigms into positivism, interpretivism and critical regime. However, Oates (2006) termed those three paradigms as 'broad-brush' assumptions because all other categories are derived from them. For instance, post-positivism is the subgroup of positivism where both paradigms explain a scientific method that ultimately deals with prediction, cause-effect, law-like generalisation of the phenomenon under study, work in nomothetic, and etic perspectives and both stand on the quantitative research (Ponterotto, 2005). On the other hand, phenomenology and hermeneutics are considered the sub-division of interpretivism (Oates, 2006) and Marxism (also termed as a transformative /emancipatory paradigm) and Feminism (also known as a postcolonial indigenous paradigm) are derived from the critical theory (Chilisa and Kawulich, 2012).

Choosing the right research paradigm can be a demanding task for the researchers because paradigms are distinct from each other due to the presence of inconsistencies and would be less challenging to determine for the study “if defined in such a way as to be able to differentiate between and across them on the basis of a fixed set of principles and procedures” (Goulding, 1999, p.862). Moreover, the choice of the research philosophy relies upon what research is trying to seek.

In the interpretivism paradigm, researchers think that, unlike positivism, the explanation of the social world is not understood by involving principles from physical science. Moreover, the business world is considerably complex to formulate a theory by concrete law like the natural sciences (Blumberg, Cooper and Schindler, 2014). Interpretivism philosophy which can also be termed as an ‘anti –positivism’ philosophy derived due to recognised inadequacy in positivism, and as an interpretivist, the researchers see the reality in the highly subjective way rather than an objective like the positivists do (Collis and Hussey, 2014). Under the interpretivism research paradigm, knowledge and theory are developed over ideas initiated from the observation and interpretation of social interaction, so that Van Maanen (1983, p.9) argues that interpretivism philosophy needs a set of procedures that “seek to describe, translate and otherwise come to terms with the meaning, not the frequency of certain more or less naturally occurring phenomena in the social world”. Therefore, in this study, the researcher has positioned himself as an interpretivist to understand the social context of the phenomenon by the way the social actors make it understandable to the world through knowledge and experience sharing and to explore the impact of cultural heritage on strategic decisions of adopting or neglecting social media into the business. Epistemological point of view, researchers under this paradigm believe that knowledge is constructed (not

discovered) subjectively through an interactive process. It means knowledge is not constructed alone and influenced by the researcher and the participant's interpretation. Thus 'truth' is socially negotiable, culturally bound and historically dependent (Cohen & Ravishankar, 2012).

When it comes to the positivism paradigm, the study rejects this paradigm because the researcher is not measuring the reality and breaking the reality into the variables (Wilson, 2010). Moreover, the positivism paradigm discourages subjectivity, as the researcher under this paradigm believes in the existence of a disciplined world outside, and for this reason, positivists make inquiries in value-free or neutral ways to attain objectivity in the study (Sarantakos, 2005). Furthermore, data required for the study is not numeric and quantifiable, and the researcher is not using statistical analysis; therefore, the positivism paradigm is not appropriate for the study (Lincoln and Guba, 1985). Critical paradigm is also not suitable for this study because the researcher's main focus is not on the oppression, conflict, or dominance in society and strives to encounter the status quo to eliminate dominance (Meyers, 1997). Instead, researchers in this paradigm hold the view of emancipation or transformation that encompasses rescuing people or communities from power dominance via group action to shape the society by empowering those (Mertens, 2007).

3.4 RESEARCH APPROACH

The research approach gives the plan and process of research that range from the wide assumptions to comprehensive methods of collection of data and analysis, and it also includes the convergence of research philosophy, design and particular method (Creswell, 2014). There are three types of research approaches are Inductive, Deductive and Abductive (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2012). According to Collis and Hussey (2014), “inductive research describes a study in which theory is developed from the observation of empirical reality; thus general inferences are induced from particular instances”. Data is collected from a small sample size for understanding phenomena, finding out any themes or patterns to create a conceptual framework. From this point of view, the Inductive approach is appropriate for this study. Moreover, as an interpretivist, the researcher aims to draw generalisation from a specific phenomenon; therefore, an inductive approach is important for the study (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2012).

However, the study rejected the deductive approach because it does not deal with a theory that can be falsified or verified or even confirmed through hypothesis testing (Gray, 2014). Compared to the Inductive approach, the deductive approach is tested by factual observation and its direction from general to specific (Collis and Hussey, 2014). The basic logic of the deductive approach is that the conclusion must be true if hypotheses are true (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2012). As the researcher adopts an inductive approach, there is no aim to test the theory through successive data collection (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2012); therefore, the abductive approach is unsuitable for this study.

3.5 RESEARCH DESIGN

Research design gives a detailed plan about the way of getting an answer to the research question. It includes clear research objectives, identifying source of data, way of data collection and analysis of collected data, ethical considerations and limitations in doing research such as available time and management, monetary issues, location etc. (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2012). Quantitative, Qualitative and multiple methods are the three types by which research can be designed.

The qualitative research focuses on understanding how people behave and consider their actions, and for this reason, it represents high contextual dependence. (Gray, 2014). Furthermore, the researchers are often called naturalistic because they work in the natural setting to explore the problem of the study experienced by the participants (Creswell, 2014). Those criteria match this study because the researcher focuses on the participant's meaning of the problem, which is the understanding of cultural heritage on social media usage in the family business, not his understanding of the issue (Creswell, 2014). This deeper understanding can only be achieved in the qualitative research design by building trust and participation (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2012). Therefore, the researcher has chosen the qualitative design to carry out this study.

Moreover, the qualitative research design emphasises inductive approach (Bryman, 2016) because of its emergence (Creswell, 2014) and naturalistic design helps better understanding of the influence of cultural heritage on the view of social media in the business than the existing literature of that issue (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2012). Ontological point of view, as an interpretivist, the researcher is highly

subjective about the issue being researched; therefore, quantitative research is not applicable for this study. Moreover, this study is not associated with numbers where collected data is converted into numerical form (Bryman and Bell, 2011). It does not examine the causal relationship between the variables and measures them numerically (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2012). For this reason, this study also rejects quantitative design. The researcher is also not collecting or analysing numerical and non-numerical data together in this research; therefore, a mixed-method design is not considered (Creswell et al., 2003). Furthermore, the researcher's philosophical underpinning of the study and the approach also rejects the mixed-method design.

3.6 RESEARCH STRATEGY

Research strategy provides scientific links between chosen philosophy and methods of data collection & analysis. (Denzin and Lincoln, 2005). Research strategy is important for the study because it enables researchers to reach an acceptable level of coherence by linking to the research's philosophy, approach, and purpose (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2012).

Different research strategies are principally linked to the specific research design. For example, experiment and survey strategies are exclusively related to quantitative research design. (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2012). On the other hand, ethnography, action research, grounded theory, narrative inquiry, gender and ethnic studies and hermeneutics are linked to qualitative research design. (Saunders, Lewis

and Thornhill, 2012; Collis and Hussey, 2014). Archival research and case study strategy can be adopted either in qualitative or quantitative or mixed research design methods. (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2009).

Experimental research is mainly chosen for the quantitative study where researchers seek the truth (Gray, 2014). Natural scientists use this strategy to find out any relationship exists between the independent and dependent variables. The experiment aims to produce valid and replicable objective results because ontologically and epistemologically, it stands in objectivism and positivism philosophy, respectively (Gray, 2014). In the standard experiment, null and alternative hypotheses are formulated to predict any relationship between the variables (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2009). Researchers test null hypothesis statistically in the experiment research strategy (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2009).

3.6.1 CASE STUDY

The following section gives readers the justification for choosing the case study method for this research, along with the selection and execution of the strategy. The interpretivist stance of the researcher and the nature of the study have driven the adoption of a case study strategy for this research. As this study aims to critically explore the understanding of the phenomenon of cultural heritage on social media embracement in diaspora community-owned businesses, the case study can validate critical thinking by broadening understanding, widening experience, and strengthening beliefs about the stated phenomenon (Stake, 2000). Hence, this

method is absolute when 'how' and 'why' questions are being used to explore a concurrent set of phenomena over which the researcher requires no control (Gray, 2014).

According to Yin (2009, p.13), the case study is "an empirical inquiry that investigates a contemporary phenomenon within its real-life context, especially when the boundaries between phenomenon and the context are not clearly evident". Moreover, in the case study, researchers can focus on achieving a clear understanding of the dynamics within a single framework (Eisenhardt, 1989). Although interpretivism mainly adopts case study methodology, positivists can also use this based on what type of methods they adopted and the scope of the previous theory (Collis and Hussey, 2014). For that reason, the case study approach falls on both qualitative and quantitative methods (Dooley, 2002). The case study approach is especially helpful for the researcher seeking to reveal a correlation between a paradox and the context in which this is happening (Grey, 2014).

In contrast to the survey, a case study can explore a wide range of themes from some more specific participants, whereas the survey does the opposite. Consequently, Tight (2010) mentioned that case study methodology encompasses a thorough investigation of a small sample from a specific perspective. The case can be a person, specific organization, position, experience, procedure, phenomena, and social group where comprehensive data is accumulated about the selected case, sometimes over an extended period (Punch, 2014). In the case study, researchers can collect data jointly from interviews, survey questionnaires, observations-particularly participant observation and archives (Dooley, 2002).

Yin (2003) outlined the admissible situation where different research strategies are more appropriate than others depending on the types of research questions, how much control is required on the behavioural events, and the level of focus on contemporary events against historical events.

Strategy	Types of research questions	Control requirement of behavioural events	Work on contemporary events
Archival research	'Where', 'What', 'Who', 'How many' and 'How much'?	Not required	Yes/No
Case study	'How' and 'Why'?	Not required	Yes
Experimental research	'How' and 'Why'?	Required	Yes
History	'How' and 'Why'?	Not required	No
Survey	'Where', 'What', 'Who', 'How many' and 'How much'?	Not required	Yes

Table 3.1: Related situations for research strategies. (Adapted from Yin, 2003)

The design of a case study can be done in various ways, and Yin (2009) provided the widely accepted classifications based on the two distinct dimensions of its design. Therefore, a case study can be single or multiple and holistic or embedded in nature which can be best displayed in a 2 x 2 matrix (Yin, 2014).

Fig. 3.1: Fundamental types of Case study design (Adapted from Yin, 2014)

Apart from that basic typology of case study, Scholz and Tietje (2002) classified case study research in other dimensions like epistemologically, purpose, motivation, data and so on which has been displayed in a tabular form.

Features	Types
<i>Epistemological</i>	'Explanatory', 'Exploratory' and 'Descriptive'
<i>Motivation</i>	'Instrumental' and 'Intrinsic'
<i>Data</i>	'Qualitative' and 'Quantitative'
<i>Purpose</i>	'Research', 'Training' and 'Action/Application'
<i>Structure</i>	'Highly structured' and 'Unstructured'

Table 3.2: Classification of the case study research (Adapted from Scholz and Tietje, 2002).

On the other hand, Stake (2005) established case study design into intrinsic instrumental and multiple forms to understand a specific case, give insight into a particular issue, and investigate an event.

The distinction between holistic and embedded case study approaches is based on the research methods. The holistic case study is mainly qualitative and depends on narrative descriptions. Embedded case study tests hypotheses through statistical analysis by quantitative data (Campbell and Stanley, 1963). In addition, the embedded form of case study gives scope to adopt a plurality of methods inside the cases (Scholz and Tietje, 2002).

However, Yin's (2014) matrix illustrates that a holistic and embedded case study can also be a single or multiple. The single case study is appropriate when the nature of the study is idiosyncratic, exceptional and on real-life events (Gray, 2014). Concerning multiple cases, Yin (1994, p.45) therefore states that "Every case should serve a specific purpose within the overall scope of inquiry. Here, a major insight is to consider multiple cases as one would consider multiple experiments-that is, to follow a 'replication' logic."

Therefore, as the study follows qualitative methods to explore a unique, real-life critical phenomenon that has not been considered well, the researcher has considered a single case study as a strategy to utilize the scope to reveal and scrutinize the fact (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2009).

Selection of Case

Non-probability purposive sampling technique was used to select 12 diaspora owned retail shops for this study. A retail shop was selected through snowball sampling mainly on account of providing the best knowledge of the field of the study and contributing to meet the research objectives, which was illustrated in the sampling section in this paper.

The case selection of this study was also powered by the Scottish Index Multiple Deprivation (SIMD - [click for the interactive Scottish Government Map](#)) to locate the business. According to the index, small food retail businesses, particularly run by the Asian diaspora community, will be selected from the different geographic areas of Glasgow. Firstly, an equal number of shops were selected from each direction within a 30-mile radius of Glasgow. Secondly, an equal number of shops were selected in each direction, representing the less and more deprived areas. This will help to identify the number of technology-oriented consumers in the specific locality. Cultural heritage is not only the reason behind the businesses implementing social media platforms for their operation or not; it is also the demand or negligence of the consumers of the particular geographic area. The aim of this case selection phase of the research study was to select information-rich cases rather than the number of cases to explore and illuminate the study's objectives.

Execution of case

The small retail industry in Glasgow, Scotland, owned by the Asian diaspora community, was considered a single case as a whole for this study. The case study strategy was carried out under the qualitative method, and primary data were collected through unstructured interviews from the shop owner and observations.

The interview and observation protocols will be discussed in detail in the data collection section of this study.

Validity and Reliability issues of the case study

Achievement of the degree of validity and reliability drive the rigour in the research process. Therefore, the intensity in validity and reliability guarantees collecting data and, above all, confidence in successfully applying and applying the research outcomes into the application (Riege, 2003). Since the case study strategy is selected under the interpretivism paradigm for understanding real-life contemporary events in-depth, the scholars pointed out credibility, transferability, dependability and confirmability to appraise the standard of the case study (Lincoln and Guba, 1985; Denzin and Lincoln, 1994). Besides, Yin (1994) mentioned construct validity, internal validity, external validity and reliability tests analogous to the tests used in interpretivism, are used to check the quality of the case study carried out under positivism philosophy.

The notion of confirmability is parallel to the concept of construct validity (Yilmaz, 2013). Gray (2014, p.279) describes, "Construct validity refers to the quality of the conceptualizations or operationalization of the relevant concepts, that is, the extent to which the study investigates what it claims to investigate". Firstly, confirmability checks that the interpreted data should be presented rationally and unbiased and secondly, it evaluates the degree to which the data produces the most logical conclusion (Miles and Huberman, 1994). For this study, researchers use confirmability tests during the data collecting and analysis phase by examining the unprocessed data, inference, outcomes and recommendations (Lincoln and Guba, 1985).

The next tool for building validity for the qualitative case study is credibility, which resembles internal validity for the quantitative one. This assessment aims to describe that the study was executed in such a means that verifies credibility, which incorporates the validation of research outcomes by the interviewees (Riege, 2003). Researchers use various techniques to ensure the credibility of the case study strategy used in qualitative research. For example, the triangulation method is often used to increase credibility during the data collection and analysis stage where more than one source is evident (Yin, 2009). Besides, credibility can also be fostered by the 'peer debriefing technique' where analysis and inference are presented to the co-researcher regularly in the analytical data phase (Hirschman, 1986).

The credibility of this case study is ensured by considering the researcher's theoretical understanding at the research design phase and the self-monitoring process (Merriam, 1988). Furthermore, apart from the tools as mentioned above, researchers have considered the respondents' opinions by cross-checking the findings in writing up the stage to ensure credibility (Lincoln and Guba, 1985).

Transferability or generalization is gained when the study provides similar or distinct outcomes of an event amongst similar or distinct respondents (Polit and Beck, 2010). According to Korstjens and Moser (2017, p.121), transferability is "the degree to which the results of qualitative research can be transferred to other contexts or settings with other respondents". The researcher has developed a database while collecting data for this study to add 'thick description', ensuring transferability (Høyland, Hagen and Engelbach, 2017). Moreover, Transferability can also be achieved using cross-case during the data analysis (Stavros and Westberg, 2009). In addition, Yin (1994) described that the use of specific coding techniques and

analysis like applying symbols or signs in the analysis stage assists to establish transferability in the case study in qualitative research.

Finally, dependability, similar to the reliability in quantitative research, needs to be ensured in the case study research (Leung, 2015). The notion of the dependability test is based on the indications of firmness and regularity in the inquiry process. Dependability includes “participants evaluating the findings and the interpretation and recommendations of the study to make sure that they are all supported by the data received from the informants of the study” (Anney, 2014, p.278). This can be achieved in various ways like ‘audit trail’, ‘stepwise replication’, ‘code-recode strategy’ and ‘peer examination’ during the research design phase (Krefting, 1991; Schwandt, Lincoln and Guba, 2007). For the audit trail, researchers are required to preserve the raw data collected through interviews, observation papers, and field notes to examine the procedures carried out incomprehensible and unbiased to confirm dependability in the research (Bowen, 2009). Besides, it can also be ensured by protecting against the researcher’s philosophical views and prejudices (Hirschman, 1986).

So, bearing the theoretical assumption in mind, the researcher has designed the study to ensure confirmability, credibility, transferability, and dependability to validate the case study. After outlining the type of research well fitted for this study, selection procedures, brief execution protocol and measures to control the quality of the case study, the following section gives in detail discussion on the types of data and its collection procedures to execute the case study strategy.

3.7 TYPES OF DATA AND COLLECTION METHODS

Data collection methods play a significant role in the result of any research. (Scheyvens and Donovan, 2003). Research becomes invalid if the data collection method is not accurate, affecting the researcher's credibility. (Bell, 2005). On the other hand, correct data collection methods help to produce successful outcomes. (Cooper and Schindler, 2003). Selection of the nature of the data for the study depends on the researcher's theoretical underpinning of the study and the research design. Interpretivism stance of the researcher and the qualitative research design for the Therefore, this section discusses the types of data appropriate for this study and its collection procedures in detail. And First of all, the section provides a brief description of the different types of data available, secondly the rationale of choosing an unstructured interview and its procedure, followed by the rationale of selecting observation and its procedure.

Most of the scholars classified data into two types. They are Primary data and secondary data. (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2012; Gray, 2014; Bryman, 2012; Collis and Hussey, 2014). For example, data generated from indigenous sources by the investigator is called primary data, and the data that already exists and is collected by some other investigators is previously called secondary data. (Collis and Hussey, 2014). There are numerous varieties of primary and secondary data available for carrying out research work. The most commonly used primary data are experiments outcomes, surveys responses, interviews and observation notes (Salkind, 2010).

On the other hand, the sources or types of secondary data are getting more diversified day by day. Therefore, secondary data can be available both in the text and non-text form, in the form of censuses carried out by the government, ongoing and regular surveys by the government and private organisations, print and

electronic media archives and academic research databases (Cowton, 1998; Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2016). Though both primary and secondary data have benefits and pitfalls over one another, the selection of the types and sources of data depends on how deliberately research questions can be answered. The advantages and disadvantages of both types of data are outlined as follows:

	Advantages	Drawbacks
Primary data	Reliable, credible and accurate	Collection and analysis could be expensive
	Can lesson any research problem	Expert skill requirement
	Can address specific research question	Time consuming
Secondary data	Cost effective	Not reliable, credible and accurate
	Quick collection	Data may be out of date
	No expert skills required to collect the data	Sources sometimes unknown
		Absent of usable presentation format
		Interpretation skills required

Table 3.3: Merits and demerits of primary and secondary data (Adapted from Morgan and Summers, 2005)

As an interpretivist, researcher has decided to collect primary data in the form of unstructured interviews which can only be understood within its context (Qu and Dumay, 2011).

3.7.1 INTERVIEW

The unstructured interview has been selected for collecting data for this study because of its explorative nature, where the researcher's main aim is to understand the feelings or perceptions of the participants on a specific phenomenon (Rowley, 2012). As a result, researchers can grasp the 'personal construct' of the interviewees based on their assumptions and thoughts (Easterby-Smith, Thorpe and Jackson, 2012). Furthermore, one of the most important criteria of this type of interview is to probe further when required. For that reason, rich and personalized data can be obtained by this technique (Grey, 2014).

The traditional face-to-face interviews will be carried out among twelve small retail shops around Glasgow. The study's sample size is determined until the data has been hit to the theoretical saturation throughout the interview process (Bryman, 2012). The participants of this study are mainly the shop owner who has only the authoritative power to decide on social media application to their businesses. Analysis of individual-level concerning a cultural phenomenon that impacts the business is compatible with the realities that are fabricated socially. It is important to stress that these interviews will be conducted over months and work across those within the family business. Given the nature of the diaspora family business and the dynamics of conducting business, it is essential to reduce the impact on the business practices and interact at their convenience. Consent was sought before the interview for recording and transcribing the conversation, and notes were taken about the

nuance, posture, gestures and interludes during the process, which allowed the researcher to capture a more vigorous and inclusive interpretation (Collis and Hussey, 2014).

3.7.2 ETHNOGRAPHIC OBSERVATION

Apart from unstructured interviews, the researcher will also collect data through participant observation. According to Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill (2012, p.342), participant observation can be described as “the researcher attempts to participate fully in the lives and activities of members and thus becomes a member of their group, organisations or community. This enables the researcher to share their experiences by not merely observing what is happening but also feeling it”.

The researcher has been working in this diaspora family business for a long time. Therefore, his role has become ethnographer while carrying out the research. This ethnography is important for the qualitative nature of the study, which helps to identify ethnic phenomena of an ethnic group inside their environment (Gray, 2014). The first ethnographer then becomes the participant as the observer helps the researcher map the area where the shops are located, business practices and presence online, and depth of digital engagement. Moreover, it will help the researcher recognise the nature of people working inside the shop, their status, family behaviour, and shop layout.

This ethnographic observation will occur while taking the interview and while the researcher is working as a part of his daily job. The researcher will take note during his observation that later will be used as data. Moreover, ethnography allows the

researcher to become a part of the field and his interactions among the other people within the field can be used as valuable data (Gray, 2014).

3.8 SAMPLING STRATEGY

Sample selection for a research study is considered an essential part of designing research because a researcher cannot study the whole population (Marshall, 1996; Creswell, 2007). Therefore, the overall research standard depends on the appropriate selection of the sampling procedure (Coyne, 1997), which is requisite to produce impartial and vigorous results (Wilmont, 2005). Despite having significance, establishing a sampling design to determine a subgroup to represent the whole research population is still a difficult topic in both qualitative and quantitative methods of research (Onwuegbuzie and Collins, 2007). It is a more difficult task for researchers when mixed methods are used because integrated methods have divergent study designs which demand the exploitation of distinct sets of sampling strategies (Teddlie and Yu, 2007). Thus, researchers should give vigilant attention to establish a rational sampling strategy so that the chosen sample in each research approach is consistent with the overall design of the research (Collins, Onwuegbuzie and Jiao, 2007).

As this is a purely qualitative study, it is therefore always vital to ensure that the selected participants' information matches with each other in the sample group and is also analogous to other individuals who were not chosen for the study (Onwuegbuzie and Leech, 2007). Undoubtedly, the key proposition for qualitative study is to discover new ideas rather than a numerical generation (Manning, 1992).

Moreover, since qualitative methods acknowledge the subjective understanding more predominantly than generalization, it intends to give a deep knowledge about a complex matter by answering 'how' and 'why' questions (Marshall, 1996). Therefore, this qualitative study demands a flexible and constant data collection and analysis and a realistic technique of sampling.

The researcher has adopted non-probability purposive sampling for this study. This sampling design is suitable because it gives rich information that cannot be obtained from other sampling settings (Gray, 2014). Furthermore, this type of sampling design allows researchers to exercise their judgment regarding selecting participants who can give the required information. Conversely, that is one of the main drawbacks of purposive sampling, where the researchers got a high chance of being biased (Gray, 2014). However, the researcher of this study has selected this design because of the qualitative nature of the study, and the sample needs to be selected deliberately based on rich information.

As the study focused on sensitive issues like family culture and how it influenced daily activities, snowball sampling was appropriate for the study. The researcher has identified one knowledge of insiders who act as the research participants' locator (Biernacki and Waldorf, 1981). Moreover, SIMD (click for the interactive Scottish Government map) was used to select the 12 family businesses cases in different parts of Glasgow, and with the help of that participant locator, the researcher reached the participants. In this way, Snowball sampling gave active control to the researcher (Biernacki and Waldorf, 1981).

3.9 ETHICAL ISSUES

This section of the methodology chapter highlights the ethical issues that the researcher experienced and had come across throughout the research study. The researcher set up a standard regarding behaviours and norms that direct him to conduct the study. Before conducting the study, the researcher has approved the project from the University of the West of Scotland's business school ethics committee in 2018, which is attached in Appendix A. The researcher followed the ethics committee guidelines (2009) of the University of the West of Scotland based on the four major principles: Non-maleficence and beneficence, Autonomy, Justice and Inclusiveness and finally, Confidentiality and Anonymity.

The participant information sheet was provided to each participant before the interview stating clearly the purpose of the study, the role of the participants for this study, storage and usage of data. (See Appendix B). Moreover, a signed consent form (see Appendix C) was taken from each participant before the interview, informing them that they have understood the information provided related to the study and have full right to withdraw from the research at any point of time without giving any explanation. Potential participants were assured that their involvement was significant and would not cause any harm while carrying out the study (Benbasat, Goldstein and Mead, 1987). Participants were also ensured that confidentiality and seclusion will be maintained about the information they gave throughout the research and will not be disclosed to any third party for commercial purposes (Myers and Newman, 2007). The researcher also informed that audio recording of interviews and their transcripts will only be used in academia and kept and protected according to the UK Data Protection Act (1998). (Gray, 2014) and the data and information will be kept in a locked personal computer, and only the researcher of this study will have access to it. It had also been informed that data

would no longer be kept after the successful completion of the study and destroyed lawfully after that (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2012). Furthermore, it was explicitly made clear that code will be used to ensure the anonymity of the participants.

4.0 DATA FINDINGS AND ANALYSIS

This chapter deals with the data findings and analysis of the study. It is accepted that findings are often presented then followed by analytical discussion. However, given the aim of the study, its methodological approach that ethnographically mines qualitatively rich data and the Bourdusian analysis findings and analysis are incrementally coupled. The rationale being this ensures the flow of sub-sectional themes with critical interrogation that build to a summarise critical discussion. Additionally, this will enable the construction of thematic knowledge to produce an overarching synthesis and critical conclusion. Therefore, within the study, the core coverage of themes are Cultural Diaspora: Framing the habitus; Discourses of Disruption; Technophobia and Influencer Network; Ethnic enclaves: Cultural cryostasis and capitals of containment; Privilege and poverty: Digital adoption and finally Diaspora, Entrepreneurship and Digital Discourse: Paradox of patriarchy and prosperity. Within each theme, key data sections will be highlighted and framed with discussion, each critically concluded and analysed through a Bourdieusian lens. The study now turns to consider the first major theme.

4.1 CULTURAL DIASPORA: FRAMING THE HABITUS

The notion of cultural singularity has played a significant role in reshaping the world profoundly after post colonialism (Hall, 1999). However, it is still a very strong and innovative effort used amongst the formerly marginalised communities to represent their culture in the new country of residence. Therefore, holding and practising inherited norms and values in the host countries transforms the dispersed population of a particular country into a diaspora community that allows them to share memories and longings. As a result, interconnectedness in the diaspora community facilitates overcoming oppression in the form of a master class of identity in the host society. Moreover, the cultural diaspora helps to counter the assimilation into the

new culture and bypass social amnesia regarding traditions and histories and to do so, the members of the diaspora community, who are termed as a 'habitus' by the French sociologist Pierre Bourdieu, attempt to brace, restore, and develop their eloquent, semantic, religious, cultural, financial, and political habits and exhibitions (Hua, 2005).

In any given context, habitus is a key component of any community and plays a significant role. Habitus can be described as "the learned set of preferences or dispositions by which a person orients to the social world" (Edgerton and Roberts, 2014, p.195). According to Bourdieu (2002, p.27), habitus is the system of substantial, compatible, cognitive "schemata or structures of perception, conception and action". Therefore, habitus is embedded in a family, nurtured and mastered by an individual's status in society. Consequently, Swartz (1997, p.108) argued that "dispositions of habitus represent master patterns of behavioural style that cut across cognitive, normative, and corporal dimensions of human action. They find expression in human language, nonverbal communication, tastes, values, perceptions, and modes of reasoning". In addition, the boundaries of an individual's understanding of power and possibility are shaped by the habitus, which can be "both a structured structure and a structuring structure" (Edgerton and Roberts, 2014, p.198).

Certainly, the sentiment expressed in the quotation embodies the view that the individual's perception and behaviour are influenced by the context of one's social roots and related life expectations and conversely, doing practices of that dispositions in everyday life can alter the individual's social context. Hence, this study needs to frame the habitus of the South Asian diaspora community, particularly the sub-continent Muslim community, to understand their norms and conducts through which culture and tradition are reflected in the host community.

The culture of the South Asian diaspora community in Glasgow is community-centric. The community structure is mainly 'Tight-knit', where the unchallenged tradition influences individuals. However, giving importance to tradition over everything in day to day life has an enormous impact on individual members of the community. This is indicated below:

Interview data

“We live in such a type of community where tradition comes first. Apart from the school education, parents in our community teach their children about the culture and traditions by practicing individually and collectively in their own community.”

“This business is considered as a ‘pride’ of our family. My father took over the responsibilities from my grandfather who started this business 60 years ago in Glasgow. Now it's my turn to carry forward the business.”

“We put religion on top of everything in our day to day life. You can say that our community is traditionally religious. We are muslims, we prefer business rather than other professions. I have seen sikh, hindus, punjabis in the community ...they are also religious.”

“My father used to have a family business in Multan, Pakistan ...actually that was our family tradition. My father tried different new things to start over here but ended up doing the same business as he used to do. For him tradition is everything.”

Interestingly, this closed relationship of culture and community shows that every family is influenced by each other at different levels. This is one of the key traits that

make the diaspora community unique from the host community. Moreover, the context and the boundaries in which the convincing happened is wide and not determined in space and time. Therefore, in a nutshell, it can be seen from a very personal to a wider professional level. The data shows:

Interview data

“My father was largely influenced by his friend who came here before us. He used to guide us and looked after issues and struggles caused by the host community. To be honest, my father was motivated and followed his footsteps.”

“Not only our major business decisions but also family issues are discussed with the senior members in the community. It is quite fruitful while having opinions and suggestions from experienced one. We live in society but act as a family.”

“My father follows our community leader blindly. He (community leader) has a good influence in the community. Anything new we want to introduce in the shop is discussed with him and mostly accepts his decision.”

It is also evident that the structure of the family of the diaspora community is built on gendered discrimination. Generally, males have the supreme power in the family that positions them in a dictatorship, therefore female and children roles are confined by the male and not allowed to take part in the decisive role. This characteristic of the family is considered a family tradition and has been followed by generation after generation. So, family members have grown up and habituated in this discriminated

environment and are dominated by their male counterparts. The following data reflect that:

Interview data

“Though this is our family business, my father is all in all in every matter of the family. My mother graduated in business from Pakistan but my father never asked or discussed business or other family issues with her.”

“In my family, women are not allowed to do jobs or business. I have grown up with the perception that females are meant to look after the matters inside the family and educate their children and males are for the business and outside matters.”

“Women in our family always do what they have been asked to do. They seek permission before they do anything from either their father or husband. Mom wanted to work in our business in her spare time but my father refused and discouraged her for the sake of family tradition.”

Moreover, most families in the diaspora community are structured as a ‘nuclear family’, opposite the host country family structure. The notion of this family structure is based on some features that provide unity through shared responsibilities and commitments with a dialogue of interconnection (Qureshi, 2006). Therefore, the joint family structure of this ethnic community acts as a resource against the uncertainties in the host country and the firm bondage among the family members gives strength to individuals to overcome the challenges in the form of social and economic support (Sanders and Nee, 1987). So, each family member grows up in this embedded

kinship network and mobilises its merits when required for the benefits of extended family members. Entrepreneurial aspirations and set-up are not excluded; the data reveals that:

Interview data

“Though the business goes well, it was not easy to start around twenty years ago. I was so depressed at that time because of language and skills, I was rejected by the employers. At that time, my family and relatives were beside me and gave support to get rid of my frustration.”

“I could not have reached this position if my family and relatives were not there. My first business was in partnership. One of my relatives actually offered to join him. At that time, I was new to this country and struggling to get a good job.”

“We always help each other who are in this type of business. When I face any sort of trouble in the business, I ask my cousin brother who has been in this sector for over 30 years for the solution. Usually, we talk to each other about our problems before seeking professional help.”

“Last couple of days some youngsters have been creating trouble in the shop. Because they are children and I do not know how to control the situation. I discussed the matter with my friend who encountered a similar situation before and took his advice.”

The above data resonates with Bourdieu's intangible construct of 'habitus', and the cultural dispositions are central to this diaspora community. Following Bourdieu, this cultural diaspora, while leaving the land, culture and community of birth, embody a

habitus that they enact in everyday life of a new county (Joy, Game and Toshniwal, 2018). They embody a structuring schema which, being inscribed and internalised via the habitus of the past, are translocated, and trans-generationally enacted and advocated in the new host community. This study demonstrates the Islamic faith placing a central and fundamental structuring relation here. While differential levels of Islamic faith, traditional, moderate to fundamentalist, were evident, the importance of faith, its recognition and role within the community and its supporting relation to entrepreneurialism was central.

This is best understood from the inter dynamic nexus of habitus working from family, retail to the community, which reinforces personal and community identity. Being the most valued and respected, culture and traditions are repetitively articulated and nurtured across the host community and family and acts as a nexus of power and influence. For Bourdieu, the cultural diaspora community is developed because almost every member lives in the same extrinsic atmosphere to easily practice their norms and values. Consequently, community-based living creates home-like feelings so that parents can easily teach their children the traits and dispositions and pass the family culture to the next generation. This clarifies that forming habitus depends on the individual's action based on the logical affinity of the social structure they live in. Hence, Bourdieu argued that habitus is constituted by the individuals and constantly reshape and transform under specific structural conditions (Bourdieu, 1990b).

From the data, it can be seen that the dispositions which people encounter through socialisation are embedded as a primary habitus in the individual. According to Bourdieu, habitus gained in the family field has a long-lasting impact on the individual character (Asimakiand Koustouraki, 2014). For that reason, a significant

number of people who migrated to this country could not assimilate the host country traditions properly. Therefore, it is evident that the Pakistani diaspora community engaged in entrepreneurial activities in Glasgow as a tradition that gives them social recognition. It is due to the social structure they have created in the community where they cultivate the habitus as a course of life. As a result, Bourdieu says that habitus not only develops in subjective processes but is also influenced by the objective structure of the society where they live, and that construction happens concurrently (Blommaert, 2005). However, the different social structure of the host country also generates the distinct mode of habitus, which does not allow the implanted habitus to remain static or undeveloped. Therefore, habitus comprises dispositions that continuously reshape according to the change of social structure and the experiences acquired from that at the same time.

Theme	Sub-theme	Illustrative data sample	Frequency	Illustrative literature
Cultural diaspora : framing the habitus	Community centric	<i>“Not only our major business decisions but also family issues are discussed with the senior members in the community. It is quite fruitful while having opinions and suggestions from experienced one. We live in society but act as a family.”</i>	10	Entrepreneurs in the diaspora community exploit their connections and take opinions and suggestions from them to develop the business. (Chen and Tan, 2009; Wang and lieu, 2015)
	Influencing power	<i>“My father was largely influenced by his friend who came here before us. He used to guide us and looked after issues and struggles caused by the host community. To be honest, my father was motivated and followed his footsteps.”</i>	9	It is always said that entrepreneurial etiquette is firmly rooted in a particular socio-economic context where some people confront or uncover scopes through discourse with others (Kirzner, 1997).

	Gendered discrimination	<i>"In my family, women are not allowed to do jobs or business. I have grown up with the perception that females are meant to look after the matters inside the family and educate their children and males are for the business and outside matters."</i>	8	Women face restraint in the family business in the form of lack of aspiration, limited power, rejection of the opinion and other different pressures from the male counterparts in the family (Mahmood, 2012).
	Nuclear family structure	<i>"I could not have reached this position if my family and relatives were not there. My first business was in partnership. One of my relatives actually offered to join him. At that time, I was new to this country and struggling to get a good job."</i>	10	Another important advantage of having a nuclear family is that members of the family get a wide range of support (Psychological, social, financial) when it is required (Bansal et.al., 2014)

Table 4.1: Cultural diaspora: framing the habitus (key data, frequency and relevant literature)

The tendency to help each other in the community at every level indicates that the habitus is also negotiable. This gives the notion that the traits acquired by the predecessor through socialization can actively influence new members of the community. Thereupon, the South Asian diaspora community, especially the Pakistani Muslim circle, has created dominance in the retail food industry because they would be able to transfer the entrepreneurial character to the other members of the community well. Bourdieu argued this is due to dispositions once gained by the individual, implemented in a consistent way into the different practices (Bourdieu, 1991). For that reason, alteration of the field does not stop the habitus to express their implanted dispositions. From the Bourdieusian theory, it can be said that the habitus of the diaspora community is nothing but a pre-reflexive retaliation to the individual's environment (Costa, Burke and Murphy, 2018).

Another significant disposition developed in the members of the diaspora society from its family structure. The joint family structure helps to disperse the different capital among the extended family members in the community. Therefore, the interchanging of capitals in the given field also plays a role in framing a habitus. It depends on the interrelation between the disposition and its milieu. Bourdieu argued that habitus results from "the conditionings associated with a particular class of conditions of existence" (Bourdieu, 1980, p.88). From the data, it is rational that the nuclear family can reduce the distance and polarity between the older and younger generations. Especially female counterparts in the family and often established people in the community act as mediators of this type of condition. Therefore, the nuclear family structure facilitates the minimization of the dichotomy in the family and sometimes provides 'nuclear reinforcement' in the family. This reflects Bourdieu's field theory, where he consciously emphasizes avoiding dualism and aims to link the agency and the social structure. According to Bourdieu's concept, this nuclear family structure explains how habitus integrates "the system of relationships that structure society" and "how agents participate in the social construction of these very structures" (Laberge and Kay, 2002, p.243). Furthermore, habitus formed and practised in the host community results from "the experience of social agents and of the objective structures that make this experience possible" (Bourdieu, 1988b, p.782).

4.2 DISCOURSES OF DISRUPTION

Disruptions happen at various levels in the diaspora community-owned small businesses. However, the study revealed an intergenerational cultural clash in using new technologies like social media in such businesses. This is typified among boomers, generation X and generation Y or millennials (Benckendorff, Moscardo and Pendergast, 2010), predominantly active in the workplace. Interestingly the dissimilarity in opinions often emerged around social media, its place or acceptance in the business operation. Data highlights such tensions:

Interview data

“It is also about the use of powers. Who is giving commands and who is listening especially when you are the youngest among the three brothers. They want to do things their own way. They do not want to listen.”

“My business partner registered the business with an online directory. He thought it would bring more customers. According to me, this is a wrong decision because people hardly see online directory nowadays for shopping.”

“The new way of marketing of the shop is now available. Last couple of years, many business representatives came to visit me. They offered to take the business online. But I do not think so, it will give something new to the business. Without it, we are still doing good.”

“I always discuss everything with my father who is the legal owner of this shop. I know the importance of social media in terms of business marketing but my father does not want to accept this. I tried to convince him but according to him going to social media is a waste of time and money.”

“My father always makes decisions about the business. Around us, there are several small businesses who are using various types of social media for

their marketing but we are not, because of him. He does not want to see out of the box. He follows certain ethics that we are unable to break.”

Additionally, the generational divide in techno-adoption was hierarchical. The older the generational layers within families and communities, the greater the resistance to technological adoption. It is due to the father and grandfather reflecting a limited knowledge compared to the son and daughter. Therefore, the younger generation faces negative opinions about social media. This is highlighted below:

Interview data

“Yes, my son always pushes me, you should actually go to social media but I do not want to because if I am going to social media, then I will lose the plot because as I said I need to focus at the same time on different aspects not on one aspect. This business is one aspect.”

“My father and elder brother do not know anything about new technology that might help our business to compete with others. That is why they do not encourage you to implement new ideas. They do not know anything but you need to listen to your elders as well. Maybe they know better than you.”

“I started this business around 25 years ago. That time, there was no such type of available technology like mobile, internet, Facebook and all. I am not used to these things. On top of that, they are changing so fast that it is impossible for me to familiarize myself with it.”

“I have seen many success stories on Television who are using social media to get quick responses from their clients. My son always tells me to learn those things and use them for this business. But you know, at this age who will learn this stuff? I can not control it . So better to put it aside.”

“ My father is the only person in the family who is away from this technology usage. So, he does not have any clue how it works. He literally disagreed with using social media for business. It was me who pushed him to do the things. We have started getting the responses but still he is unhappy with it.”

Observation

Two different generations with a knowledge gap creates disagreement in the workplace. It was evident when a comment came out from the son during the interview, ‘Its pointless talking dad as he just dismisses this as kid stuffs’ and the father replied ‘I have no chance of getting them on board with digital’.

Interestingly, these clashes followed a typical pattern. This saw the younger generation presenting an evidential claim, which was often refuted by ridicule or dismissed based on experience and seniority. This is evidenced below:

Interview data

“In small business, everyone goes for the money. They cannot spend too much money for the technology or new system in the business. It happened to me once when I wanted to put some new technology inside the cash and carry but my father says no. It’s too much money. We cannot afford it.”

“If I try to implement new things for the business or the new way of doing the thing, the head of the business opposes and says no to my idea. You need to listen to your elders as well.”

“I always discuss something with my family about business and they share their opinion as well. My daughter always comes with new ideas and all but I can not take them on board because she is young and does not have any experiences at all.”

“My brother installed a software through which we can trace every transaction of the till from our own laptop or computers. However, my father was unhappy and argued that it is unnecessary because most of the time we are on the till. According to him, it will not make any difference to the business.”

Again, this intergenerational divide created tension within the family groups, even siblings, partners or extended families, based on respect and tradition. Here, while techno-cultural impacts were a daily given for the younger generations, they clashed when arguing for the adoption of digital technologies/solutions. As highlighted here, points were often negatively deflected not with rational argument but with appeals to notions of disrespect to elders and not acknowledging one's place in the social hierarchy. This accentuates the justification of parents/grandparents to maintain traditional marketing techniques, business practices and roles. The fact of war or words or approaches positioned digital and social media as divisive and so negative. Interview data and Ethnographic observations supported such dynamic discussions:

Interview data

“Though we are working together in this shop, the major decision comes from my father. My brother adopted a new software in the business without taking the permission from father, he thought we were ignoring him. It is true we respect our seniors and have a tradition to take an opinion before any act.”

“Look, this is how we do things. You should not push your views and show more respect. It's not right to behave in this way and you should know better to do this.”

Observation

On many occasions there were fractious clashes between siblings. Interestingly, the fact of interviewer questioning often prompted or was a catalyst for such conflict. Although the interviewer would back off (not wishing to accentuate tensions, siblings would be pulled to the side and continue arguing points. Without exception, this would end, with the elder/more senior sibling returning to the interview, making apologies for the scene and offering guarded responses.

From the data, it can be said that the following Bourdieu, old generation come from a habitus that is alien or does not understand techno-culture. In essence, older generations lack technological capital due to either their unwillingness to embrace or it is difficult for them to understand modern technology. Because all those generations had different technological environments when they grew up. Therefore, generation X and generation Y are comparatively more prone to apply social media than boomers generation (Dabija, Bejan and Tipi, 2018). On the other side, the same but comparatively fewer consequences happen between generation X and

generation Y. Conversely; generation Y has more influencing power on generation X than compared to generation X on boomers generation (Jorgensen, 2003).

In family businesses, disruptions usually happen when two different mind sets work in the same environment. This was more than the tension between generations but around the distinct and differential capitals possessed by the actors within this hierarchical field. As evidenced within the above within Muslim diasporic family businesses, conflict and disruption were a cultural hangover. Resistance was inherent within the first generation who, in moving from their native country, also embodied traditional capitals of 'how to do business. As founders of the business, and have had success, and with the traditions of Muslim culture, this made acceptance of any new 'digital capital' extremely difficult. Essentially the diaspora finds themselves in a state of unwillingness to accept change. Their authority and trans-generational capitals, inherited over time and through their Asian cultural habitus, find themselves at odds with an Asian/Scot generation whose habitus is home-grown but steeped in a digital mind-set.

Moreover, despite having the technological capital, the children struggle to overcome the resistance to digital technologies. This techno capital is a form of cultural capital which describes the knowledge and skills about different forms of technology (Bourdieu, 1985). The skills of using social media are also considered techno capital, and this can also be called institutional capital as people acquire knowledge from institutions (Lee and Chen, 2017). Again the rejection or resistance to assimilating advice and techno-capitals is all the more pronounced concerning female members, from the data, and for future study, there gendered politics around the capital. Regardless, there is a clash of capitals between the authority, respect and traditions of a romanticised diaspora and a new digital generation. Here clash of capital

equates to a conflict over values around cultural and religious heritage, family and community structure and a shifting economic model driven by the digital revolution and, increasingly, cloud commerce.

Theme	Sub-theme	Illustrative data sample	Frequency	Illustrative literature
Discourses of disruption	Disruption and its various level	<i>"My father always makes decisions about the business. Around us, there are several small businesses who are using various types of social media for their marketing but we are not, because of him. He does not want to see out of the box. He follows certain ethics that we are unable to break."</i>	7	"The businesses fail because, more often than not, these people never make the decisions needed to ensure the vitality of their compa-nies in an ever-changing, even more complex world" (Ward, 1997, p.323).
	Hierarchical generational divide	<i>"Father and elder brother do not know anything about new technology that might help our business to compete with others. That is why they do not encourage you to implement new ideas. They do not know anything but you need to listen to your elders as well. Maybe they know better than you."</i>	8	"patriarchy acts through hierarchical control structures, whereby age and gender significantly influence the freedom to make entrepreneurial choices and access household labour and resources" (Xheneti, Karki and Madden, 2018 ,p.262)
	Pattern of clash	<i>"If I try to implement new things for the business or the new way of doing the thing, the head of the business opposes and says no to my idea. You need to listen to your elders as well."</i>	7	Senior members in the family start the battle and always bring the tradition and culture to win over the conflicts (Tee, 1996).
	Intergenerati onal divide on the basis of culture and tradition	<i>"My brother adopted a new software in the business without taking the permission from father, he thought we were ignoring him. It is</i>	9	"South Asian families are traditionally patriarchal with communication and authority flowing from top to bottom. Within

		<i>true we respect our seniors and have a tradition to take an opinion before any act."</i>		the family, roles are highly defined and based on age and gender." (Ahmed and Lemkau, 2000, p. 90)
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Table 4.2: Discourse of disruption (key data, frequency and relevant literature)

Again, it is noticeable that sometimes the actors cannot isolate themselves in their family and business positions. For that reason, they follow the rules of the family in the field of business. However, this is not always true. The disruption arises when the junior member of the family bypasses the family values or can view two distinct fields and try to implement his or her capital. Bourdieu and Wacquant (1992, p.98) labelled this as "prizes and profits" because of the ongoing competition among the actors of the field through which they try to take control over the field in the form of domination.

Bourdieu sees the conflict in the field that leads to disruption as the basic dynamic of social life (McNay, 1999). The data also reflects the Bourdieusian claim that the power struggles in the field are powered by symbolic capital and tangible resources. According to the Bourdieusian notion, in the family business, the first generation or the founder of the business follows the "dominant principle of hierarchy" (Swartz, 2009, p.192) more than the "second principle of hierarchy" (Swartz, 2009, p.192). In the dominant principle of hierarchy, the father figure holds more economic capital than the other family members. Therefore, in the business, other family members must take permission to implement anything new into it.

On the other hand, the data reflects Bourdieu's basic argument about cultural capitals like educational qualifications mainly held by the second generation in the

family business and considered capital and act as a well-defined cause of differentiation (Bourdieu, 1985). Thus, ironically, while an issue of respect, pride and prestige among the Muslim community, the attainment of education and institutional capital is central to triggering disruption.

The data shows that the second generation has received academic credentials in their new country of residence and tries to cash when they enter into the family business and end up in conflict with the seniors. According to Bourdieu, this is called “opposition of economic and cultural capital” (Swartz, 2009, p.192), and in this subcontinent Muslim family business, economic capital always overrides the cultural capital. Arguably education appears as a theoretical ‘prized’ rather than one to be practically implemented into business innovation. Consequently, an emerging pattern sees the second generation shifting to other fields, where jobs or start-up ventures allow them to independently exercise their capitals. But, of course, this leaves the field of Asian Corner shop culture in a precarious position as its traditional and trans-generational roots of inheritance are cut.

The ethnographic observation also shows some reflexivity from the senior agents during the conflict between the siblings regarding digital knowledge. Although interestingly, this reflexively brings an interviewer effect (Kenway and McLeod, 2004) into critical relief, this was not necessarily so given respondents highlighted such tensions were a long-lasting issue ‘those two are always arguing over bloody social media’; ‘Facebook, Twitter it’s all rubbish causes endless fights’. Therefore, while accentuating reflexivity as an over-interviewer effect as cultural and observational bias, these interventions served to unmask pre-existing issues around digital adoption and business development.

4.3 TECHNOPHOBIA AND INFLUENCER NETWORK

This section focuses on the third major theme of this study, namely, technophobia and influencer networks evidenced within the South Asian diaspora. Essentially this refers to the generational assimilation and resistance to digital technologies, how it impacts traditional entrepreneurship and the narratives and behaviours deployed to legitimate maintaining the status quo. In Bourdieusian terms, this section reflects the 'transgenerational reproduction' and resistance evidenced within the family business, local community and network of influencers (Trembaczowski, 2018). However, in this instance, transgenerational reproduction is forced or shaped via the power and privilege of the traditional network of Asian patriarchy and social hierarchy. The section highlights an inherent technophobia and technological 'anti-capital that is used to delegitimise the entrepreneurialism and spirit of the second generation. Ironically, with a claim from the fathers and influencer network that they are solidifying and ensuring the inheritance and future of their children.

Even when we look at the high street, the shop closing rate is accelerating all over the UK due to various reasons. The shopping habit of the consumers is one of the main reasons which shifts dramatically from on store to online and leads the traditional retailing shops harder to carry on. Furthermore, high street retailers fail to recognise that immense shift in online buying behaviours of the consumers and adapt online accordingly (Simpson, 2019). The fate of Asian retail shops is also the same as high street shops. The people mainly run the corner retail shops from the Asian subcontinent as a family business. Their shop running environment is more traditional than the high street. As a result, they have also gone out of business.

On the other hand, online giant Amazon has been able to grasp the behavioural change of the consumers and become identical with online buying. Amazon revealed that in 2019, the number of products sold per minute on Amazon reached 4000 (Mohsin, 2019). Therefore, to remain in the competition, businesses have started focusing on their online presence regardless of their size and volume. The businesses' overall performance is now dependent on the number of products selling online.

Technology is evolving and assimilating in day to day life at a brisk pace in the developed country where the diaspora community finds it difficult to adjust. The first generation of this community who came from a different lifestyle is the main victim of adjusting to the fast and rapidly changing information and communication technology. Therefore, this reflects into their personal life and the entrepreneurial environment where lack of technical knowledge creates technophobia and ends up with the avoidance of it. The following data highlights the fact:

Interview data

“No, because if you run a business, you have to give the script to the people who run the shop. If they got the script there, they got guidelines there, then there is no problem.”

“I know my dad is always away from new technology adoption like social media for marketing purposes or latest software for the till. The reason I understand this is not his cup of tea. It is too late for him to learn new things and implement them into the business.”

“Marketing is the key driver of the business and since last decade it is more technology driven. But my concern is, it changes too quickly. Me and my wife have been running this business for over 35 years. It is difficult for us to run with fast changing technology.”

“Technology is everywhere nowadays. It has both good and bad sides. Obviously, social media connected and integrated all walks of life but I think for a small business like us, it is time consuming. We have limited resources and workforces. On top of that, it requires continuous personal updates.”

“Applying social media into the business is not a big task but I worry about carrying it out in the right way. I do not know how to operate those things. If I go for it, I have to pay someone to run it. Big retailers are investing money on it but for small corner shops it is not worthwhile.”

“To apply social media into the business is the best idea but in a family business not every member is equally skilled in using social media. Personal use and professional use are quite different. My son always tells me to go for it but I avoid this because if I do not know how to control it, why will I take it?”

Moreover, apart from technophobia, new technology adoption also depends on the influencers from the community. This is due to the structural type of the Asian diasporic community, which is nexus in nature and created a closed environment in the family to discuss everything with the senior and getting and providing support as a result of the strong family bonding with the close and distant relatives. Apart from the hierarchical position in the family, community leader, mosque Imam, Muslim faith, culture and tradition, family and societal norms are the powerful influencers in the Asian Muslim diasporic community. This is indicated below:

Interview data:

“Many of my relatives and nearest family members asked me to join social media because it is easy. Yes, maybe their repeated influence helped me. Also I have seen a lot of people online like local takeaways, beauty salons and so on. That is why I have made a decision to use social media.”

“My dad strictly follows the religious laws in both personal and professional life. Me and my other siblings were born and graduated in this country and know about the emerging high-tech and its impact in business. However my dad does not give a green signal unless he gets a clear view on it.”

“I attended a seminar on social media organized in the mosque for the ethinc people and their business. First time I got to know its various aspects and advantages. After that I have started doing it myself on Facebook. Though not in a professional way, it is making some differences in the business.”

“The community never influenced me because they are not my competitors. My shops are just safe from this type of disease. People compare your business to the other big stores because you cannot change their thinking. They actually know the prices. The prices are on their fingertips.”

“I know people are in different businesses using social media to attract people. I have discussed this with my family and relatives. I got mixed opinions about it that makes me basically confused about getting a decision. After all it's a family business and I have to listen to it all.”

“My grandfather had the same business in Pakistan 25 years ago where there was no available technology and the business was going well without

them. Though the scenario is completely opposite in this country, my father is following grandfather's footsteps like a tradition.”

Furthermore, the relationship and connection with the community and various networks also play a crucial role in adopting social media in the business. However, lack of cohesion due to religious faith and common distrust exists between the Muslim diasporic community and the wider native community, often leading to overlooking the impact of social media implementation in the business. Apart from this, conflicts and divides in their community also drive the impediment of knowledge sharing among the community members, creating a misconception about the new technology and its impact on the business. The following data is highlighted below:

Interview data

“Yes, they always follow but they never actually share their expertise. That is the disease among the Asian people. They do not share but they copy each other. People from Both countries (India and Pakistan) still do not trust each other due to their political mindset.”

“Another important thing is that the community is not big where the shop is located. Moreover, it is on the high street, very few people know each other. If it was in the skin, that would be a different story. People would know each other. It is on the high street so people do not know each other very well.”

“If one person opens a shop in the city center and he is doing well, the other person in our community opens another shop next to him. They are not

competing with other nationalities but always competing with their own community people. Both shopkeepers go against each other.”

Surprisingly, technophobia and poor community connection are not always the cause of rejection. Sometimes, the size of the business, nature of the trade, inability to compete with big shots are the other factors that lead to social media avoidance in the business. Therefore, despite having knowledge and interest in applying various forms of social media platforms in the family firm, they cannot overcome those facts. This is evidenced as follows:

Interview data

“I had a Facebook page for my business named ‘10’ O clock shop’ but I had it taken down because we cannot afford that much money. When I started, at that time they were asking £35 per month to update the promotion. Then I stopped because I couldn’t afford it. due to the size of my business.”

“If you ask me individually, it’s basically not worth it for us. We don’t have that kind of capability or demand and or the clientation frankly. I don’t think so we got the capability. There’s not enough meat on the bone in this trade for the small retailers because it’s just too many regulations for too many things.”

“It’s nothing personal. It’s a pure business and for business you need to look into what’s your input and what’s your output. As more input than output, then no point of wasting time and money. We are small retailers, we can not win over the big supermarkets for this social media marketing campaign.”

“In online marketing, the minor things can just shake up the whole thing. For no reason you could be end up in some sort of stupid legal fight. which can

cause your business. We can't take these chances for the 4 or 5 or 6 percent business. We cannot take the chance to destroy our 94 percent business."

"I understand, as I said, our business is quite a bit different. It's not that we cannot. Being a small shopkeeper or corner shop or small retailer, we don't have that kind of privilege to go online for marketing the business or to hire a van or start delivering and these things."

The above data resembles the Bourdieusian Oeuvre of capital predominantly in south Asian Muslim owned family retail business in Glasgow. According to the Bourdieusian theory, every field carries its capital, which is competed over and through such competition legitimates the field in a self-perpetuating power struggle (Bourdieu, 1991). On the other hand, social and cultural criteria of the habitus are related to the capital that receives values. Therefore, this process highlights the inter-relationship between capital, field and habitus.

Social media adoption in the family business depends on having the financial capital and the cultural capital in the business owner. According to Bourdieu, economic capital is the mother of all forms of capital and different forms of capital evolved from the economic capital (Bourdieu, 1985). However, the data reveals that the effort required to transform the economic capital to technological skills (cultural capital) is less because most family business owners understand this cost of investment is time-consuming. However, since the first generation fails to recognise the value of digital or technological skills attainment and their positive benefit or return, they refuse to invest the time and trust, never mind economic resources, to secure such technological skills or capital. Bourdieu refers to this as gratitude or the 'trust' placed that the debt of time will, eventually, materialise into benefit or gain, i.e. time invested

will provide a productive output even though we do not know or understand what that output may be (Bourdieu, 1985). This is analogous to the Asian parents who, having no understanding or appreciation of education, 'believe' or have 'trusting faith' that their economic investment in a university education will eventually pay off. Therefore, the absence of trust in shop owners hinders the implementation of social media as a new technology in the business.

In the field of the family business, the agent's position and the proportion of capital possessed determines the agent's power within this field. The data reveals that in the family business, the shop owners, who are mostly the father in the family, hold a stance of power due to the ownership of economic capital and implementing social media in the business requires the shop owners to convert the proportion of their economic capital into the techno capital. Though they know its benefit in the business, they are making various excuses in the form of practical restrictions and enforced on them. Those practical restrictions arise from their level of educational attainment, social connectedness and status in the community. Therefore, The father/grandfather, while appreciating or having a 'gut feeling' that social media/techno capital is or could be beneficial, reject or override such feelings due to their embedded capitals accumulated over time and valued by traditional business and networks. As such, the "subjective hope of profit" (Webb, Schirato and Danahar, p.23). Becomes subsumed or dismissed by the more dominant "objective probability of profit" (Webb, Schirato and Danahar, 2002, p.23). Which they 'know to be real through experience', i.e. social media may well be a new and possibly profitable venture, but I know the established practices are, or have been, profitable. So we stay with that which we know.

To secure or improve the place in the field, agents are always gambling for the capital. Again, it is evident that the migrant families found the necessity and importance of education and, therefore, investing their assets for educating their children with the intention of a better position in the societal field. Bourdieu labelled this as a transformation of capital (Bourdieu, 1985). However, the data found that agents are showing a lack of transformation when it comes to new technology like social media adoption into the family business. Therefore, the shop owners get trapped in their behaviour resulting in the inhibition of the conversion of capital to enhance their position in the retail field.

Theme	Sub-theme	Illustrative data sample	Frequency	Illustrative literature
Technophobia and influencer network	Adjustment with technology	<i>“Not every member in the family is equally skilled in using social media. Personal use and professional use are quite different. My son always tells me to go for it but I avoid this because if I do not know how to control it, why will I take it?”</i>	10	Knowledge regarding any issue is associated with the risk in the family business and without it, business might lead in the wrong direction (Basu and Goswami, 1999).
	Community structure and its influencing power	<i>“My dad strictly follows the religious laws in both personal and professional life. However, my dad does not give a green signal unless he gets a clear view on it.”</i>	9	“embedded social relations provides the possibility of a negative, constraining or destructive influence on business development”(McPherson, 2010, p.392).
	Conflict in the community	<i>“If one person opens a shop in the city centre and he is doing well, the other person in our</i>	8	High level of community conflicts has a negative impact and therefore, members of the family

		<i>community opens another shop next to him. They are not competing with other nationalities but always competing with their own community people. Both shopkeepers go against each other."</i>		business take extra caution to prevent their business information from being exposed in the community (Dayani, 2017).
	Other social factors	<i>"There's not enough meat on the bone in this trade for the small retailers because it's just too many regulations for too many things."</i>	10	"Rapidly changing technologies often pose a financial challenge for small business ventures [...] Technologies common to larger firms such as the internet may not be common or fully utilized among small businesses" (Bressler, Bressler and Bressler, 2011, p.51).

Table 4.3: Technophobia and influencer network (Key data, frequency and relevant literature)

Technophobia emerges from the lack of technical knowledge and the agents who treated themselves as substandard, deprived of resources, restricted social connection and ambitions. The data also reveals that the agents in the family business field try to be portrayed as inferior compared to their competitors. In addition, they also denied the resources, i.e. economic capital through which they can gain other different forms of capital. According to Bourdieu, this is called "symbolic violence" (Webb, Schirato and Danahar 2002, p.25), which he describes as "the violence which is exercised upon a social agent with his or her complicity" (Bourdieu and Wacquant, 1992, p.167). This symbolic violence is the result of misrecognition that Bourdieu refers to as the "form of forgetting" (Webb, Schirato and Danahar, 2002, p.24) of the agents in the given field because they unable to

understand that they create the situation; instead, their circumstances appears to them as “the natural order of things” (Webb, Schirato and Danahar 2002, p.25). Therefore, avoidance of social media implementation in the family business results from the failure to recognise the symbolic violence created by the shop owners.

Apart from technophobia, the social media implementation in the Asian sub-continent diasporic family businesses are also largely determined by the level of connectedness at various networks in the society. It is due to the culture of that particular ethnicity where families are connected with their relatives and neighbours to a large extent. The data reflects the fact that social media utilisation for the family business strategy is greatly influenced positively and negatively by those influencer networks. According to the Bourdieusian construct, it is due to the dynamic nature of the cultural field, which is invariably being transformed by intimate practices and guidelines, and by intersection with diverse fields (Swartz, 2009). Therefore, the field of the family business can be viewed as ‘inalienable’ concerning the financial consideration that altered rapidly due to the alliance of inside and outside coercion. Bourdieu labelled this as the shift of the autonomous nature of the field of the family business into a ‘heteronomous’ nature (Deer, 2003). However, despite having techno capital in the other family members, the internal pressure from them is superseded by the patriarchal family structure and cannot understand the benefits of having social media in the family business. On the other hand, the external pressure, which is in the form of interrelationships of relatives and the society and its higher influencing power on the field of business, provided a rise of probabilities for inside changes.

The data shows that businesses are shifting towards embracing social media or even using a small extent due to external influence. Moreover, the internal changes

from the external pressure do not always bring positive outcomes in the given field. The shop owners who received the positive influences from their social networks and acted accordingly are starting to get the benefits of using social media and remain in the competition. Besides, those who have negative influences or reject the positive ones become gradually segregated and endangered their existence in the competition. (Webb, Schirato and Danahar, 2002). Apart from the influencer networks, which is always subjective, the shop owners are also influenced by the objective state like religion, culture, and others, which they ingrained over time and remained with them across the context.

The data also reveal that the shop owners have less or zero institutionalised forms of cultural capital than their second generation in the family business. This lack of technical knowledge, therefore, inhibits business growth because of their sole decision making power. On the contrary, shop owners invest money in their children in elite educational institutions to gain skills (cultural capital), network (social capital) and status (symbolic capital) (Bourdieu, 1985). As a result, a strong struggle is seen between the generations in the field of the family business. The second generation, who hold more cultural capital than their counterpart, faces resistance to convert the economic gain skills.

Social media adoption in family business does not always depend on the power relations among the family members. Sometimes, they need to put their business in a wider context with their competitors. For example, in the field of the retail industry, family businesses are the weak actors to the supermarket, particularly in terms of financial capital. Therefore, sometimes having little interest in moving the business into cloud commerce is ignored due to the fear of failure or inability to compete with big supermarkets.

4.4 ETHNIC ENCLAVES: CULTURAL CRYOSTASIS AND CAPITALS OF CONTAINMENT

An ethnic enclave refers to a geographical region where a group of people from specific nationality live together and separate from the indigenous people in both social and economic fashion (Qadeer and Kumar, 2006). Therefore, in the case of this study, the ethnic enclave refers to the family businesses run by the members of the particular ethnic/South Asian neighbourhood. Moreover, ethnic enclaves provide an environment for the south Asian Muslim diasporic community to practice their culture and tradition, which is reflected in their personal and professional life. Such cultural practices were evident from the outset of the study:

Interview data

“Staying close to each other with our own country people, I think, creates strength and bonding. The community we live in provides the feeling of living in our own country. Last year, I had some problems regarding my business. I got help mentally and financially from my neighbours.”

“The biggest advantage of living within one's own community is having mental satisfaction. I moved here to the Southside, Glasgow, 4 years ago from Newbury. Here, I got my own community. My children now can go to a mosque with other neighbours' kids to learn Islamic norms.”

“Obviously, community plays an important role. But it depends on which community you are in. We get more opportunities to celebrate our cultural

festivals like Ramadan, Eid, and Islamic New Year when we live together with our own people in the community than the native people.”

“I thought my children would never learn Urdu language, but recently in the community we got several families from Pakistan. It gives me hope. My children now can play with the neighbouring kids with the same language. It helps them to practice their own mother tongue along with the English.”

“I do not sell alcohol and pork in my shop because I am a Muslim and in my religion those are strictly prohibited to deal with. I agree, it is affecting my business but I cannot go beyond my religion.”

“Though we are away from our country physically but emotionally attached to our motherland. It becomes possible because of the community we live in. We celebrate every occasion the same way we used to do in our home country.”

The restraint of adopting social media arises from technophobia and the tendency to be geographically close and have large family units. However, this geographic and familial closeness enhances or feeds the enclave's binding and containing nature, culture, and traditions. Interview data and Ethnographic observations reflect this:

Interview data

“We have created a small but strong community here. It is our strength. It also has some negative sides. The senior members of the community are backdated and more conventional than the younger generation. As a result, the traditional way wins over updated new technology like social media.” (c)

Observations

Staff working in the business premises are more likely to speak their own language and their manners and attitudes are more culturally reflected in front of indigenous people who are mainly the customers in the business.

First generations of the diasporic Muslim family business are more prone to work under own cultural environment than their successors and they mainly show the unwillingness to come out of the comfort zone that lead to the avoidance of accepting new ideas into the business.

On many occasions, the interviewer found that the majority of the staff working in the shop are from the same nationality. The shop owners have strong feelings about their country and it is reflected in the workplace by recruiting staff from their own country.

The interviewer also observed that the shop owners and their family members are more comfortable to work with the people from the same ethnicity than the indigenous Scottish citizens. It is due to the Muslim religious faith that women are strictly prohibited to unveil themselves to those who are unknown and not a relative for them.

Another occasion, the interviewer saw that all the staff working in the shop were from the same place from the back country where the shop owner came from. One point of the interview, the respondent said it is easy to work with the people from the same region with the same language.

The interviewer noticed that the shop owner was comfortable with the staff by using his mother tongue and less effort used to get the thing done.

However, the culture and tradition of a Muslim diasporic community often do not bring a positive outcome in their personal and professional life. Sometimes, it creates a hindrance or a state of ignorance of accepting what is good for them. Therefore, a diasporic community becomes cryostasis culturally and ignores assimilating with the good things. Moreover, staying in an enclave gives rise to the cultural cryostasis and capitals of containment, which also undeniably influence the business. As a result, their cryostatic action forces them not to acquire or convert the existing capital into new capital, which could benefit their business. This capital of containment becomes self-destructive in the long run because it only privileges the shop owners to use the traditional capital in practice. Interview data and Ethnographic observations reflect this:

Interview data

“Technology is entering into the business much faster than before. But my father does not prefer those things. He had a business back home. He is running the business the way he used to run over there. He is still holding the tradition but we are getting tough day by day.”

“I have been doing this business for over 25 years. That time, there was no social media but still we did good business.. I believe, if we focus on the needs of the customers and fulfil them accordingly, the customers will come back to us again and again.”

“Moving this business on social media does not give any guarantee that you will be successful. End of the day, it is the trust that you build up with the people who come to your shop. It is very difficult to get trust from the customers via online because it is hard to recognise good customers.”

“This is the disadvantage of family business. You have to follow the chain of command. If you know something will change the business for the better but you cannot do this. My father always tells us that outside whatever you do but in the family you have to respect the tradition.”

Observation

One interviewee was given religious advice by his neighbour about social media and labelled as ‘fitna’ which means a state or temptation that separates achieving good things. This type of religious view creates an invisible barrier and as a result they fail to see the positive side of it.

This study aims to critically understand how cultural tradition impacts the acceptance of social media as a business strategy for small retail businesses. Therefore, ethnic enclaves play a significant role to meet the requirements of this investigation. Moreover, staying in an enclave gives rise to the cultural cryostasis and capitals of containment, which also undeniably influence the business. This section highlights the staying in its cultural environment as a 'paradox of proximity' (Karadağ, 2011) that causes the shop owners to run the business more traditionally, which degrades the entrepreneurial spirit due to the lack of 'professional capital' in their strategic business tool.

This study enables the researcher to observe very closely how the Muslim culture overrides the decision-making process in the business. Moreover, while taking the interview, the respondents' view was always supported by what actions were taken according to the tradition by their fellow members in the society. However, on occasion, the researcher observed that one interviewee was given religious advice

by his neighbour about social media and labelled as 'fitna', which means a state or temptation that separates achieving good things. This type of religious view creates an invisible barrier, and as a result, they fail to see the positive side of it though it has been accepted in different types of business all over the world as a diverse business strategic tool.

The cultural cryostasis is more visible in the business premises run by the members of the Muslim ethnic community. Like, surrounded by the people from the same culture and tradition in the neighbourhood, they also prefer to work with their people. That environment creates a comfort zone for them and enables them to practice their own culture and tradition in the workplace and, at the same time, run the business more traditionally. The researcher observed that staff working in the business premises are more likely to speak their language, and their manners and attitudes are more culturally reflected in front of indigenous people who are mainly the customers in the business. This is analogous to the Chinatown in every megacity where Chinese craft and food shops create the environment with their culture and tradition for the indigenous people to give a different cultural vibe in their own country. Working in a familiar environment provides "cultural reproduction" (Kraaykamp and Van Eijck, 2010, p.215) rather than demanding or changing the conventionality.

The diasporic family business owners do not know about social media's 'public value' for their business. It is more evident when the novel coronavirus or COVID-19 causes the global pandemic. The government had to lock down the country for public safety, and only shops of daily commodities were left open. In this crisis moment, online activities, especially social media, play a significant role. Supermarkets, which have online order receiving and drop off facilities, help people

stay safe and prevent the spread of the virus. The researcher has come across observations and found that the cultural or traditional obligations, lack of knowledge or interest and sometimes influence from the community lead the Asian Muslim family businesses to prevent the embracement of social media or any other form of online activities into their organisations. Therefore, whatever the reasons are lying behind it, the small shop owners are not only losing the business but also unable to comply with the emergency requirement imposed by the government during the crisis period.

Moreover, they are putting their lives at risk and the staff who are working for them. Being a part of an ethnic enclave gives the fact that the agents cannot realise social conditions that are human-made and not natural. Therefore living as part of the enclave solidifies the misrecognition (Jenkins, 2002) and practices cultural cryostasis and misses the opportunity to embrace social media.

Theme	Sub-theme	Illustrative data sample	Frequency	Illustrative literature
Ethnic enclaves: cultural cryostasis and capitals of containment	Field of cultural practice	<i>"Staying close to each other with our own country people, I think, creates strength and bonding. The community we live in provides the feeling of living in our own country. Last year, I had some problems regarding my business. I got help mentally and financially from my neighbours."</i>	10	Working in the familiar environment provides "cultural reproduction" (Kraaykamp and Van Eijck, 2010, p.215). rather than demanding or changing the conventionality.
	Actions bounded by	<i>"My dad strictly follows the religious</i>	9	"Religious influences not

	the culture	<i>laws in both personal and professional life. However, my dad does not give a green signal unless he gets a clear view on it."</i>		only shape societies, but also can have a profound impact on organizational decisions, operations, and ethical behaviour"(Alrub aishi, McAdam and Harrison, 2021).
	Outcome of the culturally oriented actions	<i>"You have to follow the chain of command in the family business. If you know something will change the business for the better but you cannot do this. My father always tells us that outside whatever you do but, in the family, you have to respect the tradition."</i>	8	"..family unity, religious faith, respect and honour - and it is those cultural values which give rise to certain hopes and fears for children who are making the difficult transition through youth into adulthood."(Qureshi and Moores, 1999, p.315)

Table 4.4: Ethnic enclave: cultural cryostasis and capitals of containment (key data, frequency and relevant literature)

However, all the time working in your cultural atmosphere sometimes creates boundaries in different aspects of the business. The researcher observed that the first generations of the diasporic Muslim family business are more prone to work under their cultural environment than their successors, and they mainly show the unwillingness to come out of the comfort zone that leads to the avoidance of accepting new ideas into the business. It is because they create a similar atmosphere in the business setting like an ethnic enclave in the society. It is due to living in the ethnic territory that creates "historically and socially situated conditions"

(Bourdieu, 1990b, p.55) that enable its members to replicate their habitus easily. Therefore, the businesses become culturally frozen, and growth becomes stagnant.

On the other hand, the researcher also observed that the second generation feels uncomfortable working within their cultural environment compared to the first generation. It is evident in their language and dress during work time. They prefer to talk in English with their colleagues in front of the indigenous people who are the customers who are hardly seen as senior members in the family business. Similar things happen in terms of dress and custom because the second generation grew up with the native people and are more comfortable with the customs and manners of the indigenous people. Therefore, cultural clashes are more obvious in the workplace of the diasporic community that appears from the intergeneration preference of the work environment.

Social media is breaking the cultural mirror, and therefore it is a new trend that challenges the tradition. However, the patriarchal nature of family business tries to resist the change by being culturally cryostasis. On the other side, younger agents are against the capital of containment held by the senior agents and therefore challenge the notion of trans-generational reproduction (Bourdieu and Passeron, 1990).

4.5 PRIVILEGE AND POVERTY: DIGITAL ADOPTION

This section focuses on the fifth major theme of this study, namely, privilege and poverty: digital adoption. This focuses on data within the family business run by the South Asian diaspora. Following this, the final theme will be discussed as a collective

analysis of the study. To start the discussion under this theme, the reader needs to contextualise this study's cultural and traditional milieu. The diaspora communities within which the study is set come from a Muslim background that promotes entrepreneurialism and supports business setup. However, this is often within the poorest areas, with high unemployment, drug and substance abuse and low educational attainment. In addition, several shops within this study mirror are supported by the SIMD profile. Therefore, the adoption of social media or any other form of technology into the business is largely associated with a wide range of socio-economic factors. Sometimes, the interest of moving the business into the digital platform is set back by the nature of the customers and the area where the shop is located. Interview data and Ethnographic observations reflect this:

Interview data

"It depends on where we are located. You see, my shop is located in the area, where mostly lower middle class or poor people live. I can even see the type of phone they are using. So, for me, it does not help my business in the deprived area. It's just a waste of money and time"

"I can understand the advantages of using social media platforms for business but most of the people in this area receive different forms of benefit from the local council for their daily living. I think social media cannot influence them much in this case. As long as they have money they come and buy products."

"It is not like that we did not look into it but the customers we have are only the passing crowd. We are located in the heart of the town, people anyway come and pick some sweets, a can of cola or bottle of water. Social media can be good but I think not for this place."

Observations

The nature of the customers, their behaviour and the outfits in less affluent areas were noticed by the researcher several times. The staff and shop owner's response to them dramatically changed in comparison to the others who were decent and not the local residents.

The shop owner came to an argument about their behaviour to the local customers that if you behave well they would sit on your head and play around you. Moreover, it would be a waste of money if you introduce a digital platform by targeting such types of customers who are fully unaware about it.

In a low profile area, fights and racial slurs were common for trivial issues. Interview was interrupted several times as the shop owner had to be involved in it. Afterwards, the interview was resumed with apologies for the incident from the shop owner and made a frustrating comment 'Why bother fancy social media campaigns for such types of people who are not worth having it'.

However, the usage of digital technology in diasporic entrepreneurship is not an uncommon issue. Like any other business run by the indigenous people, the south Asian Muslim family businesses also invest in different forms of technology but not mainly for business growth and marketing. Their primary concern is always for safety and security and, therefore, the technology used for the surveillance and protection of the business and its staff. Interview data and Ethnographic observations reflect this:

Interview data

“No chance for social media in this area. Every second day police chase someone for some sort of crime. I installed more than required surveillance cameras for the shop security. For me, it is more important to invest money for security purposes rather than marketing for the business.”

“I do not think social media can alter the situation for this business. My shop is next to a homeless hotel. You can see most of the shops nearby are shut because of this hotel. All drinkers, drug addicts live there. We survived because of the several security measures we have taken into action.”

“Though we are not using social media as a new technology, our business is digitally equipped. We are using all forms of gadgets to carry out the daily activities like all other supermarkets do. Moreover, the latest audio video security cameras are in place for the theft and burglaries”.

“My father mostly runs the business. I understand the significance of social media but this type of thing he cannot manage by himself. We are more concerned about his safety. We have installed a surveillance system in the shop. For us, personal safety is more important than business”.

Observation

An interview took place in the office room which the shop owner called ‘control room’. He was using updated software and surveillance systems to track the business and also explained how positive changes it brings. Surprisingly, the shop owner totally refuted as the researcher brought attention to the importance of social media as a new technology in the business.

Interestingly, diasporic family businesses in the more affluent customer based areas have the opposite scenario. According to the SMID profile, some areas have

different levels of substantial consumers to target marketing through digital platforms. However, those family businesses are doing more old ways of selling rather than focusing on social media promotion by which they can build strong relationships with the consumers and enhance return on investment. Therefore, possible customers' demands are cancelled by the shop owners' belief, lack of knowledge, and enthusiasm. Ethnographic observations and interview data reflect this:

Observations

The researcher noticed that the nature of the customers is completely opposite to the low profile area in terms of manners and behaviour from the high affluent area. On the other side, the shopkeeper was not open with the customers and failed to recognise the demand from them.

The shop near the university had customers who were mostly students and the university staff. 'Students can be easily reached by social media' -when this statement was made by the researcher, the shop owner argued that students are using mobile for the game and time passes.

Interview data

"When the students are away, we do not have much business. That time we usually think we should go online. But when the students come back and pick your business up again then we think that we are fine because everything is getting back to normal. So it is better to carry on as it is."

"We see different delivery cyclists running throughout the day. It is clear that now locals are more comfortable to use online to meet their daily demands. I

understand the importance of going online but my father thinks people only buy hot meals via online, they will not order grocery products.”

Moreover, in recent years, all businesses have been adopting digital platforms and the traditional approach to remain in the competition. However, compared to other industries, the retail sector in the UK is far away from this transformation. According to the report on BBC, only 18% of UK retail purchases are online (BBC, 2018). These statistics are reflected in the family-run small retail shops owned by the Asian diasporic community where they are more traditional as 'do it this way', therefore resistant to change. Interview data and Ethnographic observations reflect this:

Interview data

“We are very tiny in this whole trade. We are basically about no call when they said business. As long as the people get money, they will come to the local shops for daily commodities and I think social media will not make any difference.”

“It's not something they can plan a couple of days back. It's just a last-minute service. That's what we are, if you are good at your package, your customer will always be there. Locals do not depend on social media for their daily needs”

“To advertise on social media you need to spend money. They will give you free for a couple of months and after that you need to pay 90 pounds for a Facebook page and all I have is a certain amount of sales which I need to do and so I felt it is not worth advertising on social media.”

Observations

On occasion, the interview was frequently interrupted by the phone call. The shop owner resumed the interview stating 'people think that we do not know anything, technology makes the work faster but how can they increase my sales. I deal with the local people who do not wait for marketing or what software I am using.'

Another place, the shop got a digital signboard, a separate office room with the latest surveillance system. However, when the conversation came to the marketing on social media, the shop owner looked at his son and mentioned that my son is always against it and he thinks I cannot control it. (c)

The data presented above under the theme reflects the “practice and its logic” (Jenkins, 2002, p.62) and other different major constructs of Bourdieu. Bourdieu developed his speculated framework of social practice based on inhabitants who perceive themselves as a community. Within the community, there are different views and ideas about the realm and its position therein. Importantly, the community provides a strong structuring relation of individual worldviews or how the world is supposed to be, of individual behaviours and justifications that all support the illusion or ‘rules of the game’ and so process of misrecognition. However, the important point here is that worldviews, embodied and rationalized, are dynamically internalized and taught; learned behaviours are found in everyday interactions. Given preceding sections, the concept of social practice is evident within the south Asian Muslim diasporic family businesses. However, it is argued that the dynamic of everyday social practice is restricted, or agency hindered, by the force of the collective community.

Moreover, as data reflects, the behaviours and actions of the agents in the family business are based on knowledge, or a form of informal institutional capital, which they acquire while carrying out the actions of everyday business. Therefore, this informal institutional capital of the everyday occupies a privileged status and, given its success over many years, is easily deployed to refute the need for the new techno-capital of social media. Simply the business owner, family and community of customers, who encounter, embody and internalize this informal institutional capital or logic or practice, see no or little value in adopting 'new practices'. As stated, 'this work so why change it for something that we have never used?'

From the above data, it is evident that the senior agents in the family business considered time a natural cycle. Therefore, their behaviour and actions in the space are fixed and cannot be reconstructed. Moreover, the Islamic religious faith catalyzes their belief and blocks the thinking capability of time and space. However, according to the Bourdieusian construct, time is nothing but constructed socially (Bourdieu, 1984). Furthermore, time and space are considered as an obvious feature of practice where time is restrained and at the same time become a resource of social engagement, and space acts as a place wherein interaction happens. Therefore, in the family businesses, this misrecognition about the key features of the practice makes them carry out the business in a more traditional way. As a result, the necessity and demand of social media as a modification or upgrade in the family business strategy are impeded due to the inadequacy of tempo into everyday practice (Bourdieu, 1977).

Theme	Sub-theme	Illustrative data	Frequency	Illustrative
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		sample		literature
Privilege and Poverty: Digital adoption	Nature of the customers	<i>"You see, my shop is located in the area, where mostly lower middle class or poor people live. I can even see the type of phone they are using. So, for me, it does not help my business in the deprived area. It's just a waste of money and time"</i>	10	Organisations must pay attention to the consumers behaviour while making decision on the social and digital media as their marketing strategy (Dwivedi et al., 2021)
	Surveillances and security	<i>"Every second day police chase someone for some sort of crime. I installed more than required surveillance cameras for the shop security. For me, it is more important to invest money for security purposes rather than marketing for the business."</i>	9	"Retailers are not interested in security only to create a safe and joyful environment for consumers. Instead, their interest also lies in preventing crime toward themselves, for example, shoplifting, employee theft and vandalism" (Kajalo and Lindblom, 2016, p. 220)
	Shop location	<i>"It will be no use because my shop is next to a homeless hotel. You can see most of the shops nearby are shut because of this hotel. All drinkers, drug addicts live there."</i>	8	"Indeed many organizations have been slow to adopt new technologies due to perceived barriers such as lack of money, time and training, negative views about usefulness, as well as unfamiliarity with the particular technology" (Michaelidou, Siamagka and Christodoulides, 201, p. 1155)
	Resistant to change	<i>"Locals do not depend on social media for their daily needs. If you are good at your package, your customer will always be there"</i>	10	First-generation in the family business have failed to adapt changes in the field of business and contemporary social shifts and therefore practising myopic style of management (Pang and Chan, 1998)

Table 4.5: Privilege and poverty: digital adoption (key data, frequency and relevant literature)

Moreover, from the data, it can be said that, in family businesses, the senior members who represent the first generation in this industry show an inadequate sense of logical practice compared to the youngest members in the family. It is due to the lack of what Bourdieu labelled as 'a feels for the game' (1990b, p.66). Therefore, young generations exhibit more interest in the acceptance of new ideas and technology into the business because they are the inseparable part of the contemporary circumstances, and within it, they grew up, learned and acquired a variety of practical skills. According to Bourdieu, it is called 'the sense of the position one occupies in social space' (1991, p. 235). It means that the sense of position provides the incapacity to recognise the arbitrary nature of the social reality to the people, except 'the way things are' (Jenkins, 2002, p. 70). This sense of position in the societal space differs from person to person who is also seen in the field of the family business. Therefore, the data reflect that the adoption of social media in the business is rather granted for the son but not accepted for the father.

The main feature of this theme is the privilege of having social media in the family business. The data shows that the privilege is determined by both the customers and the shop owners. However, it did not happen together in the given context. The data also reveals that the demand from the customers is neglected due to the absence of techno-capital in the shop owners and the lack of determination and flexibility, which are the other key features of the logical practice. According to Bourdieu, it is called the 'the "art" of the necessary improvisation which defines excellence' (1990b, p. 20). In practice, excellence can be changed according to the

time and therefore, it is directly related to it. However, the observational data show that the patriarchal figure of the business got the view about the social life, which was fixed and based on the rules and models associated with the national culture and family traditions. Therefore, having this structured view inhibits the designing and creating capacity, which in turn shows the absence of improvisation in the business. For this reason, when senior members of the family run the business, they are unable to take the decision due to having a subjective stance about their practice.

The given data also reflects the social practice of the family business and is based on some set of rules and strategies. The strategies used in their practice are nothing, but the experiences they gathered and rules are determined by reproducing culture and traditions throughout life (Bourdieu, 1990b). Therefore, social media as a business strategy is based on the business owners' views about new technology. Social media and its acceptance depend on the amount of knowledge and skills in the form of cultural capital they embodied and institutionalised on the one hand and having several social contacts in the form of social capital on the other (Bourdieu, 1985). The data shows the patriarchal figure of the business got less or no cultural capital and high social capital compared to the younger generation. For that reason, senior members are more focused on their relatives and friends and are easily trusted and influenced by them. They are using social capital to set up a strategy for logical practice in the business. However, those social contacts are unable to bring economic advantages for the business owners.

The data also shows that younger family members are more interested in having new technology in the business. Again, it is due to having the institutional capital like a university degree (Bourdieu, 1985) which gives them the knowledge to understand

the importance of having social media as a strategic tool. As a result, having formal institutional capital in a son or grandson gives rise to ongoing intergenerational clashes in the field of the family business. Their logic of having social media into the business is based on their dynamic benefits in their personal lives. Therefore, logical practice differs from generation to generation and depends on the nature and its proper utilisation of capital in the field of the family business.

Furthermore, as data reflects, the practice of the agents in the family business is also based on a set of embodied dispositions or habitus of the agent and a networked system of social place or cultural field. This habitus of the agents and the field of family business collectively creates a particular logic of practice (Bourdieu, 1992b). However, the belief, understanding, relationship with the customers and actions of the patriarchal figure or the members of the first generation in this business field are constant, and they are using fixed regulations and traditions to operate the business regardless of the situation. As a result, there was a lack of introducing new rules or strategies in the business. Moreover, the business owners failed to recognise the importance of continuous connection with their customers, current social rules and trends and importantly, the time and space which are changing momentarily. Therefore, it can be said that the privilege of having social media in the family business was ignored or overlooked due to a lack of 'cultural literacy' (Webb, Schirato and Danaher, 2002 p. 57) in the agents.

The data also shows that all agents who were doing business regardless of the deprivation in the area understood its value. Therefore, this self-reflexive realisation about the importance of business leads them to utilise their resources to protect themselves. As a result, the agents were investing more economic capital to buy technology for the business's surveillance. However, the self-reflexivity in agents

about the importance of having social media as a new technology for the strategic growth of the business is very little or sometimes zero. It is due to the lack of knowledge and skills about social media. Therefore, they were not interested in spending money to use social media in the field of business. On the other side, the younger generation in the business got formal institutional capital like university degrees and technical skills, which gives them wider reflexivity about their capability and performance. Therefore, the logic of practice is opposite between two generations in the business. To sum up, it can be said that the logic of practice is influenced or determined by the level of self-reflexivity in the agents (Bourdieu and Wacquant, 1992)

The data also reflects that the logical practice in the field of the family business was also determined by the characteristics of the field (Beames and Telford, 2013). The characteristics include the internal rules and regulations and the social norms and the agent's ability to recognise both formal and informal cultural capital in all other members. In the field of the family business, rules of the game are largely based on culture and traditions, religion, gender and hierarchical position and social connectedness. In South Asian diasporic business, the social practice is influenced by the radical Islamic faith, male dominance, seniority, respect to elders, and close relatives and community opinion. Therefore, the complex structured rules give less ability to deal with strategic thinking, preventing successful practice.

Moreover, these complicated rules reduce the senior agent or business owner's ability to capitalise on moments and act accordingly. In the given context, the value of social media was also neglected due to the self-made rules on the one side and strictly following the rules on the other. As a result, younger generations who hold techno-capital and want to implement it were ignored and dominated by the senior

members. The data shows that the agents in the decision making position were unable to identify and use the capital which exists in the other family members in the business and missed the opportunity to turn them into an advantage.

The above data also reflects that apart from field rules, the habitus of the South Asian diasporic family business also strongly affects day-to-day social practices. Habitus drives all future activities and beliefs, and it differs from generation to generation in the family business due to the habitus that formed different ways of carrying out actions, choices, morals and logic and gained from diverse influential contexts like family structure, institutional attainment and others (Bourdieu, 2005).

4.6 DIASPORA, ENTREPRENEURSHIP AND DIGITAL DISCOURSE: PARADOX OF PATRIARCHY AND PROSPERITY.

This section provides the cumulative analysis of the study. Here the findings and analysis of the preceding sections, which stand in their own right, will be drawn together for a final Bourdieusian critique and contribution for the study/thesis. Following this, the final concluding chapter of the thesis will be presented. This study is not really about social media; it is about the identity of the South Asian Muslim diaspora community abroad. Therefore, it is worth stressing that as a cumulative analysis, this section provides a summative Bourdieusian discussion highlighting key theoretical concepts with core data. The section will demonstrate this by systematically highlighting the habitus of the individual agent, the structuring

relations of their community through to the field of business, its entrepreneurship, and those sanctioned and resisted capitals.

Fundamentally this study critically highlights a clash between the ultra-conservatism, or old discourse, against the new digital discourse, and both discourses have a habitus, field and capitals. In old discourse, the agency is severely structured and behaviours curtailed or controlled through the prism of religion. In comparison, Bourdieu is always at pains to avoid an overly structuralist analysis (Myles, 1999) by highlighting habitus, field, and capital interplay. Within this study, there is a distinctiveness as the Muslim religion dictates the worldview of the agent. Islam, even moderated Islam, is a 24/7 code where devotion to the faith is reflected in how deep the agent regulates or coordinates their life, business and personal relationships according to the Koran (Nisan, 1999). Therefore, agents in old discourse follow rules and regulations to carry out their daily activities. These norms and standards have restricted their knowledge and understanding and give a new shape in their behaviour towards others. In Bourdieusian terms, the Islamic system shapes or directs the bodily hexis, agents' physical movements and behaviours to an extensive degree (Starrett, 1995). The follower of the faith reflects a powerful doxic attitude and is fully immersed in the *illusio* of the belief system of Islam and the Islamic way of life, learning and, for this study, work or business (Bourdieu, 1984; Webb, 2002).

Therefore, the agents within this study exemplify a form of ultra-conservatism, and since the Islamic faith informs or impacts all aspects of life, the operation of family, business, community and faith are intertwined and central to the embodied habitus. Moreover, the first generation of agents of the cultural diaspora are the main transmitters of this mode of trans-generational reproduction. This is due to being

born and raised in a homeland environment (e.g. India, Bangladesh, and Pakistan) where the Islamic faith and culture, along with practical taxonomies like male/female, natural/cultural, are intensely encoded and practised from childhood as a learning and socialisation process. Moreover, this particular social practice results from unconscious habituation and routine work of agents, which is done without specific knowledge and awareness of their actions (Akram, 2012). In contrast to the younger generation of Scot-Asian, the first generation agents in the business reflect a larger extent of structured behaviour to the other agents in that particular business field.

Interestingly, gender discrimination is more evident in the Muslim diaspora's habitus and the family business in this old discourse. The data reflects that the females are either not allowed to participate in the decision-making process or have minimal input. This classificatory category of habitus is nothing but the result of the collective practice created by history as per schemas (Crossley, 2001; King, 2000).

Therefore, this ongoing discrimination is constantly taking forward in daily practice as a method of reproduction. Moreover, the social field also plays an important role in reproducing the habitus, and it also allows the agents to practice their transferable features of disposition in a similar field (Asimaki and Koustourakis, 2014). As a result, the power of sex or gender dominance is constantly reproduced because of the similar social field created by the agents in their new country of residence. The male superiority in this Muslim diaspora is not a novel practice. This is the continuation of the practice which was carried out by the generation and past generation. Bourdieu argued that this type of embodied disposition is based on the objective domain in which the habitus lives (Lahire, 2003; Reay, 2015). In this context of the study, the objective environment of the south Asian countries was formed culturally and driven traditionally where the first generation diaspora reveal

an overly structural or ultra-conservative worldview, which is reflected and reproduced in their habitus, bodily hexis and reinforced through their business practices or dispositions (Karim, 2003; Karner, 2007). Therefore, it is unsurprising that this generation reproduces, transmits and seeks to legitimise this in old discourse, its embodied history, dispositions and capitals to the next generation.

However, as data revealed, the maintenance of this old discourse has become increasingly untenable within the new objective environment that the younger Scot-Asian inhabit. Here a new discourse is revealed or emerging. Ethnographic data revealed a cultural clash of capitals between the old and new discourse. This is embodied in the younger generations who, being born in their new country of residence, are sensitised to a multicultural environment that informs, challenges, impacts, and shapes their habitus, the fields they engage with and the capitals required to operate within such. The Scots-Asian reflect a bodily hexis (Bourdieu, 1990a) where embodied and internalised dispositions are distinctive and different from their parents or older generation. The ethnographic data evidenced that the Scots-Asian agents ignored or bypassed the traditional ways of being and doing business. Therefore, they were more prone to use new technology and digital platforms in the business. Moreover, young agents are welcome to accept financial help from the banking system for their business as the first generation refuses to take it because of their strong religious faith.

Therefore, the habitus of the agents in the new discourse becomes less structured, and the Bourdieusian dynamic interplay of structure, agency, habitus, field and capital revealed, in the modern social and cultural trajectories, challenges and clashes of capital evidenced in the Scot-Asian. Though agents in new discourse grow up in families where cultural and traditional values and norms are

predominantly practised, the outside world provides new cultural practices. As a result, the agents in new discourse got the habitus which is mixed. Moreover, the younger generation in the family is less religiously practicable compared to their ancestors. Therefore, they tend to keep Islamic regulations aside in the day to day activities not only in the family but also in the field of the family business. This causes a conflict between the agents who have different minds set and practices in the respective fields. According to Bourdieu, it is called 'doxic attitude' (Webb, Schirato and Danaher, 2002, p.xi), which agents acquire from the different fields. The data reflects that the attitudes of the agents are different throughout the study.

It is important to inform the readers that the old discourse is mainly carried out by the agents who travelled from their country of origin, and here the participation of the second-generation agents are less significant or sometimes zero. The new discourse is moved along with the higher participation of the younger/second-generation agents with the first-generation agents. Therefore, the intergenerational clash is more evident in the new discourse than the old one. The conflicts are the results of the embodied dispositions in the agents and the different forms of capitals they acquired from the various fields (Jenkins, 2002). Throughout the study, the data reflects that the younger agents acquired institutionalized capital, which gives them the latest knowledge about the concurrent world. As a result, they are more prone to utilize their cultural capital into the economic capital in the field of the family business.

Moreover, as a generation Z, they take the usage of technology and social media in their activities of daily living. But, on the other hand, this institutional knowledge and application of new technology are novel to the senior agents in the field, which gives them less advantages in the business field. Hence, the younger agents resist change

from their older counterparts in the business as the senior agents fear that they might lose the controlling power if changes are in place. Therefore, the older agents use their hierarchical position and seniority to hide their lack of capital in the relevant field and oppress the change.

The data also highlights the role of the community in the Muslim diaspora. In old discourse, the Islamic faith influences the agents in their personal life and has strong influencing power over the different levels of the community. The power and centrality of Islam is more than simply the Mosque or Imam but is embodied, transmitted and amplified by the community. Religion plays a significant role and strongly ties up the individual in the community. In old discourse, families tend to reside near each other, and they do so to create a comfortable atmosphere so that culture and tradition can be practised easily (Bourdieu and Passeron, 1990).

Moreover, the agents create a strong diaspora in their new country of residence to help each other in the different forms of unconditional support. It is due to enormous benefits described by Islam about the unity in the community. As a result, the community provides security, protection and comfort to its members according to their religious faith. Agents in old discourse grew up in this environment and experienced the benefits of it. Therefore, they practice the same thing by creating a similar condition in their new residence (Swartz, 2009).

Moreover, in old discourse, one of the significant traditions in the south Asian diaspora community is leadership. The community is driven and followed by a leader who is selected only by the members bearing in mind that their problems will be heard, and the leader will make dynamic decisions. This is a very old tradition and has been practised generation after generation in the community. The agents in old

discourse are more traditional centric, therefore, tend to practice and focus on it. Moreover, leadership tradition in the community helps to unite and make a strong bond among its members. Therefore, the first generation agents in the diaspora community follow the tradition in the indigenous community. It gives the sense of security and strength and makes them valued in society.

Furthermore, the researcher observed that any issues regarding business and community are approached to the appropriate authority through the community leader. On the other hand, agents always seek assistance from the community leader to solve family and business conflicts in old discourse. Therefore, according to Bourdieu, it can be said that the community leaders act as bureaucrats in the community by not only instrumentalizing community or local government strategy but also explain and sometimes persuade it. How the researcher found the bureaucracy in the diaspora community will be explained later in this section of the study (Webb, Schirato and Danaher, 2002).

As it was earlier discussed about the role of Islam at the individual and community level, it is worth mentioning the role of Imam as a leader in the different aspects of the diaspora community. A significant time of working in the field of the family business and while carrying out interviews for the study in different settings, the researcher observed the motivating role of Imam in the community. In old discourse, the agents are more prone to follow the religion, and therefore, they have blind faith in them. In most cases, in old discourse, the agents' personal and professional issues are determined by the opinion of Imam. On the other hand, Imam also influences the agents' behaviour and attitude through the light of religion. Therefore, the researcher observed that senior agents always seek clarity about new ideas to introduce in the business to the Imam. In this way, Imam plays a crucial role as a

leader in the diaspora community and helps to navigate agents' habitus in the community. The core data reflects that the senior agents neglected and refused to accommodate social media in the business due to a lack of having positive influence from the community. Moreover, from the observation and the data, it is evident that the community and the community leader create the sets of values and understanding among the agents they experienced wisdom and status within the field. According to Bourdieu, those are called orthodoxy (Bourdieu, 1977). Therefore, in old discourse, agents show orthodox nature both in the family and the family business field.

Interestingly, the researcher observed an opposite ideology in the new discourse regarding community involvement and influence in personal life. Agents in new discourse mainly view the community as a hindrance to their progress. Therefore, in new discourse, the intergenerational clash is more often as the younger agents ignore the involvement of community opinion in their business matters. They believe that the community and its leadership are predominantly religious and traditionally driven and led by the view of the senior agents. Furthermore, in old discourse, community involvement causes the capital of containment, which catalyzes the intergenerational conflicts and gives to the new level (Jenkins, 2002).

After the habitus of the agents and the role of community in the diaspora, the study also focused on how business tentacles of this ultra-conservatism of Islamic culture and community shape and govern the practices and sanction those acceptable capitals. This ultra-conservatism is an old discourse that is disrupted with this age of acceleration and digital technologies (Ignatow and Robinson, 2017). Islamic culture sometimes denies and restricts the acceptance and adoption of modern inventions

into everyday life. Due to the Islamic faith ingrained deeply from childhood and put into the invisible spectacles through which agents take all decisions.

The data also reflects the different forms of capital and their conversion throughout the study. The Agents in the Muslim diaspora family businesses hold different forms of capital. The data reflects that the capital they are having has two major facts. On the one hand, agents are mostly entrepreneurial, and the entrepreneurial spirit they are having is old in nature, on the other. In old discourse, the first generation agents were used to choose entrepreneurship as a profession because of their religious faith. According to Islam, business is a more noble profession than any other profession, and moreover, Islamic culture prefers and influences entrepreneurialism in the community. Therefore, generation after generation, agents in this community grew up in the business environment for a long time. As the agents in the old discourse spent most of the time in this culture, their beliefs and idea are manipulated by religious regulations.

On the other hand, the young Scot-Asian agents grew up in a dual environment with strong family tradition inside and an open and modern atmosphere outside. They have mixed habitus, which is less likely to follow the religious and traditional norms in day to day life. The young agents live in 'cultures of co-created convergence' that are accessible beyond the strictures of family and community, and so is a product of a dual habitus lived and virtual (Bourdieu, 1985).

In diaspora, entrepreneurship and digital discourse, the male is the boss and power is distributed through hierarchy like a grandfather, father and so on. However, their entrepreneurial spirit is of an old discourse that is learned from the past. They promote or dictate how business and business relationships are conducted based on

a worldview that is increasingly outmoded or outdated. They moved to the new country for a better future and created a diaspora community where family, care, support, trust and religion are at their core. However, ironically, this ultra-conservative old discourse, while it enabled past prosperity, stifled the adoption of the new digital discourse and its capitals, which are essential for the future.

5.0 CONCLUSION

The following conclusions chapter will review the thesis overall, its core aspects and contributions to knowledge. Again it is important to reiterate the aim of the study, which was to:

Critically explore how cultural heritage impacts the utilisation of the power and potential of social media as a business strategy for growth among small food retail businesses.

However, and given this is the concluding chapter, it seems apposite at this time to briefly reflect upon the research journey undertaken. After completing the master's degree in digital marketing, the researcher moved back into the field of a family

business, where he had developed extensive work experience. Interestingly, during work and discussions with several business owners, resistance, or general negativity, was expressed to the development of forms of digital marketing. This resistance to new modes of knowledge, skills and overall digital marketing strategy was a revelation and seemed irrational. Therefore, following discussions with the current Director of Studies, it became clear that this area could become a potential focus for a DBA study.

Over time the aim of the thesis became centred on understanding the cultural protocols, or later habitus, field and capitals that were fundamental to family businesses from the South Asian Muslim diaspora community. Moreover, this study also reflected the knowledge and views of different agents in the family business about social media as new technology and business strategy and its acceptance and implementation in the business.

Therefore, from this background rationale and its aim and focus on the diaspora community's cultural and traditional norms, it was essential to underpin the study with foundational literature. Again, given the aim, literature coverage included examining the concept of social media with a definition and its revolution. The use of social media in a different organisational context and its pros and cons were discussed in detail to understand the readers. The world has seen the rise of social media since the beginning of the twenty-first century as a ubiquitous form of engagement in the 'Networked society' (Vodanovich, Sundaram and Myers, 2010; Harris, Rae and Misner, 2012). It was evident that social media was not restricted to personal use (Macnamara and Zerfass, 2012). Nowadays, businesses and organisations, regardless of their size and forms, are moving towards different types of social media as a business strategy to get its various benefits (SI, 2015; Nah and

Saxton, 2012). Furthermore, social media became a new marketing tool in this modern age for the business and got dynamic roles in different aspects of the business, which ranges from communication to trust-building with the consumers (Ainin et al., 2015; Weber, 2013).

At the beginning of the social media revolution in business and organisation, only large-sized businesses were more prone to use social media because of the costs and resources required to maintain it (Kapurubandara, 2009). However, this trend has come to an end as the rapidly changing nature of the businesses who now can develop cloud presence, and so cloud commerce is democratised (Attaran and Woods, 2018) and social media has reached individual levels, and people from all walks can access with minimal skills and knowledge because all are very born global now (Hansen, Schneiderman and Smith, 2011). These social media criteria have allowed any size and type of business to implement it into their operation. As a result, businesses worldwide have been progressively moving to utilise the advantages of different forms of social media according to their target customers (McGrath, 2013). Therefore, big companies were no longer the beneficiary of it, and small and medium-sized businesses have started moving in the digital platforms to remain in the competition (Meske and Stieglitz, 2013; Wamba and Carter, 2014).

Within the literature, the area of cultural diaspora, mainly the south Asian networked communities and their nature of businesses, was of central importance. Moreover, the literature highlighted how ethnic entrepreneurship and the various theories and models surrounding this area are essential in understanding the diaspora family business (Elo, et al., 2018). However, while of central importance, this area of literature also highlighted a gap in the workings embodied dynamics of cultural diaspora, family business and its wider community context. This study focused on

the family businesses run by the South Asian diaspora, who were mainly from the Islamic faith. Islam provides a complete way of life as they believed blindly (Ahmed and Rahman, 2015). The power of Islam was so strong that it penetrated their family and national culture at the root level (Timol, 2020). The family members in this diaspora community were more culturally and traditionally driven in day to day activities in their new country of residence (Williams, 2006). As they were religiously practising, Islamic rules and regulations also played a significant role along with the cultural heritage in the family (Franceschelli and O'Brien, 2014).

Moreover, as the family members run the businesses and therefore, family and professional values were difficult to differentiate (Gibb Dyer Jr, 2006). As a result, traditions and culture influenced the business the way it does to the family. Therefore, the decision-making process in the family business is largely influenced by the Islamic cultural heritage (Jejeebhoy and Sathar, 2001). This iconic criterion gave the importance of the study because, like diasporic family businesses, indigenous people become less influenced by their culture and traditions.

Nevertheless, given the aim and centrality of Islamic culture and diaspora, the study demanded a novel methodology. The power of Islam had given the diaspora community a new shape and identity in the new country of residence. It was evident that they were more traditional than the people who lived in their own country. Moreover, Islam controlled every aspect of life. The entrepreneurial spirit in the diaspora community was the result of one of the core Islamic beliefs that drove them to engage in the businesses (Botoeva, 2018). The workaholic nature gave them a new identity in the community and made them unique from others (Niaz and Nasir, 2018). The researcher worked in this field over a long period and noticed how conservative they were. It was difficult for indigenous white people to enter the

diaspora community and explore such a type of study. However, the researcher from the same geographical area and culture benefited from working on this study. Moreover, the researcher's culture, language, and religion gave comfort to the members of the diaspora family's own business to open up and share their understanding of the digital platforms in the business. Therefore, to get a clear understanding of the cultural heritage of the diaspora, the study demanded ethnographic nature of observation throughout the course, along with the unstructured interviews to get their deeper knowledge regarding the objectives of the study (Creswell, 2007). This novel methodology was supported by the conventional way of carrying out the study when required.

In this study, the researcher divided the aim into several objectives, including framing the study through technological development, exploration of the rise of social media and cultural diaspora, and family business entrepreneurship of a medium-sized business network. To shed light on those areas of the study, the researcher marked the study as exploratory in nature. On the other hand, a researcher's philosophical stance towards the study had given direction in the study's theoretical assumption and helped select appropriate methods for the research (Ponterotto, 2005). In this study, the researcher adopted the Interpretivism paradigm, which helps to critically explore the impact of family culture and traditions on the strategic decision-making process about social media acceptance in the family business.

The Interpretivism stance of the researcher drove him to adopt the qualitative research design, which helps to get a deep perception of the cultural heritage of the South Asian diaspora family businesses (Denzin & Lincoln, 2005). The subjective nature of the qualitative method also facilitated understanding the views about social media as a business strategy in the family businesses as the different agents have

different perspectives on the matter. Through qualitative research, the design could be done through different types of research strategies, in particular, in this study, the researcher chosen the case study as a research strategy because it can justify critical thinking by expanding the understanding, experiences and beliefs about the core aspects of the study (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2016). Moreover, the researcher has been working in the diasporic family business over a significant period and belongs to the same region and religious belief, and therefore ethnographic observations also played an important role in designing research strategy.

In terms of data for this study, the researcher collected all primary data through unstructured interviews and ethnographic observations because of the explorative nature of the study. Those data collection techniques provided rich and personalised data, which gave the deeper understanding of the interviewee on social media into the business operations who were culturally and traditionally driven in their personal and professional life (Gray, 2014). Moreover, through those data collection techniques, the researcher was able to collect reliable, credible and accurate information required to fulfil the research objectives. The researcher took 12 face to face interviews along with the ethnographic observations for this study. It is important to stress that these interviews were conducted over months and worked across those within the family business. Given the nature of the diaspora family business and the dynamics of conducting business, it was essential to reduce the impact on the business practices and interact at their convenience. Moreover, ethnography helped map the area, business practices and presence online and depth of digital engagement or not.

Impartial and vigorous results of the study depend on the appropriate selection of the sampling strategy. The researcher adopted non-probability purposive sampling for this study. Here, a small number of samples were selected on purpose based on rich and in-depth information (Creswell, 2007). As the study focused on sensitive issues like family culture and how it influenced daily activities, snowball sampling was appropriate for the study. The researcher identified one knowledge of insiders who act as the research participants' locator (Gray, 2014). Moreover, SIMD was used to select the businesses in different parts of Glasgow, and with the help of that participant locator, the researcher reached the participants. In this way, Snowball sampling gave active control to the researcher (Biernacki and Waldorf, 1981).

The researcher adopted thematic analysis in this study for the qualitative data collected through unstructured interviews and ethnographic participant observations. Several themes were identified from the data regarding the research objectives, producing a patterned meaning inside the data. The data captured six themes for the study, and they were cultural diaspora: framing the habitus; discourse of disruption; technophobia and influencer network; ethnic enclaves: cultural cryostasis and capitals of containment; privilege and poverty: digital adoption and finally diaspora, entrepreneurship and digital discourse: the paradox of Patriarchy and prosperity.

This study drew upon the work of French sociologist Pierre Bourdieu as a theoretical lens to analyse the themes derived from the data. First, Bourdieusian key notions of habitus, field and capitals were used to understand the diaspora community's family, culture and traditions, and entrepreneurial spirit (Bourdieu, 1990b). Moreover, the Bourdieusian concept of field explains family as an obvious field of reproduction where agents' dispositions are developed (Bourdieu, 1985). In addition, habitus directs how agents act out in the different fields like retail food business with the

dispositions acquired and developed in the family, and capitals enable the agents in the field for power struggle which they gained over a time (Jenkins, 2002).

Businesses run traditionally by the family also recognised the importance of social media in the business though it is late. However, family firms were more concerned about their values and traditions, which they earned over the years (Donnelley, 1988). Therefore, anything new in the business was carefully examined through a cultural lens so that the family values and traditions remain unchallenged. This trend was visible globally. However, compared to the family businesses in developing countries were still behind in the understanding and acceptance of different forms of social media platforms into their businesses than their rich and developed counterparts (Ahmad, Ahmad, and Bakar, 2018). Moreover, in the developed countries, though the technologies were at the doorsteps, the native family business was more advanced in implementing social media platforms than the diasporic family's business.

The South Asian diaspora in the UK has a long history (Vertovec, 1997). People from the Asian subcontinent have been contributing to the economy to a larger extent in the different sectors (Seaman, Bent and Unis, 2016a). The agents, particularly the first generation, had a high entrepreneurial spirit and had been involved in the business when they moved to their new country of residence for a better life (Riddle and Brinkerhoff, 2011). It is evident in Glasgow, as this was the context of the study, the Pakistani Muslim community got involved in the food and retail industry than any other sorts of business run by the diaspora community, i.e. Indian community in the curry industry, the Chinese diaspora in Chinese takeaways (Niaz and Nasir, 2018). Therefore, following this rationale underpinning literature and methodology, the study asserts five contributions to knowledge.

Firstly, this study adopted a unique methodology and analytical approach to the field under investigation. Although applied to other fields of study, Bourdieu, with a fieldwork ethnography, has never been adopted and applied to the area of Islamic, family business, and digital media before (Webb, Schirato and Danaher, 2002). In this study, an Islamic cultural lens was used at a local level in Islamic family business to get inside the dynamics of everyday entrepreneurship (Ramadani, et al., 2015). The study found that religious faith was an overarching matter of individuals' daily lives in the south Asian diaspora community (Franceschelli, 2016). In this context of the study, the small food retail businesses ran by the Muslim community where the Islamic faith and its regulations were at the centre (Seaman, Bent and Unis, 2016b). The strong Islamic faith shaped the culture and traditions of the community as a whole which was evident across the whole study. The diaspora community has a high entrepreneurial spirit due to their deep belief in the religious faith (Gilliat-Ray, 2011).

Moreover, the Islamic faith deeply influenced the eating habits, dressings, manners, role of females in the community and family level, celebrations, professional and career choices, and new ideas and technologies (Al-Kaysi, 2015). Therefore, the family members were raised in the constructed environment, and the habitus of this community became more structured than the habitus in the indigenous community (Crossley, 2003). However, the habitus of the second generation in the family got mixed dispositions and was less structured than their predecessors (Charles, Davies and Harris, 2008). It was due to the first generation agents raised in a conservative environment and moved to the new country for a better future and their culture and traditions. As a result, the second generation was more Pakistani or Indian inside the family and more indigenous outside. These two types of agents in the study showed

different views about their own cultural and traditional beliefs. The conventional methodology alone could not investigate the research aim in depth. Without an ethnographic form of observation, it would be difficult to understand this Islamic culture and its influencing power.

Secondly, the Bourdieusian lens provided an analytical contribution unravelling the clash between cultural and religious tradition and resistance to new digital media for entrepreneurial development and sustainable growth. The study revealed the intergenerational clash in the field of the family business as a day to day issue where the entrepreneurial spirit of the first generation was challenged by the young second-generation agents (Arcand, 2012). At this age of accelerations, businesses were moving quickly to digital platforms because of the demand of time (Teece and Linden, 2017). This was recognised by the second generation agents due to their institutional and techno-capitals and put pressure on the father or grandfather for the acceptance and implementations in the business, which caused the tensions in the field of the family business. However, this global trend of accelerated techno-culture like digital or online presence for cloud commerce growth for the sustainability in the competition was refuted by the lack of techno-capitals and hierarchical power of the senior agents in the family business. The Islamic family culture strongly followed the decisions from the patriarchal figure and ended up the intergenerational conflicts with no outcomes. As a result, the capital of self-preservation in the senior agents led to self-destruction.

Thirdly, insight into the inner workings of diaspora communities and the inter-relationship with the family business and its power dynamics, Islamic community, Patriarchy, gender etc. The power of the culture and community played a crucial role in the field of the family business (Janjuha-Jivraj and Woods, 2002), which was also

evident throughout the study. The culture of the South Asian Muslim diaspora drove them to create a nexus in the new environment and believed to act as power and protection from the outsiders. This overly protected nature of the community became the culture and caused resistance to the appropriation and application of digital technologies for customer engagement, business growth and sustainability. Therefore this paradox of proximity resulted from their own cultures that degraded the entrepreneurial spirit in the second generation in the family business. (Karadağ, 2011). Moreover, the tradition of living together as a community created a comfort zone for the senior agents and allowed them to cultivate "cultural reproduction" (Kraaykamp and Van Eijck, 2010, p.215).and caused the resistance of digital media as a business strategy.

Fourthly, the impact, appropriation and resistance to new digital technologies within traditional Islamic and diaspora communities. Businesses have started moving to digital platforms and making life easier for consumers (Appel et al., 2019). This transformation is evident as we see on the high street how social media have become a new modern age or marketing phenomenon to drive businesses into the future (Wrigley and Lumbar, 2014). However, family businesses, particularly from the South Asian diaspora, showed the opposite scenario. The ultra-conservative traditions wrapped up with the unchallenged Islamic faith and the lack of appropriate capital denied the welcoming of digital commerce in the family business. It was mainly due to the old discourse where the male was the boss and power was distributed from grandfather, father, and more powerful than the new discourse. This patriarchal power and gender dominance were considered a family culture and supported by the Islamic belief (Kandiyoti, 2008). Therefore, the entrepreneurial spirit of an old discourse that learned of the past was considered a cultural heritage.

Though they were privileged to dictate the business and business relationship based on the worldview that was out of date, their action was getting challenged by the young generations in the family.

Interestingly, in the new discourse, the second generation got strong institutional and techno-capitals and held an advantageous position in the business; however, their argument about social media adoption was cancelled and refuted by the power of Patriarchy. This was one of the key features in the culture of the diaspora family's own business, which was evident throughout the study's findings. The impact of resisting the digital platforms was getting serious. It caused competition in the market and demotivated the next generation to come into this trade.

Fifthly, it presents a contribution to the diaspora and the digital transformation of business. This study revealed how diaspora communities solidify and intensify identity as they move from home to new countries. While this is not unusual in and of itself, this study critically highlights how the diaspora is compelled to clash with this age of acceleration and new digital technologies. Essentially the study argues that diaspora, in having to develop and sustain and core identity, is premised upon an intensified tradition, which establishes an auto-response or resistance to new modes of living, working, or in this case, digital entrepreneurship and commerce. Moreover, the study accentuated cultural and religious identity throughout the diaspora. Echoing other diasporic communities, the Islamic diaspora of this study reflected an intensification of identity through the development and promotion of traditional Islamic norms and behaviours (Grilles, 2004); the habitus and capitals of the Islamic community being transmitted, performed and embodied as a mirroring religious observance and piety (Mellor and Shilling, 2014). Islamic culture and doctrine are woven throughout the fabric of Islamic life. A 24/7 doctrinal gaze permeates and

networks within and across the community, the mosque, family structures and business operations, Islamic habitus and capitals are reinforced daily rituals of observance and community engagement.

The other core finding of this study was the Islamic diaspora and its identity, which accentuated cultural and religious identity throughout the diaspora. Moreover, the Islamic habitus and capitals were reinforced in the daily rituals of observance and community engagement.

Before moving to the study's recommendations, it would be amiss of this study not to mention the impact and importance of Coronavirus disease-19 (COVID-19) or COVID-19 crisis. While carrying out the research, the COVID-19 has become a global pandemic, highlighting a series of lessons for all businesses and how they now have to operate (Bartik, et al., 2020). More interestingly, it is argued that the recent coronavirus pandemic has accentuated the aim, data, and critical contributions argued in the data analysis chapter. COVID-19 crisis places a glaring gaze on the businesses and focus of this study. This global crisis has unmasked the dynamic and intergenerational conflicts in the South Asian diasporic family businesses.

During the crisis period, all businesses were forced to shut; however, those operating online took advantage. Therefore, other businesses also started to take their business online for survival (Liguori and Pittz, 2020). However, again in this period, Asian diasporic family businesses have failed to grasp the opportunity. It is due to the senior agents who were holding the doxic attitude of a traditional habitus and engrained capitals and were unwilling to accept the changes in the business environment. It reflected the existence of misrecognition (Jenkins, 2002) in the Asian

culture. Moreover, the crisis gave fuel to the clashes between the two generations. The younger agents raised the conflicts to break the resistance from their senior counterparts.

COVID-19 crisis also revealed that all the cultural and traditional norms were human-made constructs, and they can be reconstructed. The first-generation agents were cryostasis culturally and showed rejection of anything new for the sake of family culture values that might be beneficial for their business. Moreover, their capitals of containment oppressed the youth by highlighting that it was all about maintaining the identity and claiming the 'truth' or the 'real' of south-Asian cultural enclaves or diaspora. However, it was all a construct, and social media showed us by moving the businesses from physical to online world or cloud. Finally, the crisis pointed out the false claim that the senior agents were nourishing and practising throughout their lives—the COVID crisis made possible, which young generations have been fighting over the years. The Koran or biblical story of NOAH can be served to summarise this situation. Here COVID resembles a flood. The hierarchical position has superseded the voice of young generations in the family, but disaster has finally come.

The global pandemic also gave a new role to the community and religious leaders in the community. As the study has gone through the pandemic, the community leaders acted professionally on time regarding the crisis. Moreover, the government used the community leader and the Imam as intermediaries between the government and the diaspora community to implement the health and safety policies and introduce and encourage people to work remotely online. According to the Bourdieusian theory, community leaders act like bureaucrats who create a "state nobility" (Webb, Danaher and Schirato, 2002, p.x) in the community. The crisis revealed the double standard of the community leaders, who are also the patriarchal figure of their family business.

In other words, the pandemic put the old discourse under an intensifying gaze and showed its weakness. Therefore, the ongoing crisis accelerated the change in the young agents in the family. Scot-Asian will challenge even more with the senior agents to embrace digital new ways of doing business.

The COVID-19 crisis also accelerated and changed shopping behaviour. As a result, people were moving more to the online platform for their daily necessities, and therefore the crisis forced the local family businesses to wake up to new ways as the value of the old world was severely reduced (Hoekstra and Leeflang, 2020). Due to the crisis, the local businesses were getting less income due to the less custom (Kalogiannidis, 2020). The values of different types of social media platforms and delivery systems had gone up. Therefore, the South Asian Muslim diasporic family businesses can say that the 'square wheels have come off the cart'. Their tradition faced new challenges, and it was not COVID that forced them to look to the 'round wheels'- social media or techno capital and the community leaders who act as a 'business imam'. Once one of them accepts a new digital form of business strategy, the rest will do it. As a result, human-made ideas and beliefs come tumbling down.

The critical point to remember for this study is, while it seemed all about the different forms of social media as a business strategy for growth; however, it was actually about the anxiety of acceleration that this 4.0 digital revolution is bringing to our life (Rainnie and Dean, 2020). It has been reshaping human beings silently and therefore challenging the cultures and communities surrounding them (Kasza, 2019). The fast inventions and rapid modification of the latest technologies are merging the natural and digital world, affecting all forms of business industries and overall economies (Hamelink, 1997). Even it challenges the ideas about the human and how it should be.

Several ideas and concepts emerged from the analysis of this study. First, worry and fear of the new 'techno capital' and the new logic of practice were that it opened the eyes of the south Asian diasporic 'community' to an external world or alternative life. This was the thing all religious and diaspora communities feared of the 'outside coming in' and 'destroying their identity. The basic problem was with the techno-capital that agents were being destroyed or reimagined from the inside out as much from the outside in. Therefore, the 'old ways' are no longer the thing that enabled success.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Given this study and its primary contributions discussed above, four recommendations can be put forward.

Firstly, this is a gendered analysis of entrepreneurship within the Islamic community. The study's findings suggest that the diaspora family businesses are predominantly male dominant and family and business decisions come from them. Moreover, females are only followers and have very little right to express any opinion regarding any issue. The diaspora family sees gendered dominance as their cultural norms and religious regulations where the female members grow up in this environment and embody and internalise the dispositions over the years. Both in family and business, males are in an authoritative position, and therefore the study has only figured out the male characteristics in the family business. On the other hand, the researcher occupies the habitus and male gender position and cannot see the female perspective. As a result, the study leaves scope for future research to

understand the female perspective within the South Asian Islamic diaspora community.

Secondly, this study reflects the Islamic patriarchy in the diasporic family business. The findings of the study highlight that religious belief becomes a part of the cultural heritage of the South Asian diasporic family where Islam crowned male like father or grandfather as a boss of the family and family own business. Moreover, this religious belief creates and reproduces patriarchal practices in the family. Therefore, this study gives a view about the role of patriarchy in both the field of family and the field of the family business. This study may help the other nationals who want to work with South Asian Islamic diaspora families by knowing Islamic patriarchy. It is important to highlight here that the study's finding also shows that the patriarchal entrepreneurial spirit has become old fashioned as they learned it long ago and never being updated according to the need. As a result, their old mode of operation is being challenged by the digital and technological revolution in the business industry and the institutional and techno-capital of the young family members. As the study was on the South Asian diaspora community in the UK, the future study can be done on the other community to explore their patriarchal role in the family business.

Thirdly, the study can be used as a cultural interpreter. The study's findings give the fact that how South Asian Muslim culture and religion drives the family members accordingly. Moreover, it is worth mentioning that two discourses are running in parallel, and both have their language as the researcher is from the same cultural background and therefore gets the advantage to enter and work with the family tradition. Therefore, this research work can be used as an interpretation handbook of Islamic family culture for the people from different religions and cultures who want to understand the business strategies of the South Asian diaspora family business.

Finally, the study is all about the views of digital commerce in South Asian family entrepreneurship. The study's outcome also reveals that the introduction of new technology or business strategy largely depends on the power and privilege of the traditional network of Asian patriarchy and social hierarchy. Moreover, the first generation in the family business is keener to legitimate maintaining the status quo by doing transgenerational reproduction. They have become successful because of the resistance against the new technology received from the local community and influencer networks. The study also finds that the inherent technophobia due to lack of knowledge acts as 'anti-capital and blocks the acceptance of social media into the business. This study can be recommended to other communities in the UK who want to collaborate their business digitally with South Asian family businesses.

This study discloses the different discourses in the diaspora family. In old discourse, the traditional disposition in the father or grandfathers' habitus and the religious practice in every aspect of life is characterised. Moreover, in old discourse, senior agents got habituated to refute new ideas like social media platforms for online marketing, which come from the young agents by the hierarchical position and to preserve cultural heritage. On the other side, in new discourse, young agents are becoming the key players in family and business. In new discourse, intergenerational clashes are more frequent due to the institutional and techno-capital gained by the young Scott-Asian agents. Therefore, possession of capital is the key element behind the power struggle in the family business. So, this research contributes to understanding the different discourses in the Muslim entrepreneurial spirit in the family business.

The rapid rise of social media is changing the way of life and attracting attention to a wide range of disciplines (Aral, Dellarocas and Godes, 2013). The diasporic family

business is not out of them. However, the generation divide in the diaspora family businesses causes hindrance and delays the digital adoption. This intergenerational conflict is evident throughout the study as the senior agents are more culturally and traditionally driven than their younger counterparts. In this study, the Bourdieusian notion of habitus, field and capitals criticise the cultural heritage of the South-Asian Muslim diasporic family business and show how the different generations see social media as a business strategy for their businesses.

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APPENDIX A

Ethics approval confirmation

25/06/2018

Dear Azhar Uddin Ahmed,

Your application 4959: DBA Thesis, submission 3705, has been approved by the Business and Enterprise SEC. You may now proceed with your study. If you wish to make any significant changes to the study you must seek the committee's approval before actioning them.

Good luck with your research.

Dr A Kourouklis

APPENDIX B

Participant Information Sheet

Title of the Study: Digital discourse and the power and paradox of patriarch in diaspora entrepreneurship

Name of the Degree: Doctor of Business Administration.

Name of the School: Graduate school, University of the West of Scotland.

I would like to invite you to take part in a research study. Before you decide you need to understand why the research is being done and what it involves. Please take time to read the following information carefully. Please feel free to ask questions if anything you read is not clear or would like more information. Take time to decide whether or not you want to take part.

Thank you for reading this.

My Name is Azhar Uddin Ahmed. I am a doctoral research student at the University of the West of Scotland. In my thesis, I have chosen to research how culture influences on using social media as a business strategy and growth among the small businesses. The Graduate School of the University of the West of Scotland is supporting me to undertake this project.

What is the purpose of this study?

Cultural traits (personal interests, motivation, faith and geographical location etc.) play an influencing power on making strategic business decisions especially for those who come from strong cultural backgrounds. There are not enough studies on how culture impacts the adoption of new technology usage particularly Social media for the business development and the growth of the small business settings. Nonetheless we can foresee a certain effects of national culture on new technology acceptance which consists of family values and behavioural patterns. On the other side, Social media is becoming a powerful podium of its predominant use and recognition, which provokes the businesses to use that platform as a new marketing tool to secure the position in the competitive business environment Users generating content and sharing content (web 2.0) are the two main concepts on which the social media phenomenon has primarily built. Social media ranges from Facebook, MySpace, Bebo (social networking sites), YouTube (audio-video sharing), Flickr (picture sharing), LinkedIn (business networking), Twitter (micro blog) and various others. Social media has immensely become an important marketing tool for small businesses because they do not have enough resources for marketing their

businesses. It is now becoming more vital for small businesses to assimilate the social media strategies so that firms can better feel the customers demand.

One survey identified that only 37 percent owners of small and local businesses described themselves competent regarding the usage of social media, whereas 32 percent believed that they have a fair enough knowledge about the subject, but needed more training and practical skills. 20 percent thought they had basic skills and 11 percent though they didn't know anything about social media marketing. So from here it can be said that there are some challenges to overcome if someone wants to implement social media for the business.

So the main focus of this study will be to explore and relate the social media as a new marketing strategy for the small business from the cultural point of view. The proposed objectives and questions must be answered to facilitate the development of a competent study. The study will address the following objectives:

- To provide an exploration of the rise of social media.
- To evaluate the social media adoption in the small food retail businesses.
- To explore the role of ethnic entrepreneurship in the cultural diaspora.
- To examine the impact of cultural heritage on social media as a business strategy.
- To critically analyse the relationship between diaspora culture and social media implementation in the business via Bourdieu's habitus, field and capital theory.

Do I have to take part?

Participation in this study is voluntary. I will describe the study and go through the information sheet, which will be given to you. I will then ask you to sign a consent form to show you agree to take part. At any time, you are free to withdraw without giving a reason. This will not affect the standard of care you receive.

What will I do in the project?

You will be required to attend one interview session which will cover topics including: understanding of social media, benefits and barriers of using social media for business strategy, factors associated with successfully adopting and implementing social media in the business setting, attitudes and cultural beliefs on using social media etc. The interview will take place in your organisational setting between May-July 2018 and each interview will last approximately 45mins to 1 hour. The interviews will be recorded on a Dictaphone and handwritten notes will be taken. In the review of guidelines by the University of the West of Scotland ethics committee (2016) principles have been taken to ensure respect for privacy, confidentiality and protection of data, honesty and integrity of information and preventing harm and risk to yourself and other participants taking part. However, if at any time during the process you feel uncomfortable answering a question you can decline to answer it.

Why have you been invited to take part?

You have been chosen to take part because you are responsible for carrying out strategic decisions in the business and most importantly you meet the nature of this study.

What are the potential risks to you in taking part?

During the research you will not be exposed to any physical, psychological or legal risk or harm. Interview questions have been structured in such a way so that your privacy will be protected and no pressure will be put on you to answer sensitive questions. All information pertaining to you as an individual and your organisation will be anonymised and kept confidential. The data you provide will not compromise your position in the organisation at any point in time.

What happens to the information in the project?

All information received will be stored securely in both locked cabinets and password protected computers. All references to individuals and organisations will be removed or given pseudonyms of data to be included within the submitted study, unless express permission has been given. All data will be destroyed on submission and successful completion of my Doctoral degree. The University of the West of Scotland is registered with the Information Commissioner's Office who implements the Data

Protection Act 1998. All personal data on participants will be processed in accordance with the provisions of the Data Protection Act 1998.

Thank you for reading this information – please ask any questions if you are unsure about what is written here.

What happens next?

If you are happy to be involved in this project, please sign the consent form to confirm this. If you do not wish to be involved, thank you very much for your time.

If desired, a feedback report can be sent once the investigation is complete.

This investigation was granted ethical approval by the University of the West of Scotland, School of Business ethics committee.

If you have any questions/concerns, during or after the investigation, or wish to contact an independent person to whom any questions may be directed or from whom further information may be sought please contact:

School Ethics Committee

School of Business and Enterprise

Paisley Campus

University of the West of Scotland,

High Street,

Paisley

PA1 2BE

Researcher Details: Azhar Uddin Ahmed

University of the West of Scotland

High street, Paisley. PA1 2BE.

Personal details withheld.

Director of studies: Dr. Matthew Frew

Personal details withheld.

University of the West of Scotland

High street, Paisley. PA1 2BE.

APPENDIX C

Consent Form

Title of the Study: A critical exploration of how cultural heritage impacts the utilization power and potential of social media as a business strategy among small food retail businesses in Glasgow.

Please initial box:

1. I confirm that I have read and understand the information

sheet dated for the above study with the relevant information and have had the opportunity to ask questions. c

2. I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw at any time, without giving any reason. c

3. I understand that my responses will be anonymised (unless I state otherwise) and that confidentiality will be ensured. c

4. I agree to take part in the above study. c

Your signature will certify that you have voluntarily decided to take part in this research study having read and understood the information in the sheet for participants. It will also certify that you have had adequate opportunity to discuss the study with the researcher and that all questions have been answered to your satisfaction.

Name of Participant:

Signature:

Date:

Name of researcher:

Signature:

Contact information:

Date:

APPENDIX D

Response to Joint Examiner Report

Dear Dr Alan Murray and Dr Amon Simba

Thank you for reviewing and giving invaluable comments on the thesis. In this part of the thesis, I have addressed your comments in the joint examiner report. Here, I

have mentioned the segment and page numbers according to your feedback to specify the changes that were made. This is done so that you might easily see the amendments concerning my first submission.

I am obliged to have the opportunity to work on these comments. Therefore, I have become more confident as the quality of the thesis has improved remarkably based on your feedback.

I believe that my amended thesis will fulfil your expectations, and thank you again for giving your valuable time for reviewing my thesis.

Kind regards

Azhar Uddin Ahmed

Examiners' comment:

- | |
|--|
| <ol style="list-style-type: none">1. The title of the thesis is too long; the candidate must consider reducing it to 12 words. |
|--|

Response:

Thank you for this helpful comment. The concern raised on this issue prompted me to reconsider the title of the thesis. Moreover, this guidance has allowed me to reconstruct the title more in a concise way with keeping in mind its length. . .

Page	Corrections made
Title page 1	Digital discourse and the power and paradox of patriarch in diaspora entrepreneurship

Examiners' comment:

2. The abstract needs to be rewritten to clearly articulate what the research is about and it has to be error free.

Response:

I highly appreciate the advice given regarding the abstract. Moreover, I have been given the opportunity to revise the abstract in a more clear way so that it can be more useful and easily understandable to the readers. I have taken necessary steps to restructure it according to the comment to fulfil the demands and expectations of the thesis.

Page	Corrections made
Page 4	Abstract has been amended to give more specific information about the thesis to the readers. Now it includes the full synopsis of the study altogether including research findings and its implications.

Examiners' comment:

3. I would suggest that a brief section on 'Key Definition of Terms' be included in the introduction to provide an explanation of some of the terms which the thesis draws heavily on e.g. habitus, capital and field and also some of the supporting theory such as illusio.

Response:

Thank you for the advice given regarding the Introduction chapter which is helpful.. This has given me the opportunity to work on the issues that I did not consider before. I believe that introducing a brief section on 'Key Definition of Terms' will be appropriate for this chapter and give the readers an explanation of some important terms that have been widely used throughout the thesis.

Page	Corrections made
1.4, pages 21-23	I have added a new section giving the definition of all the key terminology (e.g. Capital, field, habitus, illusio and so on) used in this thesis.

Examiners' comment:

4. The contribution of the work and the research gap are stated but I think more could have been made of these as, whilst the student is bringing new data to the field which is always welcome, I think that the application of the Bourdieusian framework as a means of understanding the complex

relationship between cultural heritage, social media use and the small business is something quite novel which deserves more reflection in order to highlight this.

Response:

Thank you for these important comments. The concern raised on those issues has enabled me to reassess the material in the introduction chapter. Therefore, the corrections that were done have permitted me to focus on the introduction section and produce the chapter more informative by highlighting the Bourdieusian framework and its relationship among the diaspora culture, social media and small businesses.

Page	Corrections made
1.0, Pages 18	I have added a couple of paragraphs in order to highlight the reason for considering the Bourdieusian framework as an analytical toolkit for this study. This justifies to the readers about the importance of Bourdieusian notion of habitus, field and capital theory to establish the relationship between family culture and social media implementation in the small business.

Examiners' comment:

5. The candidate needs to clearly articulate his theoretical argument(s) – in other words the foundation(s) on which he is building his research on, motivation and the gap in the current literature on SME research.

Response:

I highly appreciate the comments and instruction provided regarding the introductory chapter of the thesis, and also welcome the scope to improve the concerns. Though the motivation and the gap in the current literature on small and medium sized enterprise research were stated, after careful consideration I believe that it requires more attention. Therefore, I have tried to clearly articulate the foundations on which the foundation of my research is based for making plain to the readers.

Page	Corrections made
1.0, Page 17	I have outlined the gap in the current literature on SME research.
1.1, Page 19	I have revisited the context of the study and added the reason for choosing Glasgow and South-Asian diaspora families' own

	small food retail business as a context of the study.
--	---

Examiners' comment:

6. The research objectives must be SMART as opposed to being general.

Response:

<p>Thank you for this important comment. I appreciate the point raised on the research objectives which were general. I had chosen those objectives based on the title of the thesis. In another comment, advice being given to reconstruct the title and with the change made on the title, I have revised the aim and objectives that fulfilled the SMART (Specific, Measurable, Achievable, Realistic and Time-bound) goal.</p>
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Page	Corrections made
1.3, pages 20-21	In order to address the research objective more effectively, I have tried to provide a clearer and more robust "Research Aims and Objectives" section. Particularly, the language used is more specific in the way that these aims and objectives are communicated and meet the requirement of the comment.

Examiners' comment:

7. The literature review must clearly highlight the limitations of the current body of knowledge. This can be achieved by being more critical and evaluative in the way secondary data is analysed.

Response:

I have reviewed the literature section and highlighted gaps or oversights in the current literature, especially, in relation to South-Asian diaspora entrepreneurship. This moves the literature section from overly descriptive to more balanced and critically evaluative.

Page	Corrections made
2.1-2.7, pages 26-97	In order to highlight the limitation of the study, throughout the section, I was critical about the literature. Some places, I have introduced new paragraphs with the justification to make it clear to the reader why its inclusion is justifiable.

Examiners' comment:

8. The candidate needs to be clear on how the various concepts he covered in the literature come together. Specifically, how Bourdieu's ideas on habitus, culture and capital as the theoretical framework capture (or bring together) different themes debated in the literature review.

Response:

Thank you for the valuable comments. Upon reflection, I can see the requirement to be clearer on how the various concepts covered in the literature come together. This has allowed me to revisit the whole literature review of the study and to introduce a new subsection in the chapter focusing on Bourdieu's ideas on habitus, culture and capital as the theoretical framework that has captured different themes discussed in the literature review.

Example:

Page	Corrections made
2.9, pages 95-97	I have introduced a new segment in the literature review named 'SOCIAL MEDIA, SOUTH ASIAN DIASPORA FAMILY BUSINESS AND BOURDIEU'S THEORY'. In this

	segment, I have highlighted the importance of Bourdieusian habitus, field and capital theory in relation to social media, culture and entrepreneurship in the diaspora family business.
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Examiners' comment:

<p>9. Discussion in the methodology section needs to be customised to reflect what did as opposed to giving us a lecture on research methods.</p>

Response:

<p>I greatly appreciate the comment made on the research methodology chapter. The advice given on this chapter has allowed me to customise the section which were absent previously. Moreover, I have had the opportunity to highlight the methodology adopted for the study rather than describing all available possibilities.</p>
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Page	Corrections made
3.2, pages 100-101	I have attempted to write more clearly and specifically about the 'Nature of the study' for this thesis. Notably, language used here is more specific and informative. Now the section describes the

	<p>justification of why study fits into an exploratory nature and why it rejects the other types.</p>
<p>3.3, pages 101-104</p>	<p>The 'Research philosophy' section has been edited to be more concise. Firstly, I have mentioned why philosophy is important for the study followed by the types of philosophy available for the research. Secondly, I have pointed out why the Interpretivism paradigm is appropriate for this study. Lastly, I have justified why others are not appropriate for this study.</p>
<p>3.4, pages 104-105</p>	<p>Again revisited the 'Research approach' section and highlighted why the Inductive approach is important for the study over other approaches.</p>
<p>3.5, pages 105-106</p>	<p>The section 'Research design' highlights more explicit grounds for the designing qualitative method over quantitative and mixed method</p>
<p>3.6 and throughout</p>	<p>In the Research strategy section, I have highlighted the justification of choosing the case study along with the selection and execution of the case study. In the types of data and collection methods section, only unstructured interview and ethnographic observations are being highlighted from which the key data collected for this study. Again, the Sampling strategy section describes only the non-probability</p>

	purposive snowball sampling for the demand of the study.
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Examiners' comment:

<p>10. The quality of the grammar needs to be greatly improved and it is suggested that the services of a professional proofreading service be secured prior to final resubmission of the thesis.</p>

Response:

<p>I appreciate the comment made on the grammatical issue for this study. Given English is my second language, the nuances of English grammar can be difficult. Nevertheless, I have gone through the thesis, re-checked the work as directed, had it proofread by native speaker with corrections and re-read. Hopefully, this addresses the issues (detailed below) for the resubmission.</p>

Page	Corrections made
Throughout	Proof-reading done rigorously, used appropriate words where necessary.

Throughout	Added missing words and rectified the syntax errors.
Throughout	Checks made for consistency throughout: where applicable, restructured the passages.
Throughout	Checks made for consistency throughout: where applicable, changed in tense (Present, Present perfect and Past)

Examiners' comment:

11.A number of typos are also noted which should be addressed and also some minor errors which should be resolved

Response:

Thank you for these valuable comments. This has enabled me to check the typographical errors made throughout the study. Changes made throughout the study have allowed me not only to eliminate the typos but also upgrade the standard by resolving the minor errors.

Page	Corrections made
Throughout	Checks made for consistency throughout: where applicable, changed font style and size.
Throughout	Ensured page numbers are correct and matched to the table of content.
Throughout	Tables number and figures numbers have been checked and sequence has been maintained
Throughout	Referencing has been checked throughout and ensured that all are listed in the referencing list at the end.

Examiners' comment:

12. Some very long direct quotes were noted in the Bourdieusian discussion and these could be shortened without losing any impact or meaning.

Response:

I am thankful for the comment made on the Bourdieusian discussion section and also for giving the opportunity to do recommended amendments. Specifically, I welcome the opinion that the Bourdieusian discussion had long direct quotes and advised to short those quotes without losing any impact or meaning. This has inspired me to reconsider the long quotes stated in the relevant sections and allowed me to reduce the length of the quotations by keeping their meaning in place.

Page	Corrections made
2.8.1, page 74	Revisited the quote and significantly reduced its length.
2.8.2, page 79-80	Reviewed the long quote on the definition of habitus and remarkably shortened without losing the meaning.
2.8.2, pages 80-81	Readdressed the quote and shortened it according to the comment of examiners'.
2.8.2, page 84	Revisited the quote on habitus and shortened it.
2.8.2, page 85	Reconsidered the quote and reduced its length.
2.8.3, page 88	Reviewed the long quote on the definition of field and remarkably shortened without losing any impact..
2.8.3, page 89	Revisited the quote on field and compressed according to meet the requirement

2.8.3, page 90	Reconsidered the quote and reduced its length.

Examiners' comment:

13. Chapter 4 is very descriptive and needs to be more concise. The data items (interview quotes) are generally extremely lengthy and could be broken down more to get to the heart of the meaning you derive from them. I think the points you wish to highlight are at times lost in these very long quotes.

Response:

Thank you for the vital comments. The advice given has allowed me to reconsider the data items particularly interview quotes which are exceedingly wordy and makes the chapter very detailed. Therefore, the corrections that were done have permitted me not only to give a focus on the data cited in the chapter but also to reconstruct the data by breaking down more to specific and clear to get the heart of the meaning. Moreover, additional corrections have been made by removing unnecessary quotes where needed.

Page	Corrections made
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4.1, pages 127-130	Long quotes have been considerably shortened to convey only the meaning related to the theme. However, some quotes remained the same when it was deemed inevitable.
4.2, pages 135-139	Reconsidered the long interview data and cut down irrelevant parts without losing the meaning. However, some quotes remained the same when it was deemed inevitable.
4.3, pages 145-150	I have taken care to reduce the length of the interview quotes where required. The changes were made for improving the flow of the section and to reduce a 'long walk' into different points.
4.4, pages 156-160	The long direct quotes have been articulated in different ways to keep its length minimum. However, some quotes remained the same when it was deemed inevitable.
4.5, pages 165-170	Revisited the long quotes and shortened where it seems appropriate.

Examiners' comment:

14. Greater clarity could be achieved in Chapter 4 if some of the data was

presented in table form alongside the narrative discussion. In this vein it would also be useful to include a table here which triangulates and presents the key data in one place and which highlights the impact of your findings i.e. the key themes, the key data (relevant quotes), the frequency of occurrence of each key theme from the interviews e.g. 8 out of 10 respondents and a sample of the corresponding relevant literature.

Response:

I sincerely appreciate the guidance mentioned regarding chapter 4. and welcome the scope to address the issue by revisiting the chapter. This comment has enabled me to present the data in a tabular form which was absent earlier. Moreover, it allowed me to triangulate and present the key data in one place.

Page	Corrections made
4.1 to 4.5, pages 132-133,141-142,152-153,162-163 and 171-172.	I have added one table each in the first five subsections of chapter 4 highlighting the key theme, sub-theme, key data, frequency and sample of the corresponding literature review.

Examiners' comment:

15. In Chapter 5 there are large sections of narrative with no supporting theory

therefore the discussion is subjective. Comments here need to be supported by the literature and the data from the study.

Response:

I am greatly thankful for the comments and concern raised on the issue. On reflection, I can undoubtedly see the requirement of the amendment in chapter 5. I appreciate the opinion that the chapter contains several large sections of narrative without supporting theory. This has enabled me to revisit the chapter and therefore, I have added supporting theory in this section from the literature and the data from the study where required.

Page	Corrections made
5.0, Page 186 and throughout	All the paragraphs of this chapter have been reviewed to ensure that all narratives are supported by Literature used in this study where needed.
Throughout	The large narratives have been reviewed and supported by Bourdieusian theory where needed.

Examiners' comment:

16. The recommendations are essentially a series of fairly broad generalisations

and these need to be clear, meaningful and supported by the findings of the study.

Response:

Thank you for the valuable comment. The instruction given regarding the issues has enabled me to revisit the recommendations section in the conclusion chapter. I welcome the view that the recommendations are substantially a sequence of moderately broad generalisations. Firstly, this has motivated me to refocus the recommendations and make those more specific and meaningful. Secondly, this has allowed me to support the recommendations by the findings of the study. These amendments jointly with one another are aimed to provide clear recommendations for the readers.

Page	Corrections made
5.0, pages 200-202	All four recommendations have been reviewed and organised so that those are now clear and meaningful to the readers. Moreover, all recommendations are supported by the findings of the study. Summary of the recommendations are as follows:

	<ul style="list-style-type: none">● Firstly, this is a gendered analysis of entrepreneurship within the Islamic community. The study leaves scope to understand the female perspective within the South Asian Islamic diaspora community for future research.● Secondly, this study reflects the Islamic patriarchy in the diasporic family business. As the study was on the South Asian diaspora community in the UK, the future study can be done on the other community to explore their patriarchal role in the family business.● Thirdly, this research work is recommended as an interpretation handbook of Islamic family culture for the people from different religions and cultures who want to understand the business strategies of the South Asian diaspora family business.● Finally, the study is all about the views of digital commerce in South Asian family entrepreneurship. Therefore, this study can be recommended to other communities in the UK who want to collaborate their business digitally with South Asian family businesses.
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